

ALL-Ready Project Deliverable 2.3

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

Drivers of agroecology transition

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List of abbreviations

AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
LL	Living Lab
NCP	National Contact Point
OIA	Open Innovation Arrangement
RI	Research Infrastructure
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RI) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, degradation of soil and water quality.

The purpose of this report is to provide a synthesis of drivers of agroecology transition based on interviews with key informants in 23 different European countries (Turkey, the Netherlands, Switzerland, Slovakia, Serbia, Poland, Norway, Lichtenstein, Luxembourg, Lithuania, Latvia, Ireland, Iceland, Finland, Estonia, Denmark, Czech, Cyprus, Belgium, the United Kingdom, France, Germany and Hungary). The latter 5 countries are mapped jointly with the Coordination and Support Action AE4EU.

The current report (D2.3) is part of a series of reports under All-Ready WP2. Other deliverables of the WP include an outline of the assessment framework (D2.1), a report on funding mechanisms for agroecology initiatives (D2.2), Overview of agroecology living labs and research infrastructures in Europe (D2.4), Agroecology open Innovation: Best cases across Europe (D2.5) and Towards a network of agroecology living labs (D2.6).

Altogether these reports provide a part of the foundation for the preparation of the candidate Horizon Europe Partnership '*accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures*'. This report is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 presents the methodology that has been used by partners to acquire data based on national contact points and methodology applied in the compilation of results in this report.
- Chapter 3 presents a synthesis of stakeholders' perspectives on the drivers of agroecology transition. The chapter is organised in six sections each representing different perspectives on drivers for an agroecological transition.
- Chapter 4 summarises the main conclusions from the exercise.

2. Methodology

This report is written as a synthesis of 23 national reports that were prepared by partners based on a joint mapping exercise (the phase 1 survey described in D2.1 'Assessment Framework'). In this chapter we will initially describe the approach and content of the mapping exercise, secondly, we will describe the data that has been produced as a part of the mapping exercise, and finally, we describe our approach to the comparison of the individual national reports.

2.1 Mapping approach

The boundaries of the agroecology concept are wide, blurred and contested. However, the basic scope of the mapping task reflects the ALL-Ready project document, which stipulates a focus on agroecology projects and programmes, institutional mechanisms such as LLs, RIs, open innovation arrangements (OIA) and policies that affect agroecology, at primary production level. Based on criteria described in D2.1 - the All-Ready CSA has mapped the landscape in a transition context, i.e. the focus is on initiatives and the policies and institutional arrangements across Europe sustaining these initiatives. In this context we understand initiatives as activities involving stakeholders that are established with the purpose of promoting a transition towards agroecology. This was done with the ambition to gain an overview of the 'landscape' and understand drivers, barriers and incentives for innovation for agroecology transition.

To ensure comparability across the countries that are surveyed, the mapping exercise is based on a survey among key informants (national contact points, see below) providing an overview of country level implementation of regulatory frameworks, funding institutions as well as an overview of current national agroecology initiatives, LLs and RIs. This information constitutes indicators for (i) assessing levels of transition, barriers and drivers and (ii) inquiries into transition processes in selected national contexts.

National Contact Points (NCPs) were the main entry point for providing overviews of the national contexts. NCP's are, by the EC, considered essential components in the implementation of successive Framework Programmes, providing information and on-the-ground advice to potential applicants and beneficiaries (EC, 2022). NCP's have been singled out as key drivers for the establishment of local living labs as experimental and learning hubs in projects funded under Horizon Europe and are therefore considered highly relevant entry points to gain an overview of the national initiatives and experiences. However, while, the NCP's in the context of Horizon Europe are mainly civil servants, we have in this report adopted a somewhat wider definition that also includes informants from research and civil society, including NGO's. NCP's for this survey thus include case officers in ministries, researchers, and civil society.

Informants, many of which were proficient in English were selected on the basis of prominent positions within national agricultural knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS). NCP's from policy were identified, initially through FACCE-JPI, a Europe-wide initiative that gathers agroecology relevant research and research funding expertise. Further, contacts within the research sector were identified by exploring participants of agroecology related projects under Horizon 2020 and civil society (NGO) NCPs were identified through a combination of WP2 partners and internet searches.. Thereafter, snowballing allowed for the identification of further national contact points representing other stakeholders perspectives.

This constitutes a purposive sampling approach, where informants are selected because they have particular predefined characteristics that are needed in the sample. In other words, units are selected "on purpose", which is a preferred selection method in qualitative inquiries in which specialized knowledge is needed and where randomised sampling will not be

applicable due to a small sampling population. Further, since qualitative inquiries are time and resource consuming, it is important that informants were carefully selected to maximize the information gained and there is no room for a wide sample population as in a representative survey (Flyvbjerg, 2001).

NCPs were selected with the aim of covering the three main stakeholder domains in the countries. Therefore, they represent in-depth knowledge on the agricultural sector in their countries, although representing complementary perspectives for each country. Using these NCPs as key informants enabled the collection of information that we have analysed analytically, but not information that can be generalised statistically (see below).

Ensuring comparable information collected in the different national reports, an interview guide was designed for the joint mapping and a joint reporting template was provided (for further information see D2.1 Assessment Framework). The interview guide was based on characterisations and definitions of what constitutes agroecological production systems and agroecological LLs and RIs, prepared in WP1 (c.f. ALL-READY Deliverable 1.1 and 1.2 in particular). A combination of closed and open questions formed the basis of the interview guidelines. Closed questions (questions which can only be answered by selecting from a limited number of options) allowed for direct comparison across countries.

The open questions (questions that require more than one-word answers or choosing among limited options) provide a basis for interpreting replies, and for detailed characterisation of perspectives. This mix of methods aims to ensure a rich picture of the situation within the different countries. The interviews were completed either face-to-face, by phone or online, depending on local conditions. Furthermore, partners structured each interview according to the themes outlined below and planned for an open and explorative conversation (semi-structured). This enabled stakeholders to present their views and perceptions as openly as possible and inclusive towards unexpected inputs.

However, it is important to emphasise that the objective of this report is not to generalise results statistically beyond or even within the national contexts where they appear. Rather, the focus is on the processes and drivers behind agroecology transition. The emphasised issues that are brought forward in the national reports are important even when they only appear in one particular setting and not in others.

2.2 Data

To the extent possible, partners were recommended to conduct interviews with at least 3 NCPs, representing policymaking, research and practice, in each of the 23 countries to be mapped.

Table 1: The number, categories of informants for the national reports and partners responsible for the completing the national report.

	Partner	Public administration	Researcher/Scientist	NGO	Total (individuals)
Belgium	ILVO	2	2	0	4
Cyprus	Lifewatch	0	1	0	1
Czech	Ömki	0	2	1	3
Denmark	AU	1	2	0	3
Estonia	FIBL	3	1	1	4*
Finland	FIBL	0	2	1	2*
France	INRAE	2	1	0	3
Germany	Thunen	1	1	0	2

Hungary	Ömki	2	1	1	4
Iceland	AU	0	1	1	2
Ireland	Lifewatch	2	1	1	2*
Latvia	Thunen	1	2	1	3*
Lichtenstein	FIBL	0	0	1	1
Lithuania	Thunen	0	1	1	2
Luxembourg	FIBL	1	1	1	2*
Norway	FIBL	1	3	1	5
Poland	Sheffield	1	1	1	2*
Serbia	AU	1	1	0	1*
Slovakia	Ömki	3	0	0	3
Switzerland	FIBL	1	3	0	4
the Netherlands	FIBL	2	1	0	3
Turkey	INRAE	3	0	0	3
United Kingdom	Sheffield	0	2	1	3
Total		27	30	13	63

* indicate that at least one individual respondent features in several categories

The national reports are based on interviews with a total of 63 NCPs, representing different perspectives on the drivers of agroecology in the 23 countries (See table 1).

Although the total number of respondents and stakeholder categories diverge across and within countries, the selection broadly covers the diversity of European farming systems, as well as social and institutional contexts. However, for some countries, the number of NCPs is somewhat limited and does not include all NCP categories. However, again it is important to stress that the NCPs are informants with a deep and broad knowledge of the processes behind agroecological transition within the individual countries, hence, the limited sampling size does not constitute a major problem for the analysis of the data.

2.3 Data treatment

Reports from partners include qualitative and quantitative elements. This combination provides different types of information, offering a rich picture on the state of agroecology across countries and the drivers of agroecology transition. (Creswell, 2013). The qualitative and quantitative data were analysed in an iterative process providing complementary insights. The survey findings appear in tables, while open replies are used to deepen and discuss the insights and to highlight and unfold recurring themes. The tables containing replies to the closed questions represent an assessment of the national partners regarding the situation in the country or environmental zone based on the data acquired through the stocktake. We present quantitative elements using descriptive statistics of the mean value of responses aggregated at country scale and deliberately do not use advanced statistical models for the analysis as the total number of replies is low (N=63) and the contextual differences are notable across countries. Furthermore, analysis of the open replies were used to highlight recurrent themes and broaden perspectives of the closed questions. Themes were grouped and regrouped in a process of constant comparison, developing distinct categories that account for the entire data set (Corbin, 1998; Silverman, 2011).

The contents of the replies for the open questions differed slightly across national reports; therefore, in this report we have reorganised themes so they are presented in the same discussions, preventing redundancy. Further, replies to the open questions diverge across

countries. Therefore, we refrain from emphasising the country from where points originate as comments may also apply to other countries. The first part of the result presentation (Chapter 3) presents a range of general conclusions regarding stakeholders' perspectives on the drivers of agroecology transition, emphasising differences across the 23 countries. For a more detailed overview of the country specific situation, we refer to the Appendices (A-F), which feature a complete transcript of the national reports.

Furthermore, the environmental and institutional conditions differ substantially across national contexts which has implications for respondents' conceptualisations of agroecology and drivers of the agroecology transition, see for instance Metzger et al. (2005) and Klerkx, van Mierlo, and Leeuwis (2012); Knierim et al. (2015). In the current report, we broadly group countries in three European regions (North-western Europe, North-eastern Europe and Southern Europe (including Turkey)). These regions, however, should not be considered as a determining factor for how countries within the region have approached agroecology, but rather as a loose grouping of countries with somewhat comparable environmental and institutional conditions.

3. Results

This section outlines the outcome of the mapping exercise assessing the drivers of agroecology transition. Results are grouped according to the structure described in D2.1 Assessment framework. Thus, initially we outline the different perceptions of agroecology (section 3.1) and the extent of agroecology-based production practices (section 3.2). Subsequently, we analyse the importance of four categories of drivers, including, research and innovation systems (section 3.3), competencies (section 3.4), stakeholder involvement (section 3.5) and policy (section 3.6).

3.1 Perceptions of agroecology

The perception of agroecology differs substantially across the different European countries (see table 2). Within and across Europe there is variation in perceptions of agroecology and the importance of different dimensions of agroecology. Generally, the perception of agroecology as a scientific discipline tends to be of most importance in the North-Eastern parts of Europe. Further, agroecology as a social movement tends to be of less importance within countries in the northern parts of Europe, while it is more pronounced in the southern parts of Europe.

Analysis of the open replies adds some detail to this general picture. Below we summarised some of the themes that occurred recurrently in the national reports; for a detailed overview of specific countries, see Appendix A:

- The concept "agroecology" is widely reported to be unfamiliar according to NCPs and the concept is not formally recognised and codified in domestic regulation. Reports further stress that there are different perceptions of agroecology in use both within countries and across countries. Therefore, there are limited efforts in support of agroecology, although, reports from a number of countries stress that practices and management approaches which can be considered agroecology are more widely used and pursued in research.
- Although the three dimensions of agroecology are not found in all the countries surveyed, interviewees indicate that these three dimensions of agroecology should all be seen as important dimensions of agroecology and mutually constitutive driving forces. However, it is important to bear in mind that we interviewed experts in agroecology, who may represent a view influenced by academic debates.

- Although the importance of agroecology is growing, the qualitative replies emphasize that in most countries the concept is still of rather marginal importance. As a result, agroecology is often equated with organic farming or sustainability.
- There are opportunities for further advancing agroecology, particularly by linking up with some of the challenges that are neglected in many countries, such as social dimensions of sustainability and the systemic transdisciplinary elements of agroecology.

Table 2: Replies to the question: "How important are the different dimensions of agroecology in your country?"

		Practices	Science	Social Movements		
NW Europe	Belgium	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral		
	Denmark	Important	Important	Neutral		
	Finland	Important	Important	Neutral		
	Germany	Important	Neutral	Important		
	Iceland	Neutral	Neutral	Neutral		
	Ireland	Important	Important	Neutral		
	Lichtenstein	Important	Neutral	Less important		
	Luxembourg	Neutral	Less important	Less important		
	Norway	Important	Neutral	Neutral		
	the Netherlands	Important	Important	Important		
	Switzerland	Important	Important	Neutral		
	United Kingdom	Important	Neutral	Less important		
	NE Europe	Czech	Important	Neutral	Neutral	
Estonia		Important	Important	Neutral		
Hungary		Neutral	Neutral	Less important		
Latvia		Neutral	Neutral	Important		
Lithuania		Important	Neutral	Important		
Poland		Neutral	Neutral	Important		
Slovakia		Important	Important	Neutral		
S Europe	Cyprus	Less important	Neutral	Less important		
	France	Important	Important	Important		
	Serbia	Neutral	Important	Neutral		
	Turkey	Important	Important	Neutral		
	Average	Important	Neutral	Neutral		
		Very important	Important	Neutral	Less important	Unimportant

3.2 The extent of agroecology-based practices within the country

Although the agroecology concept is generally not well recognised as outlined above, the data suggest that a number of agroecological practices are still widely used among practitioners in the surveyed countries (see table 3). Some agroecological principles/practices feature more prominently than others and are also more widely used in certain environmental zones. For instance, integrated pest management and biological control is very important in many European countries, while wetland restoration using paludiculture is of less importance. Further, fertiliser and nutrient management appear prominent in the North-western part of Europe. While mixed cropping systems and diversified crop rotation as well as sustainable water management, have a particular focus in Southern Europe.

With respect to "Other" important practices, several items are mentioned particularly by respondents from countries in the northern part of Europe. The list of practices mentioned include practices that relate to the socio-economic aspects of agroecology (Community

Supported Agriculture, Social Farming, short supply chains and producer-consumer associations). Additionally, a range of agronomic practices are also reported (e.g. Permaculture, regenerative agriculture, agroforestry and extensive grazing). Further, respondents mention the need to also include measures and practices that are relevant for livestock producers.

Analysis of the country reports adds some detail to this general picture. Below we summarised some of the themes that occurred recurrently in the national reports; for a detailed overview of specific countries, see Appendix B:

- The extent to which the different agricultural practices are adopted vary significantly within countries and depends both on the configuration of the farming systems as well as variations in soils and climatic conditions. Typically, a range of national considerations and challenges are important in terms of which specific agroecological practices are adopted and supported by local governments.
- Several reports stress that although some of the practices hold potential, the novelty of some of the practices (for instance, wetland restoration with paludiculture) mean that they are less applied at the moment.
- Interest in agroecological practices is mostly reported as present amongst practitioners, and in several countries the focus on agroecology is much less pronounced in science and research programmes.
- When agroecological practices are applied, they are often practiced by organic farmers and/or small-scale farms in marginal areas. However, agroecological practices are also often associated with nature and biodiversity protection, for instance used in response to particular needs in the context of national parks or recreational areas.
- In certain areas some of the agroecological practices are enforced in regulation supporting groundwater protection or specifically appointed natural areas. This for instance includes no-tillage, biodiversity preservation, and cover crops.
- For practitioners, economic considerations play an important role in the design and adoption of farming practices. Thus, the availability of subsidy schemes is very important for the adoption of agroecological practices.
- National-level resource constraints mean that the dissemination of such agroecological practices is less developed than it could be if further resources were employed.

Table 3: Replies to the question: "How commonly applied are the following agroecological principles and/or agroecology-based practices in your country?"

		Integrated Pest Management and Biological Control	Conservation Tillage	Mixed Cropping Systems	Diversified Crop Rotation	Cover Crops	Fertiliser and Nutrient Management Efficiency/recycling	Biodiversity Preservation	Circularity in Biomass Utilisation	Wetland Restoration with Paludiculture	Sustainable Water Management	Other
NW Europe	Belgium											
	Denmark											
	Finland											
	Germany											
	Iceland											
	Ireland											
	Lichtenstein											
	Luxembourg											
	Norway											
	the Netherlands											
	Switzerland											
United Kingdom												
NE Europe	Czech											
	Estonia											
	Hungary											
	Latvia											
	Lithuania											
	Poland											
	Slovakia											
S Europe	Cyprus											
	France											
	Serbia											
	Turkey											
Average												
		Very common	Common	Neutral	Somewhat common	Unusual	No data					

3.3 Research and innovation systems in support of agroecology

Respondents' assessments of current RIs generally indicate that RIs are sufficiently attuned to support the agroecology transition in most of the countries reported in the mapping exercise (see table 4). However, for certain countries this is not the case, like Germany and Luxemburg. With respect to financial resources allocated for research into agroecologically based practices, however, respondents from a majority of countries stress that funds are lacking, indicating that there may be constraints in using the RIs for dedicated research into agroecology transition. On-farm experimentation is generally used in research activities, although this is not the case for all countries.

Analysis of the country reports adds some detail to this general picture. Below we summarised some of the themes that occurred recurrently in the national reports; for a detailed overview of specific countries, see Appendix C:

- If policy ambitions are lacking, then it is difficult to attract funding for research regarding agroecology transition. In a range of countries, interdisciplinary research on agroecology transition is often not prioritised. Rather, priority research includes single-disciplinary projects which promotes productivity-oriented research, with only limited attention to the negative impacts of productivity-focused farming systems.
- A challenge for the research and innovations system is also a lack of systems thinking and transdisciplinary thinking within the relevant research communities. This means that it is difficult to properly reflect the holistic perspective of agroecology transition and improve the connection between different fields of research. In addition, researchers often neglect multi-actor projects and stakeholder involvement in research projects, because this is time and resource consuming. Respondents often stressed, however, that in their opinion improving stakeholder involvement would strengthen research projects.
- Generally, the involvement of end-users is stressed as an important element for research into agroecology transition. However, for some countries, particularly in the eastern and southern part of Europe a poor relationship between farmers and the research community is also reported as a hindrance to further increasing and improving stakeholders' involvement in research projects. An important shortcoming is that research projects are often not evaluated based on their ability to deliver solutions to practitioners and to facilitate the agroecological transition. This contributes to the research-practitioner disconnect.
- Several national reports also highlight the short-term duration of research projects and the lack of dedicated research programs on agroecology as a hindrance to research. Often, research into the agroecological transition requires a longer temporal horizon as issues are complex, systemic and need the coordination of multiple stakeholders. A number of reports suggest that there is little state funded research into agroecological transition, suggesting that European funds are essential for carrying out such work nationally.
- Furthermore, several national reports emphasise that particularly the social dimension of agroecology is often neglected in research projects, which is an important hindrance to the adoption and successful implementation of real-life solutions in many agri-food systems.

Table 4: Replies to the question: "To which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding research and innovation systems in support of agroecology in your country?"

		Research infrastructures (research facilities) are sufficiently attuned to support agroecological transition	Research programs have focus on agroecological transition	Sufficient financial resources are allocated for research into agroecology-based practices	Farmers needs in an agroecological transition are sufficiently reflected in current research activities	Living labs and other forms of multi-actor involvement are used in agroecological research and innovation	On farm experimentation is often applied in research activities
NW Europe	Belgium						
	Denmark						
	Finland						
	Germany						
	Iceland						
	Ireland						
	Lichtenstein						
	Luxembourg						
	Norway						
	the Netherlands						
	Switzerland						
	United Kingdom						
NE Europe	Czech						
	Hungary						
	Latvia						
	Lithuania						
	Estonia						
	Poland						
	Slovakia						
S Europe	Cyprus						
	France						
	Serbia						
	Turkey						
Average							
To a high extent	To some extent	Neutral	To a limited extent	Not at all	No Data		

3.4 Competencies for an agroecological transition

Competencies reflect actor's capability to alter their practice and are thus an important foundation for an agroecology transition. Given the use of key informant interviews we focus on the functional aspect of competencies (for an overview, see: Le Deist & Winterton, 2005). Overall, the competencies needed to achieve the agroecology transition are unequally developed in different European countries (see table 5). In some of the Northwest-European countries, competencies are assessed to be well developed, particularly in Denmark, Norway and the Netherlands. Beyond, competencies are assessed to be somewhat less developed, particularly in a range of Northeast-European countries as well as Cyprus and Turkey.

Analysis of the country reports adds some detail to this general picture. Below we summarised some of the themes that occurred recurrently in the national reports; for a detailed overview of specific countries, see Appendix D:

- With respect to capacity building, reports suggest that agroecology should be seen as a knowledge intensive form of production, as opposed to an input intensive one. In some countries, vocational training, knowledge networks and advisory service are described as well developed. Nonetheless, these facilities are unable to fulfil some of the specific needs related to agroecology transition and offer limited insights into other alternative modes of farming. This is often not what is requested by the younger cohort of farmers, who are interested in the systemic and transdisciplinary aspects of agroecology as well as some of the more specific agricultural practices. Therefore, with respect to agroecology, reports suggest that training and dissemination primarily take place in more small scale and informal networks, including social media, beyond conventional advisory service.
- The composition of the farm advisory service diverge quite substantially across the countries surveyed. While many private and cooperatively owned advisory services are found in the western part of Europe, in Eastern Europe the advisory service is mainly owned and managed by the state and has a focus on improving productivity, rather than promoting alternative modes of production. Although there are targeted programmes on various aspects. The need to establish peer-to-peer learning settings is an element that is often stressed in many reports.
- We find that among researchers and practitioners there is a lack of the application of systems thinking and of a holistic approach to the development of farming systems, as opposed to the narrow sector-specific focus that is the foundation for competence development in many countries. Further, although there are networks around organic farmers, which are engaged with agroecological principles and practices, less focus is given to conventional farmers who need advice and these groups may often feel that they have been left behind. In addition, deep divisions between conventional and alternative farming communities prevent dialogue and knowledge exchange, and the perceived "alternativeness" of agroecology deters conventional farmers from an interest in acquiring skills in agroecological practices.
- Lacking the willingness to cooperate is also mentioned as an obstacle to the dissemination of experiences and advancement of agroecological practices.
- Among national reports a lacking sense of ownership of the agroecology transition is reported. As a base for developing competencies that promote transition, institution-building is currently a critical shortcoming. An inventory of agroecological practices and the evidence base around these practices are requested in several national reports. In addition, there is hindrance to the development of market opportunities for products based on agroecology practices when an institutional setting around agroecology is missing.

Table 5: Replies to the question: "How would you classify the state of the following elements in the context of agroecology in your country?"

		Education of farmers in agricultural colleges	Technological infrastructure in the farming sector	Knowledge networks among farmers	Farm advisory service	Resources available for training/retraining of farmers	Farmer networks for knowledge sharing	Other
NW Europe	Belgium							
	Denmark							
	Finland							
	Germany							
	Iceland							
	Ireland							
	Lichtenstein							
	Luxembourg							
	Norway							
	the Netherlands							
	Switzerland							
United Kingdom								
NE Europe	Czech							
	Estonia							
	Hungary							
	Latvia							
	Lithuania							
	Poland							
	Slovakia							
S Europe	Cyprus							
	France							
	Serbia							
	Turkey							
	Average							
	Very well developed	Developed	Neutral	Somewhat developed	Not developed at all	No data		

Table 6: Replies to the question: "To which extent do you agree with the following statements regarding stakeholder involvement with respect to agroecology related matters in your country?"

		Stakeholders are organised in associations that represent their interests	Stakeholder associations possess a high level of technical expertise	Stakeholders' views are taken into consideration in policymaking	Stakeholders are well integrated in research programmes	Stakeholder associations representing farmers have a strong interest in pursuing an agroecology transition	Living labs and other open innovation arrangements are frequently used in to foster transition within your country	Stakeholders are actively participating in multi-stakeholder living labs
NW Europe	Belgium							
	Denmark							
	Finland							
	Germany							
	Iceland							
	Ireland							
	Lichtenstein							
	Luxembourg							
	Norway							
	the Netherlands							
	Switzerland							
	United Kingdom							
NE Europe	Czech							
	Estonia							
	Hungary							
	Latvia							
	Lithuania							
	Poland							
	Slovakia							
S Europe	Cyprus							
	France							
	Serbia							
	Turkey							
	Average							
		To a high extent	To some extent	Neutral	To a limited extent	Not at all	No data	

3.5 Involvement of stakeholders

In the Northwest of Europe, stakeholders are particularly organised in strong farmers associations that are able to represent farmers' interests, while this is mostly not the case in a number of countries in Northeast and Southern Europe (see figure 6). In addition, for the vast majority of the surveyed countries, the reports suggest that, generally, stakeholders are not used to foster transition, particularly not in North-eastern Europe.

Analysis of the country reports adds some detail to this general picture. Below we summarised some of the themes that occurred recurrently in the national reports; for a detailed overview of specific countries, see Appendix E:

- Generally, it is emphasised in several reports that LLs offer a powerful tool that ought to be strengthened to ensure better processes around stakeholder involvement. Particularly, the potential for using the LLs as a testbed for novel techniques, technology and practices are emphasised. Further, improving the coordination between, science, practice and policy-makers is something that should be further developed.
- While some reports indicate specific shortcomings for stakeholder involvement in LLs, other indicate great preparedness and technical expertise. However, positive attitudes towards the processes are important if LLs should be established as successful institutions. Therefore, there is a need for an improvement of the institutional structure around the labs. The importance of establishing training programmes for LL facilitators, securing neutral meeting spaces, building capacities for bridging across different groups of stakeholders is critical for the success of LLs and emphasised in a number of reports. Further, some country reports stress the lack of social capital and a cooperative culture as a critical shortcoming that should also be taken into account in the design of LL interventions.
- Among stakeholders the need to establish spaces for the practical demonstrations and peer-to-peer learning is underscored as an important function that should be sustained. Thus, building a culture around LL collaboration and showcasing best practice examples of LLs and disseminating knowledge about LLs facilitation is crucial for the overall success of this new institution.
- It is stressed that the lacking institutional setup around agroecology hinders successful stakeholder involvement, because it is difficult to know which actors should be considered as stakeholders in relation to decisions regarding agroecology.
- There are different local traditions of stakeholder involvement in research activities and policy-making. Several national reports stress that it is important to strengthen networks and farmers' inclusion in research projects to enable better coordination of the agroecology transition, including ensuring that stakeholders have a real say in relation to relevant decision-making. Conducting this type of participatory research implies that knowledge producers should work directly with end-users, thus ensuring that research activities consider stakeholders' needs. Further, it is stressed that lacking possibilities for compensating farmers for the time they spend in activities related to LLs is a constraint. Related to this, it is also important to avoid too much interaction, which can cause stakeholder fatigue.
- A potentially successful agroecology transition not only depends on the mobilisation of the farming community, but it is also important to include other actors, including those in the value-chains, and indeed consumers. These types of actors have an important role as their decisions are instrumental in shaping the agro-food market, which constitute the framework around the decision-making of producers and should be taken into account as well.

- It is also important to recognise that many participants have time constraints and LLS should be designed to cater for such difference, ensuring that there will be opportunities for very engaged participants and some that are interested, but do not have much time to spend.

3.6 Policies in support of agroecology

With respect to policies in support of agroecology transition, national reports indicate that while some principles and practices associated with agroecology transition feature prominently in current policy making, others do not (see figure 7). Fertiliser and manure management, diversified crop rotation and integrated pest management using biological control, are generally well supported in national policy-making. Wetland restoration using paludiculture and multi-stakeholder innovation are other key practices that are only sustained to a smaller extent in a number of countries.

Analysis of the country reports adds some detail to this general picture. Below we summarised some of the themes that occurred recurrently in the national reports; for a detailed overview of specific countries, see Appendix F:

- Although the green transition now features quite prominently in the European agro-food policies, most notably in the Green Deal, respondents indicate a range of shortcomings to current policies, including a lacking emphasis on knowledge transfer, the need to strengthen advisory systems, and to provide incentives for agroecology transition.
- A number of respondents across different countries discussed the CAP and the ability of the CAP to deliver on agroecology transition. Generally, it is argued across a number of reports that although the CAP in terms of funding is the most important foundation for agro-food development, it is generally not used to support agroecology transition, but rather used to sustain the agroindustry. This, it is argued, is a critical shortcoming as the current funding is not sufficiently allocated for agroecology transition and improving the subsidy structure of the CAP in favour of agroecology transition is an important point to emphasize. Some of these shortcomings may also be due to the recent change in policy objectives, where the emission of climate change mitigation increasingly play a role. Relatedly, the short-term nature of a number of the European funding instruments is highlighted as a challenge because, transitional processes are complex and presuppose a long-term commitment.
- Aside from the financial support provided by the CAP, different regulatory initiatives that ban harmful practices and regulates farmers conduct with respect to biodiversity, aquatic environment and soils are also emphasised as important elements of an agroecology transition.

Some elements of agroecology are supported in all countries, with for instance policies in support of organic farming featuring prominently in many regions. A lack of clear targets in European policies with respect to the objectives of an agroecology transition hinders the successful development of new initiatives. For instance, in many countries it is reported that maintaining and improving the productivity of agricultural production is still more important in national policymaking, than ensuring the foundations for sustainable production. Furthermore, policymaking in relation to agroecology is organised in silos where for instance agricultural policies, environmental policies and industrial policies are poorly integrated.

With respect to the practices and principles mentioned in the question, several reports highlight that some of these initiatives are already required by farmers as a condition

for direct payments and that that national policies ought to go beyond these initiatives.

Table 7: Replies to the question: “To which extent do national policies aim to support the following principles and practices associated with agroecology transition?”

		Integrated Pest Management and Biological Control	Conservation Tillage	Mixed Cropping Systems	Diversified Crop Rotation	Cover Crops	Fertiliser and Nutrient Management Efficiency	Biodiversity Preservation	Circularity in Biomass Utilisation	Wetland Restoration/Paludiculture	Sustainable Water Management	Multi-stakeholder innovation arrangements such as living labs
NW Europe	Belgium	Blue	Grey	Green	Grey	Blue	Grey	Blue	Grey	Yellow	Blue	Grey
	Denmark	Grey	Grey	Green	Grey	Blue	Blue	Grey	Blue	Grey	Blue	Green
	Finland	Blue	Blue	Green	Grey	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green
	Germany	Blue	Grey	Green	Grey	Blue	Blue	Blue	Grey	Green	Blue	Green
	Iceland	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
	Ireland	Blue	Blue	Grey	Grey	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green	Blue
	Lichtenstein	Grey	Green	Green	Grey	Blue	Green	Grey	Grey	Grey	Green	Green
	Luxembourg	Blue	Blue	Yellow	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green
	Norway	Blue	Blue	Green	Grey	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	the Netherlands	Blue	Blue	Grey	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	Switzerland	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	United Kingdom	Green	Grey	Green	Grey	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green
NE Europe	Czech	Blue	Grey	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green	Grey	Blue	Green
	Estonia	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green
	Hungary	Blue	Blue	Green	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Yellow	Blue	Green
	Latvia	Blue	Blue	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	Lithuania	Green	Blue	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green
	Poland	Blue	Blue	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Yellow	Blue	Green
	Slovakia	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Yellow	Blue	Green
S Europe	Cyprus											
	France	Grey	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Grey	Blue	Blue
	Serbia	Blue	Green	Green	Blue	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green
	Turkey	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green	Blue	Green
	Average	Blue	Blue	Green	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Green
		To a high extent	To some extent	Neutral	To a limited extent		Not at all		No data			

4. Conclusions

The purpose of this report is to provide a synthesis of NCP's perception on the drivers of agroecology transition as these appear in 23 different European countries (Turkey, the Netherlands, Switzerland, Slovakia, Serbia, Poland, Norway, Lichtenstein, Luxembourg, Lithuania, Latvia, Ireland, Iceland, Finland, Estonia, Denmark, Czech, Cyprus, Belgium, the United Kingdom, France, Germany and Hungary). This report is written as a synthesis of 23 national reports that were prepared by partners based on a joint mapping exercise. Reports from partners include qualitative and quantitative elements. This combination provides different types of information, offering a rich picture on the state of agroecology across countries and the drivers of agroecology transition.

The report is based on a survey among NCP's who were purposively selected as key informants to outline the understanding and drivers of agroecology transition as it appear nationally. Given the role of NCP's as key actors for the establishment of local living labs, as experimental and learning hubs in projects funded under Horizon Europe, they were a highly relevant entry-point to gain an overview of national initiatives and experiences. However, it is important to stress that the information obtained during these interviews are essentially qualitative in nature reflecting the perspectives of individual informants. Guidelines were designed to inquire into the understandings of agroecology and local initiatives and infrastructures in support of agroecology, topics which are somewhat factual, and have relatively limited sensitivity to the personal opinions and values of informant, and therefore less influential on the outcomes of the inquiry.

Since the NCP's have an important bridging function in the local Agricultural Knowledge and Information Systems (AKIS'), with detailed knowledge of local initiatives, policies, drivers in support of, or barriers for an agroecology transition, they were a valuable entry point for the analysis.

The report documents that the perception of agroecology differs substantially across the different European countries and the concept "agroecology" is widely reported to be novel to NCPs. Reflecting this, the concept is not formally recognised and codified in domestic regulation. However, reports suggest that a number of agroecological practices are widely applied among practitioners in the surveyed countries, for instance, integrated pest management and biological control is very important in many European countries. With respect to the ongoing engagement activities from All-Ready and further in the upcoming partnership this implies that communication efforts need to be adapted to several user groups. .

Respondents' assessments of current RIs generally indicate that RIs are sufficiently attuned to support the agroecology transition in most of the countries. Further, while competencies for agroecology transition diverge quite a lot across the different European countries, several reports emphasise that LLs offer a powerful tool that ought to be strengthened to ensure better processes around stakeholder involvement. For the design of upcoming research support programmes this implies that there is a need for designing activities that are agile and able to support particular national needs that are contextually situated. Further, the composition of the farm advisory service vary across the countries surveyed. While many private and cooperatively owned advisory services are found in the western part of Europe, in Eastern Europe the advisory service is mainly owned and managed by the state and has a focus on improving productivity, rather than promoting alternative modes of production. This implies that ongoing engagement activities with regards to agroecology and the later

establishment of Living Labs should take conditions that prevail for these knowledge brokers into account.

With respect to policies in support of agroecology transition, national reports indicate that while some principles and practices associated with agroecology feature prominently in current policy making, others are absent. Here it is important to emphasize that the advancement of agroecology presupposes an integrative approach which should preferably also be supported in policies. Further, mapping respondents indicate a range of shortcomings to current policies, including a lacking emphasis on knowledge transfer, strengthening advisory systems- and providing incentives for agroecology transition.

The national reports also stress a number of barriers for the agroecology transition. For instance, research and innovation systems are often reported to lack a systems- and transdisciplinary perspective, meaning that it is difficult to properly reflect the holistic thinking required for agroecology transition. This indicates that supporting the agroecology transition also requires a more fundamental transition of different subsystems, including research, practices and supporting policies to accommodate this complex transition. Further, the involvement of end-users is stressed as an important element for research into agroecology transition.

However, for some countries, particularly in the eastern and southern part of Europe, a poor relationship between farmers and the research community is reported as a hindrance to further increasing and improving stakeholders' involvement in research projects. This is a critical shortcoming that needs to be considered in supporting activities for agroecology because the foundations for establishing Living Labs may be hindered by unfortunate past experiences or lacking familiarity across stakeholder categories. Additionally, for practitioners, economic considerations play an important role in the design and adoption of farming practices. Hence, the availability of subsidy schemes is very important for the adoption of these practices, and generally partners report that practices, which are supported in government programmes gain more popularity.

The information provided in this report will feed into subsequent tasks and deliverables of All-Ready. Most importantly, it constitutes a foundation for D2.4 and D2.5, as well as D2.6 which will focus on the implications for the further advancement of agroecology and how the project and the wider agroecological transition will be positioned in relation to that.

Annex A: National definitions of agroecology

Table 9: Partners synthesis of the interviews with respect to the entry: "Definitions of agroecology".

Belgium	<p>In general, the interest in agroecology both as a science, practice and social movement is growing, but the relative importance compared to the whole agrifood system in the country is still low. In Belgium, the farmers who practice agroecology are mostly the organic farmers and there aren't many. In the Walloon region there are more organic farmers than in the Flemish region, which is also translated in the % of agricultural area which is used for organic farming. There is research on aspects or components of agroecology, but not so much on agroecology as a holistic, systemic approach. One of the interviewees referred to GIRAF group as an interdisciplinary agroecology research group of the FNRS (Belgian National Scientific Research Foundation). This group was founded in 2009 and consists of Belgian Scientists with various backgrounds from a range of institutions. Some NGO's are involved in agroecology as a social movement, but this is a minority. They represent only a minority of farmers and citizens. It was said by one interviewee there is not a common understanding on the concept of agroecology at Flemish Government just as it is not clear how it relates to organic farming.</p>
Cyprus	<p>Agroecology is a new concept in Cyprus and it is not well spread. Although diversity is a key concept in farming systems, currently, farmers are not leading practices to reduce inputs. Some groups are studying the application of ecological concepts and principles in the farming systems, but more on the theoretical aspects than practical applications. Regarding social movements, they are not important in Cyprus currently, but associated with the Academia, there are some seeds of social movements and a growing interest to launch NGOs linked to agroecology.</p>
Czech Rep.	<p>All respondents agreed that the three dimensions of agroecology listed in the questionnaire should be seen as equally important. However, they reported that the perception of agroecology on a country level is not established fully according to such a holistic definition. It is seen as a very broad topic with way too many definitions. "This "full definition" would be understood only by few researchers involved in international research projects. The general understanding of it is mainly focused on agricultural and conservation practices, and the science behind them." "People would speak about some shift from conventional to more environmentally sensitive practices. But they wouldn't mention value chains, social movements. They would speak immediately about organic farming and some conversation farming." "Quite often people think that they are talking about agroecology, but what they are really talking about is organic farming. They don't see the other things that are included in agroecology. They don't see its holistic approach." Social movements are rarely associated with agroecology, and receive little or</p>

	<p>no attention. Only a few specialized researchers and some deeply engaged stakeholder groups are dedicated to the promotion of these aspects of agroecology. These social movements are rather seen to be linked to organic farming or permaculture. The ‘science part’ of agroecology focuses more on conservation or organic farming practices, overlooking the importance of learning about the social aspects of agroecology or researching the dynamics of the related social movements. Agroecological practices seem to fail to attract a wider range of stakeholder involvement and stakeholder cooperation, which would be required to make changes in the food system. However, there are some projects, like TRAEce that focus specifically on the social dimension of agroecology though providing agroecological vocational training for farmers. The promotion of food produced through agroecological practices highlights mostly just the environmental advantages of these production practices (mostly listed as organic) and fails to include the social achievements linked to them - as those are not seen as selling points.</p>
Denmark	<p>The term agroecology is not recognised broadly in DK practical agriculture nor as a movement. The main application of agroecology is within Organic farming, where the development of agroecological practices has been supported for more than 25 years in constructive collaboration between science, extension and farmers (ICROFS and other initiatives). Some former organisations, such as Økologisk Landsforening may be considered an example of an agroecological social movement and there are other more local initiatives within organic agriculture which may be seen from this perspective. Furthermore, the connection between organic farming and agroecology is not very clear and are often confused. It is a challenge to separate the two concepts and the organic concept is given more importance and considered a strong brand.</p>
Estonia	<p>In Estonia, the term agroecology is used as an official word which is, however, rather new and the people do not really understand what it means. It is more common in the scientific and theoretical context than in practices and in social movements. Still, Estonia must deal with agroecology and use the term, because a lot of European politicians are using the term agroecology. In general, agroecological practices are common in Estonia and the country is perceived as sustainable and environmentally friendly. Moreover, Estonia is perceived as a country based on natural resources. This is, however seen mostly on a superficial level and not so much when it comes to the details. Moreover, the importance of agroecology in Estonia depends on the stakeholders. Some NCPs think, that the social aspect of agroecology is not understood well in Estonia.</p>
Finland	<p>In Finland, agroecological practices and sciences are considered more important than social movements in the field of agroecology. In general, agroecology is linked to organic agriculture and sustainability. Agroecology as a concept is not very often mentioned when these topics are discussed. In general, the term Agroecology is not widely used and it</p>

	<p>is more common in research than in the practice among farmers. A finish term for “Agroekologia” would probably be more easily accepted. Still, agroecology in the sense of organic and sustainable agriculture has become more interesting to farmers, also conventional ones, after the prices of inputs has increased. Also, as animal farms are reducing inputs and manure is used less, soil structure and growing conditions are getting worse due to lacking organic inputs. This has become more evident and has boosted the interest in agroecological practices. Still, the topic of agroecology is not so much on the table in Finland, as other topics are more important like for example community supported agriculture.</p> <p>Organic agriculture is more used, having partly similar issues like conventional agriculture in Finland: the food systems are divided in crop and animal farms, but they are not mixed, mainly due to regional differences. Therefore, nutrient recycling is not working well.</p> <p>Agriculture in Finland is focusing more on specific practices (e.g. nutrient cycling) rather than on a more comprehensive approach. So, Finland is lacking of a vision of a sustainable food system.</p>
France	<p>The interviewees agree about the concept of agroecology containing practices, science and being a social movement, and consider them all as important or very important. These three dimensions are interconnected as they influence each other and change over time. For instance, INRAE as a scientific organisation was ranked lower in terms of publications in France 10 years ago, but is one of the main leaders in agroecology research now. All agree that there must be a good balance between the three dimensions. For the ministry of agriculture, agroecology including all of its three dimensions has a top priority for the present and near future. It is considered that there are no improvements in the practices without science, and no development in general without practices, especially on the farm level. Farmers must be one of the main targets as they need to help to foster the transition. Nevertheless, they need to be convinced by arguments and not just pressure from the political side. Therefore, science has to provide better solutions (e.g. for reducing pesticides) to ensure that farmers can maintain the production level and/or at least secure the economic output for them. In this process they need to be actively involved. Despite that, the social movement is considered to be very important in France. Agroecology is understood by a growing amount of consumers and citizens as a philosophy that can change the conventional farming system into a transition process. Altogether, France is seen as a leader for agroecology in Europe, but still has many tasks ahead to improve as well.</p>
Germany	<p>Agroecological practices and agroecology as a social movement were seen as important perspectives and drivers of agroecology in Germany. Social movements could also be a critical bottle-neck for the overall acceptance of agroecology in Germany. Some of the key actors in the farming sector strongly associate the interpretation of agroecology as a social movement with negative impacts on economic values and farm</p>

	<p>income. Broadening the discussion beyond economic values to wider social, environmental and economic benefits agroecology can potentially provide was seen as important. But interviewees also emphasised the importance of an integrated view on agroecology combining practices, science and social movements. In the academic discourse the concept and importance of agroecology is mainly conceived as a science and often operates within the realms of plant sciences, ecology and zoology. While attention to transdisciplinary science is seen as increasing, interviewees also pointed out that a lack of experience with transdisciplinary research and the need for an earlier involvement of farmers already during the design phase of research projects remain key issues.</p>
Hungary	<p>People in general don't understand the complexity of the concept of agroecology, they tend to see it as a set of practises. Even the NGOs and policy makers that focus specifically on the agroecology transition fail to equally address the different dimensions of it. The biodiversity conservation action plan based on CAP was given as an example of this shortcoming. However, new generations, and those with foreign studies or with working relationships with colleagues from other countries have a better understanding of the optimal dynamics of these three dimensions, and are ready to pay equal attention to its social aspects.</p> <p>In Hungary, the understanding of the concept of agroecology includes the incorporation of traditional farming (peasant) knowledge into agrarian practises to some extent, and the combination of traditional and scientific ecological knowledge. Despite the emphasised state support, there are no specific tools that would make it easier to consult such knowledge in a more systematic way. In Hungary, the importance of traditional species receives strong state support, which shows that we are not lacking behind in all aspects. There are many initiatives with great potential to support the agroecological transition and a valuable knowledge base accumulated and ready to be harvested.</p> <p>Also, the recognition of the importance of specific local contexts when implementing certain agroecological practises is also characteristic of the Hungarian perception of agroecology. Agroecology seeks to find context-specific solutions to local problems. There is no "one size fits all". The understanding of agroecology also recognizes the importance of circularity. Circularity is a key concept of agroecology, which includes efforts to promote the circular use of biomass and other resources, and the recycling of production side products to mitigate waste production. From a socio-economic point of view, cooperation is also a key concept of agroecology, with its efforts to reconnect producers and consumers through the development of local markets, short food supply chains. It also should promote fair, equitable wages - an aspect hardly addressed in the region.</p> <p>The agroecological practises implemented represent the most significant dimension of agroecology in Hungary. However, we must recognize that</p>

	<p>the proliferation of such practises is still minimal, and they are often recognized just as organic agricultural practises. The second dimension of agroecology is far more consciously developed. It mainly consists of the work of research institutions and NGOs that study and promote the implementation of applicable agronomic and socioeconomic practises. They also aim to develop a participatory research infrastructure, recently through the creation of on-farm networks and living labs. However, the social aspects that could complement these agronomic practises do not receive sufficient attention. There are few NGOs that provide assistance to developing consumer associations, and producer markets. They operate beyond their strength, with low financial resources, not receiving sufficient state support. They have difficulties reaching beyond the “bubble of conscious consumers and dedicated farmers” they operate within.</p> <p>The social aspects of agroecology have been receiving more attention lately, but there is still a long way to go before it gets even close to being seen as equally important to the actual agronomic practises implemented. The social aspects of agroecology are somewhat included in the scope of a range of related fields of science. However, they gradually become neglected at later stages of research. The research deliverables rarely provide implementable results that would address the above-mentioned inequality. The importance of addressing its social aspects is clearly recognized in this “bubble”. However, it receives far less attention among policymakers and society in general. When policy makers look at agroecology, they see a set of agroecological agronomic practises that require supportive policies. However, when we look at the goals attached to the social aspects of agroecology, this hands-on mentality to develop policies with assigned supportive frameworks is missing.</p>
Iceland	<p>Agroecology is not a recognized concept in Iceland. According to interviewee 1, conservation of organic soils (peatland) is a crucial aspect, and much effort is put into preservation and restoration of these. In general, agricultural production is limited, with limited use of chemicals (mostly grassland). Research on agricultural practices and science is done in collaboration with advisors and farmers, and the dimension of social movements is minor. There are groups of organic farmers, but they focus is on inputs and the use of GMOs (it is described as a polarized debate, without much space for dialogue).</p>
Ireland	<p>Interviewees agree that the broad or general understanding of agroecology is most likely limited in the majority of cases in Ireland. For one of the interviewees, different agroecology-based practices are being promoted, such as soil cover, nutrient use efficiency, nature-based solutions, carbon storage, etc. However, few people is using the term agroecology to refer to them. Meanwhile, the other interviewee thinks that there is significant engagement and application of agroecology across different areas of the agri-food sector by individual farmers, networks, cooperatives, NGOs, that are working in the</p>

	<p>agroecology space.</p> <p>As a reflection, one of the NCP commented that from an understanding perspective, agroecology should also see itself in a continuum that goes from natural capital through the agri-food sector to a circular and bio-economy. It should not stand alone but be an activity addressing national and EU high level objectives. For example, as a practice agroecology should also relate to the circular and bio-economy. In Ireland’s Food Vision 2030 strategy Mission 1 Goal 6 seeks to embed the agri-food sector in a circular regenerative bioeconomy and agroecology can play a significant role in this Mission/Goal.</p>
Latvia	<p>Divergent views were expressed on the importance of the different perspectives on agroecology in Latvia. Agroecology as a social movement was seen as important perspectives of the understanding of agroecology in Latvia. Interviewees highlighted the need for an integrated view on agroecology combining practices, science and social movements. The research strategies of scientific institutions pay attention to agroecological principles and sustainable agriculture, e.g. in relation to the maintenance of soil fertility and biological activity, including effective use of fertilizers and plant protection strategies. Research of soil, microorganisms and invertebrates and their interactions with plants were highlighted in this context as one of the most important research directions. Stronger integration of social sciences was recommended.</p>
Lichtenstein	<p>In Lichtenstein, agroecology is coming, however, with a focus on individual aspects. Agroecology as a concept is not very common in Lichtenstein, with the exception of the project “Lebenswertes Lichtenstein”. This is reflected in the importance of the different agroecological dimensions, where the practices are perceived as important, the sciences are seen as neutral and social movements are seen as less important.</p> <p>In Lichtenstein there is no research institution in the field of agriculture. Instead, the focus in Lichtenstein is on advisory services and on how the latest research findings can be implemented and applied in practice. The social movements in the field of agroecology are less important, because there are already various institutions and because agriculture is rather small-scale. However, there are much larger farms in Lichtenstein compared to Switzerland. There are about 100 farms that are entitled to direct payments.</p>
Lithuania	<p>Agroecological practices and agroecology as a social movement were seen as important perspectives of the understanding of agroecology in Lithuania. Interviewees highlighted the importance of an integrated view on agroecology combining practices, science and social movements. Past and on-going examples of research activities in the field of agroecology were highlighted. It was pointed out that research activities often have an agronomic emphasis focusing on agroecology as a means to improve agricultural production (e.g. with respect to the productivity of the system or the quality of products).</p>

Luxembourg	<p>In Luxembourg, the term agroecology does exist but it is not really established and known in society, yet. A lot of the agroecological principles are already included in organic farming. About 5% of the agricultural area in Luxembourg is farmed organically. For the society, organic agriculture is seen as less use of pesticides and fertilizers. In Luxembourg, the agroecological practices are on average considered slightly more important than the sciences and the social movements. Currently, there are two ministries responsible for agriculture (environment & agriculture), making it difficult to get projects & funding in agroecology. Changing this situation would be a first step into the direction of agroecological transition.</p>
Netherlands	<p>In the Netherlands, the term agroecology is not so common, maybe more in the research fields than in the practice. Agroecology as a broad concept includes different movements like organic agriculture, nature inclusive agriculture, resilience agriculture, precision farming, circular farming, regenerative agriculture. All these movements are included in the concept of agroecology, but with different uses and skills. Therefore, the answers to the closed questions depend on the movement or type of agroecology. Overall, the given answers reflect the average over the different types of agroecology. They are, however, not so strict: all the three dimensions of agroecology are seen as important. Some national contact points see all the three dimensions as equally important, others see the sciences as most important and some see the social movements as a bit less important and they are less organized specifically on agroecology. Even though, the term agroecology is not very common, the principles are used. However, there are different understandings and different definitions of agroecology. During a research meeting of an institutional program with a setup of agroecology partnerships, including different partners, agroecology principles were agreed to concern sustainable and ecological management principles in farming. Yet, most farmers do not apply agroecological methods, although, a lot of major issues in the agriculture refer to nitrogen and agroecology may serve as a solution.</p>
Norway	<p>The term Agroecology is not very common in Norway. There are only few agroecology concepts used, rather sustainable agriculture or organic agriculture are the concepts, being discussed. Agroecology is practiced but the term is not used as such. This might have led to the fact that agroecological practices are by some national contacts seen as not very important and by others as less important than agroecological science and social movements in agroecology. The latter can also be explained by the fact, that farms in Norway are small and family run, leading to conditions that do not require agroecological practices to a large extent. In biodynamic farms agroecology concepts are common. Social movements in agroecology in Norway concern mainly cooperatives which are common. Regarding sciences, half of the research is assumed to be related to sustainability and agroecology, however, not related to the concepts. Agroecology is not clearly defined and not commonly used in Norway.</p>

	<p>The agroecology concept has been coming from NGOs, stakeholders and is inspired by international discussions. Now the sciences and the governmental bodies have noticed the concept and started to apply it, but not yet as a strategy. The discussions on what agroecology means as a concept has started and is ongoing. EU was earlier in discussing the concept of agroecology than Norway. But Norway has been using the practices. Those who are involved in the practices, for example farmers, are not using the term “agroecology” but are applying the practices. A similar development as with agroecology was seen for living-labs: living-labs is a new concept also in EU. In Norway, living-labs have been doing for longer than the concept was there. But many subsidise go in the agroecological direction. However, this is more common agronomic practice and the wish of the government, rather than that they want to support the concept of Agroecology as such.</p> <p>Self-sufficient farming, which was performed during the last century, was more in line with agroecology than the conventional production system now. Moreover, traditional / conventional agronomy studies do not deal so much with agroecology, however, there are exceptions, which are seen as important. Also, the social movements do not use the term “agroecology” so much or at all, but they work with the concept. Some exceptions of social movements, however, are even based on agroecology.</p> <p>In Norway, there are agroecology practices but they are not formulated in the debate in the opinion of the farmers who use the practices, since the concept of agroecology itself is not that common. Instead of the agroecology concept, the debate among farmers is more about practices from organic farming (with its specific principles, its label and policies), regenerative farming (with its new concept without label), etc. The practices are environmental friendly, sustainable, resilient, good-agronomical principles, However, all the concepts are loose, with different meanings.</p> <p>Moreover, in Norway, there are subsidies related to how farming has to be carried out, including specific principles, related to environment / biodiversity / soil conditions. These subsidies are payed per decar.</p>
Poland	<p>Agroecology practically does not exist in the official discourse, or in training programs for farmers and agricultural advisors. There is no support for agroecology from the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. Wojtowicz, who organises training events at her agroforestry farm, reports that out of over 3,000 people participating in training and workshops that she conducted in 2019-2021 in Poland, none of them has ever heard about agroecology. In Poland, agroecology is promoted mainly by social movements, however research doesn't play any major role so far. There is a number of foundations and organisations as well as eco-villages which pursue agro-ecology. These often connect with urban centres, and in some urban environments one can perceive an interest in ecological and local food, and in the farmer-consumer reconnection.</p>

Serbia	<p>The agroecology (In Serbian: agroekologija) is in most cases perceived as equal to the organic agriculture or as agriculture with a reduced use of the pesticides. AE as a 'practice' is gradually becoming more important. The 'scientific' aspect of agroecology is quite well developed through publications related to 'agro-technical issues'. However, these publications are not easily published in the high impact journals. In terms of AE as 'social movement' the NGO sector dedicated to organic agriculture is active and there are more funds accessible in this context.</p>
Slovakia	<p>The three dimensions of agroecology are perceived as equally important by those who are actively involved in the promotion of agroecology in Slovakia. However, there is more emphasis on its most advanced aspect, the dimension of scientific research. It is followed by the implementation of its results through the promotion of agroecological farming practices, with the social movement lagging behind, despite its abilities to support the implementation of the research results into practice.</p> <p>The following topics are considered to be part of agroecology: the protection of agricultural and forest land, the protection of soil quality, water quality, the promotion of integrated management systems, the protection of biodiversity, traditional agroforestry system practices (with high cultural and natural value), the reconstruction of the landscape through the creation of biocorridors, and the efforts to secure a healthy life in the countryside.</p> <p>The general stakeholder awareness about the concept of agroecology and knowledge about the related agroecology-based practices is low. Raising awareness and the engagement of a wider array of stakeholders needs to be further developed. Many farmers are engaged in agroecological practices, without being aware that they in fact contribute to the agroecological transition might not even fully understand what is meant by the agroecological transition. These agroecological practices are usually implemented by organic and/or small-scale farmers.</p> <p>Agroecology should be recognized as a social movement as well. This perception of it, and the general recognition of how a well addressed social dimension could contribute to the transition is still rarely understood. At the moment, it restricts its focus on connecting farmers with consumers, and organizing community activities. Besides some NGOs, mostly a couple of engaged farmers are in charge of such loosely coordinated efforts (see the agroecological initiatives listed in Section 9).</p>
Switzerland	<p>In Switzerland, all the three dimensions of agroecology, e.g. practices, sciences and social movements are seen as important. Agroecological practices are perceived as slightly more important than agroecological sciences, and social movements. However, it is very often restricted to practices, ignoring the social and political aspects.</p> <p>The frame of agroecology is not very common in Switzerland. There is no</p>

	<p>agricultural policy instruments specific to agroecology. There is no aim for a label, this would confuse the consumers with another term. The aim is rather to foster the concept and to apply practices in the field, generally.</p> <p>The understanding of agroecology is quite broad, and many things referred to or thought of as agroecology does not fit all the principles of agroecology. However, agroecology is often understood by its ‘old-school’ definition, most people understand it as it was framed 20 years ago, not like the high-level panel of experts and FAO defined it, which includes the principle of social values, co-creation of knowledge, fairness etc.</p> <p>The consideration of all biodiversity levels and facets is necessary to understand and efficiently implement agroecology. On-farm research is very important for innovation and co-creation within all aspects of agroecology. Important question: How can biodiversity contribute specifically to increase resilience and performance of agroecosystems? Mostly only individual ecosystem services e.g. pollination, promotion of beneficial insects have been considered. Landscape perspective and integration of different ecosystem services (system perspective) would be highly relevant for innovation and sustainably improving production capacity and resilience.</p>
Turkey	<p>Regarding agroecology, many measures have been undertaken using the name of sustainable agriculture for many years in the country. There are research and legislation studies on Organic Agriculture, Precision Agriculture, Waste Management, and Use of Renewable Energy in Agriculture, Conservation Tillage, Protection of Biodiversity, and Sustainable Use of Biomass. Action plans were also created within the scope of the Green Deal of the European Union. Nevertheless, research and legislative studies should be carried out more for the transition to the understanding of agroecology. In general, the three dimensions of agroecology are seen as equally important and interconnected. Beside the pushing of agroecology by the consumers, science can be considered as starting point that delivers the tools for the practices to apply (e.g. technologies). The results are products created by agroecological standards which can then impact the social movement by offering more products created that way. If one dimension of the circle is missing, the whole system is unable to work, e.g. because the farmers do not have proper tools to use if science does not deliver them.</p>
United Kingdom	<p>Interviewees agree that agroecology is not a familiar concept beyond very specific social movement groups. In Wales especially the awareness of agroecology is low. However, they also agree that practices or approaches which can be interpreted as or form part of agroecology are widely known and pursued in research and by practitioners. Reducing inputs and improving environmental outcomes is widely recognised, and there is significant research into this, although not under an agroecology term (rather terms such as sustainable intensification, sustainable farming, or recently regenerative farming are more common). Research into agroecology as a holistic approach is rare,</p>

	<p>although not non-existent. The association between anti-GM and agroecology means a holistic approach is rare. The debate about agroecology becomes polarised because agroecology is associated with organic growing, and there are long-standing tensions between organic and conventional farming organisations. Engagement with the term as holistic is strongest in specific social movements concerned with agroecology, however it is not a banner under which different movements coalesce. These social movements are also not very impactful.</p>
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Annex B: Agroecology-based practices

Table 10: Partners synthesis of the interviews with respect to the entry: “*The extent of agroecology-based practices*”

Belgium	<p>Integrated pest management, cover crops, and sustainable water management are most common used agroecology-based practices in Flanders. Fertilizer and nutrient efficiency management, diversified crop rotation, sustainable water management and cover crops are most common used agroecology-based practices in the Walloon region. Most of the more common practices are induced by law or can be subsidised. Moreover, some of the principles/practices are applied, but not always to a high degree (eg different degrees to implement conservation tillage, to implement crop rotation and sustainable water use). This survey does not allow these nuances in implementation. Wetland restauration with paludiculture is very unusual in both regions. The extent to which particular practices are adopted, is very much depending on the agricultural sector. One of the interviewees emphasized that in the list of practices provided in the survey practices relevant for livestock production are underrepresented (focus on plant production). Another interviewee missed the socio-economic dimension of agroecology in this list of practices. Besides agricultural sector, also soil and climate conditions, which are heterogeneous across Wallonia, have an impact on agroecological practices applied. For example low tillage will occur mainly in loamy, sandy loamy and condroz agricultural region, integrated pest management in fruit, vegetable and arable cropping areas</p>
Cyprus	<p>In Cyprus, mixed cropping systems, diversified crop rotation and sustainable water management are common or very common. Then, other practices such as biodiversity preservation, cover crops, nutrient management efficiency, circularity in biomass utilisation or integrated pest management are developed or somewhat developed. However, these practices are not usually mentioned as agroecology practices. There are regional differences in Cyprus. In general, mountain agriculture is characterised to receive lower inputs than the agriculture practised in plains. And there is also more intensification in vegetables than in cereals.</p>
Czech Rep.	<p>A general remark: All respondents noted that the practices listed in the interview guideline focused on concrete agronomic practices, while many relevant non-agronomic practices were missing. Respondents found this problematic, and saw it as a telling sign of how even the research communities pay less attention to the relevance of the social, socio-economic aspects of the agroecological practices in general. Most of the listed agroecological practices are applied mostly by organic farmers. The advancement of agroecological practices linked to arable land is limited, as in the Czech Republic organic farming is mostly applied on permanent grasslands (over 80%). However, the agroecological practices applicable to arable land are commonly applied</p>

	<p>even by conventional farmers. These include the use of cover crops or conservation tillage. The latter is becoming a trend in organic farming. When it comes to biodiversity preservation, ‘intensive’ measures are applied only by a few. Practices including the social aspects of agroecology, like social farming should receive greater attention. Social farming focuses on the promotion of socioeconomic values in the countryside. It supports nonproductive functions, such as the creation of space and opportunities that keep the people in the rural landscape. It aims to provide a better quality of life in the countryside for the disadvantaged by creating jobs in agriculture for them. There are consumer associations that associate themselves with the organic farming movement. Even though they address a wider array of issues, they ‘would be surprised to know that what they do is agroecology’. Most of the regional differences are mostly due to regional climatic conditions. The country is divided into three regions. The Southeast lowlands in the middle of the country are characterized by arable lands under intensive conventional farming, growing mostly vegetables. The mountainous areas on the borders provide space for permanent grasslands with mostly organic and/or extensive practices related to biodiversity preservation. South Moravia is characterized mostly by its vineyards; nearly all of them operate under integrated management practices, some of them are certified as organic.</p>
Denmark	<p>The regional differences follow to a certain extent the regional differentiation of farming types including the spread of organic agriculture, following soil and agro-climatic conditions. Specifically, there is a history of organic farming in the Southern parts of Jylland and on the island of Bornholm. This was driven by these areas being given increased financial support. Many have, however, converted back to conventional farming practices again. The interviewees agreed that there is a need for practices to be discussed more openly within the whole system of stakeholders (from seed to table) and there is a hope that the new CAP reform will facilitate and support this, also in terms of the broad effects, such as climate mitigation. SEGES was especially identified as having an important role in this.</p>
Estonia	<p>In Estonia, the application of the majority of agroecological principles and agroecology-based practices is common or neutral (e.g. integrated pest management and biological control, conservation tillage, diversified crop rotation, cover crops, fertiliser and nutrient management efficiency/recycling and biodiversity preservation). Wetland restoration with paludiculture is unusual in Estonia. The extent of the application of “mixed cropping systems” and “sustainable water management” is seen differently (All in all, the extent of the application of agroecological principles and agroecology-based practices is differing a lot in the different regions in Estonia, since there are considerable regional differences in the agriculture in Estonia. The centre is very farmer organized with its very big farms. The soil in the centre is fertile and agroecological practices are less common than in the south and on the islands where organic farming is more common. In the south and on</p>

	<p>the islands, the soil fertility is generally lower than in the central region and the landscape is more hilly. Farmers in the south of Estonia use cover crops, biomass recycling, long crop rotations and have a high organic farming share. Moreover, there are a lot of semi-natural grasslands, permanent grasslands in the west of Estonia, containing aspects of agroforestry with grazing between the woodland. Forests and national parks are also important in Estonia, e.g. unusual or very common), due to regional differences: in the centre of Estonia, nutrient management and water quality are monitored. As additional common agroecology-based practice, the well-being of pollinators is monitored with a focus on managed bees, rather than on wild bees. A The majority of small and middle sized farms are perceived to be dealing with agroecology, either directly or indirectly. There are open farm days since 5 years already with the purpose to promote rural life and agriculture. Last year, there were over 300 open farms that day with 300'000 visitors. Purpose: promote rural life & agriculture. In general, the agroecology understanding in Estonia is very good and 25% of the agricultural land is organically managed. Further agroecology-based practice is the application of organic fertilizers and initiatives that make life easier for farmers (e.g. soil sample devices).</p>
Finland	<p>In general, agroecology based practices are not so commonly in Finland. Only “conservation tillage” is perceived as common. Other agroecology-based practices such as “cover crops”, “circularity in biomass utilisation”, “diversified crop rotation”, “fertiliser and nutrient management efficiency/recycling”, “biodiversity preservation” and “sustainable water management” generally perceived as neutral to somewhat common. “Integrated Pest Management and Biological Control” is considered more important for vegetables, and less for cereals, because Finland has not so many pests in general. Overall, the agroecology based practices are not perceived to be applied very ambitiously.</p> <p>Organic farms use agroecology-based practices more often than conventional farms. The traditional practices are easier to use and do not require as much knowledge as Agroecology practices. In the near future, when sustainability issues are hopefully more discussed, Agroecology practices will be more common, hopefully, also in traditional farms.</p> <p>There are regional differences in the Finnish agriculture: a lot of peatlands and grasslands are present in the north and east and thus more livestock production is found in these regions. Ruminants are more farmed in the northern and also other parts and monogastric animal are mostly farmed in the western part. Crop production (feed) and very few livestock production is found in the south and south-west, where the soil is more suitable for crop production. Due to this separation, 70 - 80% of the feed production needs to be transported across the country to the animals. In general, organic crop farms and animal farms are present in all regions and these farms have more diversity than conventional crop farms. The diversity in the agricultural production is</p>

	<p>an issue being discussed increasingly. Also, an increase in protein crop production is desired, especially on the crop farms, which would be good for the farm (e.g. by improving crop rotation, soil growing condition and biodiversity) and for the industry (e.g. by secure domestic raw material flows as most protein crops are imported by now). The size of the agricultural fields is generally small and scattered around, requiring a lot of transportation. The agricultural area has been staying stable over the last years, however, the farm size has been increasing lately and the number of farms is decreasing a lot. There is a growing attention to Agroforestry in Finland. In cropping systems, Agroforestry is unusual, but in life stock systems, it is more common, like pasture systems including trees.</p>
France	<p>In France there is a variety regarding the importance and application of the different agroecology principles and practices. In science, most of them are not as present even through being pushed through the ministries. This shows that France could increase their research efforts in this aspect. It also has to be considered that there is always a time gap between political decisions or laws and practices being implemented. There are two possible approaches on how to use the different practices and principles. One is to implement all of them at once and try to ensure all of them are fulfilled directly. The second and slower approach is to do it stepwise and principle-oriented . It was also mentioned that for the principles it is highly important to conduct the transition under the umbrella of the food system, and to include consumer behaviour and use the force of change which comes from them .</p> <p>Regionally, there are big differences in France. They are not only visible within continental France, but obviously even more between continental and the oversee departments. In general, southern France is considered to be more diversified in terms crop production, which might have on one hand to do with cultural reasons. Historically, in these areas (and also in mountainous regions) there was more free land available back in time, which led to more farmers trying more different types of farming techniques and products. The types of crops in the south of France are normally more heat and drought resistant due to environmental and climatic conditions. Therefore, the production is based on species, sorts and varieties that are adapted to these conditions. This fact brings back the need of science and further research on that aspect(. The oversee departments of France are all located outside of Europe within the tropical climate zones. This makes them more similar to each other about what plants to grow. For the oversea departments one central aspect is that enough food for the local people needs to be produced when implementing agroecology. Further, the species and sorts of crops have to be chosen in a proper way, being suitable for the different regions, and obviously differ from the ones produced in continental France (e.g. cassava instead of wheat). The different areas might also make it necessary to ensure that technologies are adapted and adjusted (e.g. irrigation practices more important for southern than northern</p>

	<p>France). Nevertheless, all interviewees agree that the general and main principles of implementing agroecology is the same everywhere, but the details of implementation differ.</p> <p>Additionally was mentioned that e.g. agroforestry and also organic farming should have been added as latter is not inclusive nor exclusive from agroecology .</p>
Germany	<p>While different views were expressed how commonly applied agroecological practices are (e.g. Integrated pest management, conservation tillage and fertiliser and nutrient management), relatively common application was indicated for mixed cropping systems and diversified crop rotations. Interviewees agreed that sustainable water management is the least frequently applied practices, although an increasing recognition of the importance of the water holding capacity of soils was indicated.</p> <p>Interviewees also emphasised the importance of social practices and elements of agroecology, which were not explicitly included in the list. Community Supported Agriculture and producer – consumer associations were highlighted in this context. Such associations have gained importance in particular in and around major cities. Further regional variations in the application of practices were related to structural reasons, e.g. more frequent applications in small field structures in Baden Württemberg in comparison to areas with large fields in Saxony Anhalt and Brandenburg. In addition, there are intensive livestock regions and other regions with intensive crop production. Interviewees raised the issue of nutrient recycling and how nutrient recycling can be addressed within and also between the regions, thinking about “closing the system” across different regions. To address such issues and questions it requires living labs at larger scale to jointly address issues across different agroecological zones.</p>
Hungary	<p>Note: Respondents remarked that the questionnaire listed mostly agronomic agroecological practises and failed to include those that are focused on processing (unusual) or consumption (somewhat unusual). A list of agronomic agroecology practises relevant in Hungary, not listed in the questionnaire include: practises of permaculture, regenerative agriculture, agroforestry, biointensive farming, usage of landrace seeds/breeds, the development of local markets and short food chains.</p> <p>Extensive grazing is a characteristic practice of agroecology in Hungary; the maintenance and cultivation of highly biodiverse grasslands are linked to this.</p> <p>Agroforestry is still unusual, the classical agroforestry systems receive no support, however the wooded pastures started to receive state support, despite how there is less and less of it.</p> <p>Digitalization is also a broad concept applicable, where technology could be used to make sure that we put less pressure on our environment, to use targeted measure for pest management and the application of fertilizers and nutrients.</p>

There are several small, but well-established and relatively well-connected NGOs with focus on socio-economic practises, such as the organization of consumer groups, small-scale, family farming, food sovereignty, and economic welfare. Their significance is not determined by the size of their operations, or the extent of their proliferation but their potential to prove to farmers and other stakeholders that such agroecology practises are worth considering.

On the other hand, authorities fail to provide sufficient assistance to those farmers who would be willing to implement alternative measures. There is a lack of straightforward information they would need, which hinders their willingness to try alternative production methods. Also, the bureaucratic burden attached to the calls they could participate in is way too high. As authorities often fail to keep the applicant informed about their applications, they don't feel that they can rely on the financial support needed to make the required investment. There is a great sense of instability that comes with their willingness to participate, which could be improved by more reassuring, supportive communication on behalf of the authorities. Farmers need opportunities, and support so they can escape the logic of extensive farming, avoid mounting debts.

It is more likely that they receive such assistance and support from organizations dedicated to promote the agroecology transition from bottom up. These initiatives however, also require support, as their current resources are just enough to keep them afloat and prevent them from reaching a more significant impact.

There are clear regional differences in the extent of the application of agroecological practices. Close to the Austrian border in Western Hungary, the Austrian farmers tend to implement a wider range of agroecological technologies. The most characteristic practices include soil conservation (reduced till), mixed cropping, and diversified crop rotation. There are also island-like examples, where Hungarian, German, Dutch and other investors adopt a wide range of technologies, including agroecological practices, such as integrated pest management, fertilizer and nutrient management efficiency.

There is also a regional difference in the application of agroecological practices through which soil-related or critical climatic problems could be addressed, such as soil erosion or exposure to drought. These practices include the use of cover crops, water retention, and conservation tillage. Farmers in these critical areas tend to react faster and they proactively look for solutions on their own when they begin to sense these problems.

Practices related to biodiversity conservation are most likely to be linked to nature protection areas and national parks. These territories are often under cultivation. They need to comply with a wide range of requirements, at different levels. Therefore, they often apply

	<p>agroecological production methods that fit into the agro-environmental management programs of these territories.</p> <p>Consumer associations with their innovative consumption practices in support of the agroecology transition are mainly organized around cities and major towns. Organizing access to mass catering could address this geographical inequality producers in more rural areas with insufficient access to consumer markets face.</p>
Iceland	<p>The interviewees agree that most agroecology-based practices are unusual in Iceland. This is due to the type of agricultural systems, which are mostly based on perennial grasses (with semi-permanent fields), with cattle and sheep. According to the farmer advisor, mixed cropping systems (integrating livestock and crops) are a common practice but recycling of nutrients to improve efficiency at the farm scale is not. On the other hand, the scientist reported that recycling of nutrients is one of the major research focuses in Iceland, not only within farms but also from urban to agricultural areas. At the national level, the Soil Conservation Service is very active in wetland restoration; farmers get subsidies for restoring wetlands and there is not a specific focus on paludiculture. Agricultural production is limited to a small area, with regional differences due to different soil types and volcanic activity. Cattle farming is more localized than sheep, which is more widespread (also in areas that have been categorized as land not in a good state, which can cause conflicts between farmers and the soil conservation service).</p>
Ireland	<p>Many of these practices are core concepts for a number of different farming systems (e.g. organic, regenerative and silviopasture systems) and their respective networks and organisations (outlined below in section 9 below) that apply them. Whereas the some of the mentioned practices, such as biodiversity preservation, cover crops and fertiliser management, for other agri-food systems of farming have a range of development and applied in a more limited way. Regarding Conservation tillage, Mixed Cropping Systems, Diversified Crop Rotation, Cover Crops is taking off in the last years, promoted by Base Ireland (https://www.baseireland.ie/). Specifically, cover crops are well established in the last 5 years, so it can be considered as a common practice in Ireland. Fertiliser and Nutrient Management Efficiency/recycling is considered a very common practice in Ireland. A lot of projects were spent in Biodiversity preservation, but there is only somewhat adopted. Sustainable Water Management is concentrated mainly in the dairy sector. More specifically, for wetland restorations there is significant activities on peatlands in Ireland (a target of 40,000 ha for peatland restoration) whereas the system of Paludiculture in wetlands is more limited and is currently in a more exploratory phase to determine its viability etc.</p> <p>The interviewees mentioned other practices, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Natural Capital accounting at farm level, Climate neutral and resilient farms - Farm Zero C – BiOrbic, Bioeconomy SFI Research Centre.

	<p>o Multispecies management and legume incorporation in the crops.</p> <p>Agroecology would be more dominant where there is less intensification (e.g., marginal lands), mainly in West of Ireland. However, in the South and the East of the country, with more intensification in agriculture production, agroecology is less developed or focussed on agroecology principles at a certain level. Nonetheless there are projects that are piloting or demonstrating these types of approaches in more intensive agricultural systems (such projects would include the BRIDE project and Teagasc Signpost Farms).</p> <p>The Irish European Innovation Partnership Scheme (www.gov.ie) projects cover a range of areas including: restoring, preserving and enhancing ecosystems related to agriculture and forestry; promoting resource efficiency and supporting the shift towards a low carbon and climate resilient economy in agriculture, food and forestry sectors; preservation of agricultural landscapes, water quality, resources efficiency and biodiversity</p> <p>These projects are excellent examples of living labs and agroecology practices, social movements that integrate scientific and multi-actor approaches. These include: Enable Conservation Tillage (ECT); Maximising Organic Production Systems (MOPS); OviData; Sustainable Uplands Agri-environment Scheme (SUAS); Danú Farming Group; The Duncannon Blue Flag Farming and Communities Scheme; North Connemara Locally Led Agri-environmental Scheme; Mulkear EIP; Farming Rathcroghan Project; Inishowen Upland Farmers Project; Blackstairs Farming Futures; Sustainable Agricultural Plan for the MacGillycuddy Reeks; Allow Project - Duhallow Farming for Blue Dot Catchments; Caomhnú Árann; Cúlra Créafóige; BRIDE - Biodiversity Regeneration in a Dairying Environment; Locally Led Scheme for the Conservation of the Hen Harrier; Protecting Farmland Pollinators; Conservation of Breeding Curlew in Ireland; Pearl Mussel Project.</p> <p>As a final reflection, one of the interviewees mentioned the importance of bioeconomy policy to involve agroecology, because this policy include the following principles: Sustainability; Food First; Cascading Use and precautionary principle.</p>
Latvia	<p>While different views were expressed how commonly applied agroecological practices are, common application was indicated by at least two interviewees for integrated pest management and biological control and cover crops. These practices are relatively easy to implement without major changes to current systems. Interviewees agreed that wetland restoration with paludiculture is rather unusual, while other agroecological practices listed are applied to some extent. Some regional variations in the application of practices were indicated, e.g. depending on soils, relief, moisture and climate factors. Crop rotation differs between regions with simple rotations in the bread producing regions. More intensive agriculture is common in fertile plains with little uptake of agroecological practices. There are also regional differences regarding agroecological practices for sustainable water</p>

	<p>management, cover crops and fertilizer and the efficiency of nutrient management. Nitrate vulnerable zone have been set in Latvia with increased requirements for farmers to protect water quality from pollution with nitrates. These requirements include preparation of a fertilization plan, periods when spreading of fertilizers is prohibited, maximum nitrogen fertilization rates for crops and the requirement that a certain part of agricultural land has to be covered by green areas in autumn and winter.</p>
Lichtenstein	<p>In Lichtenstein, 40% of the agriculture is farmed organically. This is also reflected in the extent of agroecology-based practices that are common in Lichtenstein: many agroecology based practices and principles are generally perceived as common, such as “integrated pest management and biological control”, “diversified crop rotation”, “cover crops”, “fertiliser and nutrient management efficiency/recycling”, “biodiversity preservation” and “circularity in biomass utilisation”. “Sustainable Water Management” is slightly less common and “wetland restoration with paludiculture” as well as “mixed cropping systems” are perceived as to some extent common. Only “conservation tillage” is seen as unusual in Lichtenstein.</p> <p>Lichtenstein is very small and has a very high percentage of organic farms (40%). 40% of the farms and 40% of the agricultural area are managed organically. This agriculture naturally implies the majority of the practices mentioned.</p> <p>Lichtenstein has a valley area and a mountain area. In the valley area, along the Rhine, the most fertile soils are found. That is why vegetable growing and arable farming are mainly found there. In the mountain</p>
Lithuania	<p>While different views were expressed how commonly applied agroecological practices are, interviewees agreed that cover crops, conservation tillage and fertiliser and nutrient management are relatively commonly applied compared to other practices listed. These practices are relatively easy to implement without major changes to current systems and supported through agri-environmental payments. Comparably little experience was identified with mixed cropping systems. Uncertainty was expressed about circularity in biomass utilisation, but interviewees indicated the production of pellets and packaging as well as composting as rather unusual specific practices. Some regional variations in the application of practices were indicated. Differences in soil fertility are a key driver of those variations in the application of agroecological practices. Central parts of Lithuania have the most fertile soils and intensive crop production with fewer agroecological practices and low uptake of agri-environmental measures. Agroecological practices such as biodiversity preservation and wetland management are more commonly take up on land with poorer soil quality in Eastern Lithuania. Western Lithuania has a longer tradition of cattle systems with a higher share of grassland related practices on traditional cattle farming systems (biodiversity preservation). Eco Schemes could have the potential to increase</p>

	attention for, and uptake of, agroecological practices in the coming years.
Luxembourg	<p>In Luxembourg, a lot of the agroecological principles are already included in organic farming. However, many agroecology based practices and principles are on average perceived as less common such as “mixed cropping systems” and “diversified crop rotation”, “circularity in biomass utilisation”, “wetland restoration with paludiculture” and “sustainable water management”. The agro-ecology based practices “Conservation tillage”, and “cover crops”, “integrated pest management and biological control”, “fertiliser and nutrient management efficiency/recycling”, and “biodiversity preservation” are on average neutral. Only “fertiliser and nutrient management efficiency/recycling” is on average considered as common. Further agroecology-based practices like agroforestry programs and programs involving structural elements for insect biodiversity are starting. Other agroecological practices such as composting was forbidden until last year, as compost was considered as waste.</p> <p>In Luxembourg, there are only slight agricultural difference between the north and the south. The northern region is more hilly, has more grassland and has in general more agricultural area than the southern region. But there are water protection areas where the following practices are enforced by law: reduced-tillage, cover crops, reduced fertilisation; Moreover, there are nature conservation zones, where no tillage and no fertilisation is permitted. In viticulture, there is usually a lot of pesticides applied, but they have started to work a lot with pheromones too.</p>
Netherlands	<p>In the Netherlands, agroecology-based practices and principles are on average common, with cover crops and integrated pest management and biological control being the most common practices. Among all the listed practices, mixed cropping systems are seen as the least common. Another agroecological practices that is common in the Netherlands is mixed farming. This important practice has, however, still room for improvement. For mixed farming, crops and animals are produced simultaneously. However, this does not mean that crops and animals are farmed on the same farm, but in the same region, having exchange of for example manure. A further agroecology-based practice is the saline cultivation, which is perceived as common. Integrated pest management and biological control is part of the agricultural policy in the Netherlands and they are common in greenhouses, where also recycling of nutrients etc. are important and very commonly used. There are a lot of research projects in this field going on, right now. However, it is probably only a minor part of the farmers, such as pioneers and organic farmers, who apply these techniques in the Netherlands. Most of the farmers are waiting and apply the well-known techniques. Conservation tillage is used to prevent erosion and is commonly used in the south, where the landscape is more hilly.</p> <p>In the Netherlands, the regional differences with respect to the extent of agroecology-based applications concern mainly the soil structures:</p>

	<p>there are more erosion problems with sandy soils in the west, which is at the coast and more densely populated than other regions. There are mostly greenhouses and horticulture found. The application of biological control is more common there but also other highly innovative applications. peat and clay soils are more common in the middle of the country and in the north, where measures are needed to maintain the soil quality. The east of the country is more divers and more agroecological practices are found. There are also historical and cultural difference in agriculture, which are reflected in the application of different principles. In the south, the coastal region, the soils are dominated by chalk and salinization is a problem. There and also in other parts of the Netherlands, intensive livestock keeping is performed. The animal production is considered too intensive, leading to health problems for the people, including the transmittance of diseases from animals to humans. Also the nitrogen deposition derived from this meat production has a negative impact on the environment. Thus, it would be desirable to have less meat production in the Netherlands, but the farmers get a good price for it.</p> <p>Local and agroecological production could be fostered by appropriate/true pricing. It is complicated to distinguish between the different agroecosystems. For the organic agriculture there is a label (on EU level). The agroecological transition is linked to economic issues. Thus, the farmers rely on their income which must be feasible also in agroecology (true pricing discussion). Also the working hours must be feasible for the farmers, for examples the mechanical weeding can take a lot of labour hour, more than spraying and sometimes it is not possible to perform this task within the available working hours. In the Netherlands, there are mostly one-man/woman farms.</p>
Norway	<p>In Norway, many agroecology based practices and principles, such as “integrated pest management and biological control”, “conservation tillage”, “diversified crop rotation” and “cover crops” are generally perceived as somewhat common to common, since Norway has only few pests that need to be addressed. “Fertiliser and nutrient management efficiency/recycling”, “circularity in biomass utilisation” and “sustainable water management” also, are generally perceived as somewhat common to common. Also “mixed cropping systems”, “biodiversity preservation” and “wetland restoration with paludiculture” are seen as somewhat common to common by the majority, with one or two national contact point, however, who perceived these practices as unusual in Norway. It was mentioned that wetland restoration in Norway means conservation rather than restoration on farming landscapes. On other landscapes, however, wetlands are more restored or recreated. Wetland restoration has been done for many years on environmental sites, in cooperation with agricultural sites. Regarding sustainable water management in Norway, irrigation is less concerned than the protection of the aqua-environment. Regarding further agroecological practices, agroforestry was named, as farmers in Norway own often both forests and land but usually there are no trees on</p>

	<p>farmlands. Grazing in the mountains is common in animals. Restoration agriculture with focus on soil health as well as biochar are coming. However, there is enough land in Norway to spread the manure. Still, in the big farms with up to 1000 cattle, spreading of the manure can lead to pollution of the soil. But in general, the farms in Norway are small, often even too small to give enough money for a living. And with the drop of the goals on organic agriculture set by the government, the number of organic farms in Norway is going down. There is not much money from the authorities for organic agriculture.</p> <p>Norway is a quite long country, covering different climatic zones and different length in growing seasons. This is reflected in the use of agroecological applications and in the farm sizes that are adapted to the land: Cows and sheep husbandry is found in the west and the north, where the conditions are more wet and where smaller farms are found. Crops are more found in the south and the east, where the land is more flat, with less forests and longer growing seasons. Grain production is for animal fodder, food grains are imported. In the north, cereals cannot be produced to the extent needed. Fruits are also more cultivated in the west. This is all regulated by policies. The policies have the goal to enable the best production in regard to the conditions. Until the 70s and 80s, most farms represented integrated systems where animals and crops were cultivated at the same time. Afterwards the systems changed leading to farms, that had a focus either on crop production or on animal production. Nowadays, this system is desired to be changed to improve the soil fertility. A higher diversity is required. However, climate change will maybe change the conditions for the agriculture. Every year, there is a national meeting with all the stakeholders involved in agriculture in Norway, where the food production goals and the subsidies are being negotiated. Also the sizes of the farms are reflected / adapted based on the amount of people living in that region. Farming in Norway is not so much market driven but based on the budget of the country. As the annual farmer agreement decides on what is subsidised and what not, also agroecology goals can be negotiated, which is however, depending on how much the farmers are interested in agroecology.</p>
Poland	<p>Conservation tillage is very popular because it has a lot support from advisors. It also carries financial benefits (cost saving) for farmers, which has resulted in its popularity. While farmers may be interested in using more agroecological practices, this is not financially viable for them. In Poland, agriculture is not very competitive, and so there is little surplus to re-invest into systemic change (Pawlik). The regional differences are not significant. What impacts on uptake of agroecology are not the regions, but the availability of subsidies for specific practices, and availability of training (less important than the subsidies). Some of the areas which see a greater presence of agroecological practices are those close to national parks, who offer specific incentives or have specific legal policies for land management changes for ecological outcomes. As a result, the voievodships of Warmia and</p>

	<p>Mazury, West Pomeranian, Podlaskie, and Mazowsze see a higher presence of organic farming. Overall, the financial incentives are seen by both interviewees as the strongest driver for land managers in Poland. While there is some demand for organic products, the number of organic farms is actually falling due to the burden and cost of certification, and an insufficient price premium and lack of viable market strategies.</p>
Serbia	<p>The main agricultural crops are wheat, corn, soy, sunflower, and to a lesser extent rapeseed and sugar beet. There are no significant regional differences related to the perception of AE, even if the interest for agroecology is more dominant in autonomous province of Vojvodina that has an extensive agricultural production due to this specific geography. In Serbia, agricultural 'production is mostly present in northern province of Vojvodina in the fertile Pannonian Plain (45% of all used arable land) [...]. It is estimated that around 1.1 million people in Serbia (15.70% of total population) is employed on agricultural farms, with around 530,000 being employed in farms all-year long (as of 2018). As of 2018, there is a total of 564,542 agricultural farms in Serbia, of which the vast majority of 99.7% are traditional family farms.'</p> <p>Regarding the question on 'On a scale from 1 to 5 how commonly applied are the following agroecological principles and/or agroecology-based practices in your country?', it was indicated that integrated pest management and biological control are associated with organic agriculture and that conservation tillage is still in adoption process and mainly used by the smaller producers. The relevant agroecological practices that are well integrated in agricultural work are related to the soil quality improvement and the soil health practices (i.e. soil quality improvement through use of organic and microbiological fertiliser, or use of legume crops, etc.). The use of fertilisers itself is not an issue in Serbia, rather the wrong use of fertilisers. The decline in the soil quality, resulting in decrease of humus content in some areas for up to 1%, is a consequence of number of interlinked factors, as lesser production of manure and decline in animal keeping resulting from 1990s economic crisis and sanctions in Serbia. This means that the fertilisation of soil would need to be developed through other methods as cover-crops, inter-crops, plant fertilisation. Competent authorities for agriculture each year organize support for free soil sampling and analysis for registered agricultural produces, with recommendations from experts about need for fertiliser based on the analysis performed.</p>
Slovakia	<p>The implementation of agro-ecology based practices is still challenging because there aren't enough tools provided to support the "greening of agriculture". There are still no operation groups set up in the relevant ministries to directly address this challenge. The stakeholders also have some reservations that prevent them from engaging in the implementation of even those agroecological practices that fit their operations. There should be tools they could rely on such as experience based assistance linked to on-farm networks or living labs. The</p>

	<p>implementation of the results of scientific research into practice should be supported more deliberately. Living labs are recognized as an optimal tool to address this challenge.</p> <p>There are two agroecological practices, not listed in the questionnaire, that are recognized to have significant impact on Slovakia's agroecological transition. One of these is traditional agroforestry and the other is crop circle farming. Legislation should be adapted to recognize traditional agroforestry as a management system in line with the principles of agroecology. It should be done, so the relevant support schemes could be applied to it (CAP-RDP). Even though it has been recognized as a practice, which has the potential to support the transition at its initial stage. These practices build on historic, mostly local knowledge. There is also a growing interest in crop circle farming, which is already present to some extent.</p> <p>When it comes to the application of agroecology-based practices, organic farmers are ahead of the game. Also some extensive farmers unintentionally implement certain agroecology practices.</p> <p>There are regional differences in the extent of application of agroecological practices. These are due not just to climatic, but also to economic conditions. The Southern and Western regions of Slovakia, where most of its agricultural production is concentrated, are characterized by intensive production. In the Northern regions, due to the more severe climatic conditions and the specific soil quality, forms of extensive agriculture are developed with practices familiar with agroecology. The extent of application of agroecology principles is more or less dependent on the economic performance of agricultural entities. Stability increases the probability of the application of agroecological practices. Being located in or near to protected areas is also a driving force. Even though agriculture in the Southern part of Slovakia is more intensive, there are still farmers interested in "more nature friendly" practices.</p>
Switzerland	<p>In Switzerland, many agroecology based practices and principles are generally perceived as common, such as "integrated pest management and biological control", "conservation tillage", "diversified crop rotation", "cover crops". Also "fertiliser and nutrient management efficiency/recycling" and "biodiversity preservation" are perceived as common by most but not all national contact points. However, biodiversity preservation is seen as one of the weaknesses in Switzerland, as the measures are too weak and biodiversity preservation doesn't work with island solutions. "Circularity in Biomass Utilisation" and "Sustainable Water Management" are seen as somewhat common. "Wetland restoration with paludiculture" is seen as unusual in Switzerland by most contact points. Other practices such as "diversified farms", "transdisciplinary R&I", "farmer-consumer interactions in direct sale, farm shop, solidarity farming (SOLAWI)", "agroforestry", "animal husbandry practices – higher animal welfare, Mutterkuhhaltung, combining egg-broiler production: dual breeds" and "grassland conservation" are common to somewhat common in Switzerland.</p>

	<p>Individual agroecological measures very often implemented. The comprehensive system approach is however mostly missing. Also, alternative markets are coming up (e.g. solidarity economy, CSAs). Additionally, there are some initiatives of social-agriculture e.g. working with children, mental health, etc. It was mentioned, that there is a shortcoming of fairness principles in the listed principles: i.e. how these practices ensure gender equity, youth employment etc. In Switzerland, there are regional differences in the agriculture due to topography and therefore climate and agricultural conditions. This result is a high diversity of farming systems in Switzerland, predominantly small-scale agriculture. But also, the policy regulations have an effect. The best agriculture land are in lowlands of Switzerland. There and in the hill zone, the land is used more intensively and simpler mechanical management is applied with individual agroecological measures. The mountain zone, like the alps, is more extensively and thus more sustainably used. More agroecological approaches are applied there. The process of re-thinking the practices and viewing them from a more holistic viewpoint, the 'new' definition has arrived in research and society. At the moment, we are missing the food system aspect what is driven by the consumer side – this should be included in the implementation of agroecology.</p>
Turkey	<p>The aim of the developed of plant breeding programs is to gain drought, pest and disease resistances of new plant varieties. For this purpose both public and private institutions as well as NGOs cooperate to develop new varieties that can be used by farmers in Turkey. The regional differences in Turkey are mainly due to different topography, climatic and soil conditions. Depending on the farm scale and infrastructure of the farmers in the country, there are also differences in the cultivation techniques and product demands. Many differences in specific regions manifest through 'lessons learned'. For instance, if one farmer is planting cotton, the neighbour farmers most likely will do the same as they can share their experiences and learn from each other. This counts especially for products that are more complicated to grow (e.g. cotton instead of most cereals) which shows that also education plays a big role in creating regional differences. Linked to the education is also the use of new technologies which are necessary for the production of certain products and not spread evenly over the whole country. Projects that are developed to produce new technologies and to work on priority issues such as the needs of the agricultural sector. The hurdles of using interdisciplinary approaches are fostered through different organisations. These are mainly TAGEM R&D institutes, universities, TUBITAK, but also the private sector to transfer knowledge and new technologies to farmers and agricultural industrialists. The General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policy (TAGEM) under the umbrella of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry is mainly responsible of the National Agricultural Research System within the country.</p>
United Kingdom	<p>In the UK, the extent to which agroecology practices are used differs between regions. This is in part due to the legacy of agricultural specialisation, with livestock and grassland management in the West and grain production in the East and South East. Arable farmers have a</p>

greater awareness of agroecology practices than livestock farmers (e.g. see in quantitative responses to Q5, interview 3 responded mainly negatively as she was focusing on the practices in Wales, where livestock farming dominates). The extent to which practices are used also differs between regions in the UK due to soil type (which influences e.g. uptake of no- or min-till), and climate (e.g. Scotland does not use cover crops much). Uptake also differs between size of holdings, with agroecology practices being more attractive to people doing small scale growing. Minimum tillage is now widely applied, as shown in national government surveys, and the uptake is strongly influenced by soil type. Mixed farming is seeing a come-back.

AE4EU: There are some specific 'hot beds' of agroecological practice, in certain regions (e.g. South West, such as Devon and Cornwall, where land used to be cheaper and attracted like-minded people), around some cities (London and Bristol), and in county Leitrim in Northern Ireland. In Scotland there has been work on improving land management around river estuaries to manage water pollution, which has included using agroecological practices (but not systemic change). Overall the use of agroecological practices is low. Some new practices which are gaining traction are agroforestry and composting. There is a growing use of green manures and overall better nutrient management on farms.

Annex C: Research and innovation systems

Table 11: Partners synthesis of the interviews with respect to the entry: *"Research and innovation systems in support of agroecology"*

Belgium	<p>There is few research on agroecology in both regions in Belgium. Most of the interviewees indicated that far more financial resources are needed for research in agroecology. Because research is linked to policy ambitions, a clear(er) signal and funding from the policy side is needed to invest more in agroecology research. However, there is a clear regional difference in policy ambitions between Wallonia and Flanders, which is also reflected in the budget that is made available for research on organic farming and agroecology. In Wallonia, they have a clear ambition to increase agricultural area under organic production up to 30%. In Flanders, government supports organic farming, but this is insufficiently reflected in resources or policies, probably due to strong lobby of agro industry supporting intensive production systems. A challenge mentioned in all interviews is the lack of systems thinking by researchers (especially mentioned in the Walloon region). Researchers focus on separate aspects of agroecology (single agroecological practices) and do not always look from a systems perspective. This is because of a lack of systems thinking in the education of the researchers. Moreover, multi-actor based research integrating different stakeholders' perspectives (system approach) is time consuming and is in conflict with the current research system where high publication rate is expected. One interviewee mentioned also that Wallonia participated in the EIP at a later stage compared to many other regions. One interviewee also mentioned the lack of rewarding farmers (financial and emotional) when they participate in research</p>
Cyprus	<p>There are limited resources and research programs focused on agroecology in Cyprus. As in other countries, research is driven by funding. Therefore, in order to foster a transition towards agroecology-based practices, more funds should be addressed to agroecological research and related research infrastructures. There is also a need to increase the policy focus on agroecological issues.</p> <p>Research infrastructures and research programmes can be improved by involving farmers in the research. However, there is a problem in Cyprus because they manage small scale farms, and for them, there is a high risk to dedicate some portion of the land for research. Another limitation is that farmers are usually old and refuse to change their practices.</p>
Czech Rep.	<p>There are only a few research programs linked to agroecology, but generally they don't focus on the agroecological transition. The main coverage of the current research programs is mostly limited to field level farming practices. Nearly all calls for research tend to include some 'sustainability buzzwords', but the actual deliverables are just production oriented. There is room for improvement, as 'the social part', 'the value chain part' of agroecology is not sufficiently covered by</p>

these projects. “There is a need to apply a systems approach, otherwise one simply can’t pursue agroecology.” The current research projects do not reflect farmers' agroecology related needs. As they might not even be aware that they have some. And mostly because there are very few farmers with good relationships with researchers and there are only a few research organizations that include a focus on the implementation of agroecological practices. Even those research projects that are meant to focus on such practices fail to communicate well with their intended audience, the farmers. The kind of requirements, against which the results of these research projects are evaluated, fail to motivate them to better communicate their results or to provide venues where they could work with the farmers on their implementation. Budget restructuring of these programs, changing the criteria against which they are evaluated and adding steps to their design, and providing tools to support the implementation of their results could shift the range of supported actions. This could make the research programs focus on the more practical aspects of the agroecological initiatives, being more responsive to farmers' needs. Keeping in mind that currently most of the listed agroecological practices are predominantly implemented by organic farmers. Agroecological research should keep assisting the promotion of organic farming, with a stronger focus on the inclusion of social aspects and mending the “huge gap between organic production and the market”. Living-labs and on-farm experimentation, both are new and relatively new trends. They should be used as a model and be further developed to address the needs of agroecology. There is quite good research infrastructure available based on on-farm experimentation, demonstration farms, and access to successful organic farms. The further development of these could help the agroecological transition. Even the recently emerging living labs fall short of the strict definition of how living labs should be, as they would require deeper engagement and broader outreach. Even though the current research initiatives are mostly focused on farm level practices, there is still not enough cooperation with farmers. This hinders their efforts to develop suitable tools to promote agroecological transition. The current research infrastructure is strong enough, but it is not used to strengthen the agroecological transition. It needs to have a stronger focus, more holistic approach. It is not enough to have a few programs that specifically focus on such transitions. It should be integrated into other programs. The balance between the three main pillars of the research infrastructure was disrupted by the strengthening of the role of state funded research institutes in agricultural research (relative to the size of research done by the Academy of Science, universities, and the research coordinated by NGOs or the private sector). It is problematic, as state funded research tends to be less effective when it comes to complex issues such as agroecology. Also, they are not that well connected to the actual agricultural practices. Besides, there is less pressure on them to be productive. Even though some of them deliver exceptional work, this imbalance partial to state-funded research institutes is hindering

	<p>agroecological transition. There is a need to organize research in a more 'systems way of thinking', where cooperation between different fields of science is better connected and coordinated. But so far these links have been built artificially, not based on a complex system understanding. There are gaps between the fields of knowledge. The weakest point is between natural and social sciences, which is quite common in post-communist countries, where "policy research used to be a crime". It is still challenging to apply social science-based policies into real life.</p>
Denmark	<p>Both interviewees agreed that within Denmark there is a good basis for research and innovative approaches in DK and the agricultural sector have traditionally been good at using them, but they need new thinking, especially from abroad. It was also mentioned that there are good and long-lasting experiments at Foulum (AU) (and used to be in FOOD at Fyn (KU)) within organic and agroecological crop rotations. But the research at AU and KU could be devoted to a higher degree to more innovative experimental use in agroecology including non-chemical pest control in diversified crop. We need to develop the use of living labs in a form with broad and actual stakeholder engagement and including a landscape level perspective. It was said that within Denmark, "we can and have a lot, but it needs adjusting and updating".</p> <p>One challenge identified was that on EU level we have H2020 which clusters agriculture, environment and biodiversity together. But infrastructure and research are separated into different focus paths. This should be connected more closely. Research needs to be closer connected in general and there is a lot of funding to receive, if a higher level is collaboration is reached. Mission-driven research is a hot topic at the moment, internationally.</p>
Estonia	<p>In Estonia, there are different opinions on the support of agroecology in research and innovation. However, the farmer's needs are seen as sufficiently reflected in current research activities. There is a disagreement among the national contact points on whether research infrastructures are considered sufficiently attuned to support agroecological transitions and whether there is sufficient focus of research programs on an agroecological transition or not. Also, whether sufficient financial resources are allocated for research into agroecology-based practices is seen opposingly (e.g. to high extent and not at all). There is also a disagreement on the use of living labs and other forms of multi-actor involvement in agroecological research and innovation (e.g. on some extent and not at all). And also, the extent of the application of on farm experimentation in research activities is seen differently in Estonia (e.g. on some extent and not at all).</p>
Finland	<p>There are rather different opinions on the role of research and innovation systems in support of agroecology in Finland. Especially the focus of research infrastructures and research programs is on one hand seen as sufficiently attuned to support agroecological transition and on the other hand as not sufficiently attuned. However, there is a clear agreement that living labs and other forms of multi-actor involvement are used in agroecological research and innovation and that on farm</p>

	<p>experimentation is applied in research activities.</p> <p>The current research infrastructure in Finland is in good exchange with the industry, farmers and retail. The aim is to include different actors in the projects and find a dialog with them all. Pure research sites are getting less: on few sites empirical research can still be done. The culture of doing agricultural research has changed, more research is done on farms. This enables better communication with the farmers. But the research has to be adjusted also to the farmer's needs.</p> <p>More system oriented research is needed. Agricultural and food systems are very complex and include many sectors and actors. Participatory research and multidisciplinary research would be helpful. Long-term planning and longer projects with sufficient funding would be needed. Recently, the government has not allocated enough money to research. This poses a risk for limited quality of research at the university.</p> <p>Moreover, the projects are too short and it is difficult that the knowledge stays alive and is transferred. The communication between scientists and other actors should be improved. Also, for the scientists it would be important to know how complex a farm system is. When they work alone (not on the farm) they often miss the complexity of a farm. Combining of social, economic and ecological elements are often getting missing in the research.</p> <p>Food production is not a prioritised topic in Finland.</p>
France	<p>All interviewees agree that Research Infrastructures (RIs) and other Open Innovation Arrangements are a key to foster agroecology transition, but that there is not enough emphasis on it so far. These steps have to be conducted not only on a national, but also regional and local level. Furthermore, it is important that RIs are developed in a co-creational way and need to be adopted geographically on the needs of the farmers. In general RIs are important as sometimes a "controlled" environment is needed to elucidate mechanisms and processes that are involved (e.g. micro-related techniques). Further, research programs play an important role in the transition process, and many of the applications for funding, deal with the topic of agroecology transition, even if many of them are often not innovative enough to speed up the process. Here it is up to the scientists to improve that, as innovation cannot (only) come from the farmers themselves. The finances to support are not enough from the science perspective, while the ministry would be willing to fund more, but not always receives enough proper project proposals to support within France. Regarding needs, the farmers have to be completely convinced by understandable practices they can use for the transition, that also ensure them economical security. This aspect needs to be clearly reflected in the research activities and the focus on it has to be increased. The interviewees agree that Living Labs (LLs) are being developed in an increasing number, but still not spread widely enough all over France. Another problem is that due to the reason of this relatively new term and concept, some so called LLs can not always be identified as one. For LLs and it is important that many different stakeholders work together and share the space to</p>

	<p>co-create, develop platforms etc. One of the hurdles for all, RIs, LLs and other research programs is to connect the right people, keep them included, motivated and the network of people running over a longer period than just few years. Another big aspect on how to improve RIs is to use broader reaching media to spread the need, principles, research, results, practices etc. of agroecology transition. It is advantageous if the information and news are reaching people directly instead of making them search for it. As RIs and research programs often work local or regional, the outcomes and outputs need to be adopted to various scales, farming system, environmental conditions and the needs of the different types of farmers. Here science needs to push more into the right direction .</p>
Germany	<p>Interviewees generally agreed only to a limited extent with the statements regarding research and innovation systems in support of agroecology. Several issues were highlighted. For example, research programmes reflect the awareness and intention to address transitions to agroecology, but interviewees highlighted a limited understanding of social components and the knowledge system of agroecology transitions that require a stronger focus. Financial resources are allocated for research into single agroecological practices (e.g. integrated pest management or conservation tillage), but a shift in paradigm in research funding was suggested to enable funding of long term research on systemic changes (and improvements) of a transition to agroecology. Farmer needs are reflected to a limited extent in current research activities. More research is required to better capture and understand the needs of the large diversity of farmers and farms across Germany. Living labs and other forms of multi-actor involvement are used to a limited extent in agroecological research and innovation. Real world settings are important for on-farm experimentation in research activities agroecological practices. Activities of research informing practice were acknowledged, but a gap was seen in the other direction of knowledge and information flow, practice informing research. Here networks of living labs and research infrastructures have an important role to play.</p> <p>Interviewees acknowledged that a good basis of infrastructure for research on transitions to agroecology exists in Germany. In addition to technical innovations more attention was suggested to be paid to social innovations improving knowledge systems and governance of transitions to agroecology. This would require stronger integration of social sciences and practice within a transdisciplinary research framework. Further improvements suggested include a shift from short term to more long term funding enabling (and securing) research on systemic changes in agroecology transitions. EIP Agri projects and networks could be further strengthened and better linked across Federal States.</p>
Hungary	<p>The current research infrastructures require huge investments to increase their knowledge, technical, infrastructural and digital capacities, so they could be ready to support the transition. Therefore, targeted governmental support or private funds would be instrumental</p>

	<p>to create an enabling environment. First of all, the concept of agroecology and its principles should be introduced into the current research infrastructure, since their current understanding fails to recognize the importance of the systematic thinking required.</p> <p>Training and education of scientific and technical personnel is needed who would be capable of handling the research equipment specialized in agroecology measurements. Also, researchers should be able to work with multidisciplinary projects, at least understanding the importance of the socioeconomic implications of their work.</p> <p>The availability of financial resources is limited. A big investment (governmental) is needed to adjust current infrastructure to the needs of agroecological research as well.</p> <p>The currently active research institutions rarely focus directly on the agroecology transition. Research conducted by different institutes separately covers a wide range of aspects of agroecology. There is a lack of interaction and coordination among these institutions. The available research infrastructure should be mapped and assessed, looking for connections. There is also no multidisciplinary research present, with a more inclusive focus going beyond specific research interests. Foreign practices and research, innovation structures should be assessed in order to see how they could be adapted. The adaptation of the living lab-like systems is a good example.</p> <p>For research programmes, it would be essential if dedicated research calls (focused on agroecology or agroecology research infrastructures) would be announced with a multi-actor approach on the national level. In Hungary, so far there haven't been such calls announced, the term research infrastructure is also not really known, let alone used (although many university or research centre infrastructures can be considered as such). Better involvement of stakeholders (end-user, procurer, software developers) would be important for research programmes since it is very common that calls operate with a top-down, single or two actor approach.</p> <p>Keeping in mind this all, in Hungary, we are at a stage when the necessary research infrastructures are started to be developed, and there is a list of expectations towards these research infrastructures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research programs should keep in mind social, economic and ecological sustainability when they draft their agenda. ● Research should be made multidisciplinary. ● Research infrastructures should be open to adapt foreign experience. <p>Research should be independent from corporations; at the moment several research activities are influenced by industrial input providers. There is also some greenwashing present in the industry-funded research sector, promoting practices to be in line with the agroecological principles when they couldn't be farther away from that. It should be addressed to prevent further confusion.</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Living- labs and on-farm systems should be made more widespread. ● Farmers should receive training based on their practical experience. ● More stakeholder groups should be engaged in the research infrastructure. ● Agroecology could provide space to promote the engagement of marginalized people. ● Research should be recognized as a tool to support the agroecology transition. ● Research should directly communicate with the farmers. ● The research deliverables should be easily understandable and easily applicable, and should be actively disseminated among the farmers. ● Research should not just address the research community. ● The research infrastructure should include the development and maintenance of channels targeting policy makers. As currently there is no live connection between the research institutions and the policy makers, at least what is available is limited. Without such active communication channels policy makers can't follow the new research trends or incorporate their findings into their measures.
Iceland	<p>The opinion of the two interviewees on the state of research and innovation systems in support of agroecology was very different. The advisor answered “not at all” to all points, pointing out that there are too few people working on agroecology-related issues and that there is a strong need for increase farmers’ knowledge. The researcher, on the other hand, answered “to some” or “to a high” extent, underlining that research infrastructures, programs and financial resources are improving. In particular, the researcher pointed out that infrastructures to support better nutrient cycling and more efficient use of fertilizers are being improved, with a focus on livestock and the related emissions of greenhouse gases (but more should be done, also at the field level).</p>
Ireland	<p>Agroecology is not explicitly recognised in the research infrastructure catalogue or the research programmes. Although there are some research lines or infrastructure into agroecological practices, this is not done usually under an agroecology umbrella. Under the context of EIP operational group, there are few people working on agro-environment schemes and the impact of agriculture on the environment. But also, there are other groups as part of Signpost Programme working on sustainability transition, but it is not totally in line with agroecological transition.</p> <p>Despite this general situation, there is an agreement that the current research infrastructures can be used to foster a transition towards agroecology-based practices. They can be used for creating policy background for policymakers. In particular, Teagasc Johnstown Castle and UCD Lyons Farm may be useful examples, but there may be further scope for other research infrastructures as well, such as those at Teagasc Centres - Moorepark, Athenry, Grange, Oakpark. The current research infrastructure could consider applying agroecological principles to all research developments.</p>

	<p>Two elements potentially can be used to foster that transition Teagasc Advisory Services, Teagasc Signpost Farms and EIP Agri. EIP-AGRI funding facilitates this, and the AECM CAP funding should also contribute in this respect. In addition, this is an action that is sought to be addressed under the DRCD Rural Futures Policy.</p> <p>Moreover, two big infrastructures in Ireland can be used to foster this transition: The National Agricultural Soil Carbon Observatory, Soil Sampling and Analysis Programme.</p> <p>Begin to work on supporting on place the research mechanism and programmes on agroecology-based practices. A critical step that can help foster a transition towards agroecology-based practice in terms of research infrastructure and programmes is to improve communication and elaboration of the term agroecology as an overarching concept that involves different spread elements all together. On the other hand, it is necessary to get mechanisms to put in place living labs and demonstrators to move to TRL 8-9. Also trying to support living lab framework from the research perspective. There is an opportunity to consider how the DAFM Competitive Research Programme Research Plus & Innovation Platform funding instrument could be configured to address this matter. Links could also be created with the proposed CAP Network Innovation Hub to be funded under the CAP Strategic Plan. There is a final comment about the need to engage with Higher Education Institutions such as University College of Dublin to examine the research and innovation system in support of agroecology.</p>
Latvia	<p>Research infrastructure and research programmes in Latvia are seen as relatively well developed in general, but the need for a stronger focus on agroecology combining ecological and social sciences and covering crop and livestock farming was indicated. In addition, enhanced education and awareness raising on agroecology through improved curricula and e-courses were suggested.</p> <p>Financing was identified as a particular issue. Significant investments in the infrastructure do not take place based on regular investments and often rely on the availability of support from EU funds. A more significant State guarantee for the financing of research would be needed, from which regular investments in infrastructure development should be made. Greater availability of national funding for programmes on applied research, experimentation and innovative demonstrations how to improve the development and application of agroecology-based practices was recommended.</p> <p>Improvements in research infrastructure have been made in recent years (with funding from the EU) and have also been positively assessed in the international evaluation of scientific institutions. But the future development and modernisation of research infrastructure could become a major challenge in the near future, given that EU funds have not yet been earmarked for this purpose and national funding does not</p>

	<p>provide sufficient opportunities. Participation in international projects and networks will thus play an important role.</p> <p>The importance and dependency on EU-funded research was also emphasised for living labs and other forms of multi-actor engagement. Multi-actor involvement is often driven by international research. The importance of the continuity in financing multi-actor research was highlighted to enable the building and subsequently utilisation of trusting relationships in multi-actor networks as a basis to address barriers of transitions to agroecology.</p>
Lichtenstein	<p>Lichtenstein does not have its own research infrastructures, but is associated to research infrastructures in Switzerland and Austria. Therefore, the opinion on whether research infrastructures (research facilities) are sufficiently attuned to support agroecological transition, and on whether research programs have focus on agroecological transition is neutral. Farmers needs in an agroecological transition are not seen as sufficiently reflected in current research activities. Also, living labs and other forms of multi-actor involvement are not sufficiently used in agroecological research and innovation and also, on farm experimentation is not seen as often applied in research activities. There are no research institutions in Lichtenstein. There are cooperations, collaborations and research projects together with FiBL Switzerland and FiBL Austria, as well as with Biosuisse, where Lichtenstein is involved. There are also contacts and ideas with the ETH for a project on climate-neutral agriculture. In Lichtenstein, the main task of the advisory service is to ensure that research results are put into practice and that agroecological practices can be promoted. In order to promote the transition to agroecological practices, the network to farmers should be built with a focus on agroecology. First of all, it is necessary to consider what can and cannot be implemented by the farmers. Appropriate structures should be created and/or adapted.</p>
Lithuania	<p>National research programmes focus to some extent on issues related to transitions to agroecology, but the research is commissioned and done more in an ad-hoc approach and could be better integrated in a long term strategy. Research programmes also need to be better connected to farms with a research agenda that is based on a stronger consideration of the needs identified by and with farmers.</p> <p>Additional issues raised included a perceived lack of interest of environmental research organisations in research on agroecology and a need to better integrate environmental and agricultural monitoring activities and programmes. Research on agroecology is currently mainly done agricultural research organisations focusing on agricultural issues. One possible reason indicated for the lack of interest of environmental research organisations in research on agroecology is the priority setting of research activities through funding schemes for environmental research organisations. Also agroecology is a transdisciplinary research subject that might require rethinking of traditional nature protection research integrating social sciences and humanities into classic environmental research. Here is a need for further capacity building.</p>

	<p>Agricultural and environmental monitoring is currently done independently. The analysis of the impacts of a transition to agroecology would benefit from an integration of environmental and agricultural monitoring to better link agricultural management to changes in the environment. It would be important for environmental monitoring programmes (e.g. biodiversity monitoring programmes) to be able to monitor changes in agricultural management to provide evidence for future policy support for agroecological practices. The Ministry of Agriculture is preparing new rules for research with living labs to foster a longer time frame for research projects and the involvement of local actors, which is expected to increase the use of living labs in agroecological research and innovation. Networks of research institutes and universities with advisory centres exist (e.g. on soil issues) that future living labs can build on. Connections of the Lithuanian research infrastructure with European networks and organisations (e.g. ANAEE) are strengthened.</p>
Luxembourg	<p>In Luxembourg, research and innovation systems in general are only to a limited extent perceived as supportive of agroecology. There are not at all sufficient financial resources are allocated for research into agroecology-based practices. Research infrastructures (research facilities) are to a limited extent attuned to support agroecological transition and also research programs have a limited focus on agroecological transition. Farmers needs in an agroecological transition are only to a limited extent reflected in current research activities and living labs and other forms of multi-actor involvement are used to a limited extent in agroecological research and innovation. Only on farm experimentation is to some extent applied in research activities. Current research infrastructures can be used to foster a transition towards agroecology-based practices by allocating more money for research. Moreover, clear goals are needed, going into the direction of agroecology, IBLA is already working into this direction. The competences and knowledge in regard to agroecology have to be built up until then ecologists have to fill this gap. In Luxembourg, there are several universities, IBLA, LIST, School for arable farming (LTA), Naturparks with small research projects, Municipality syndicates SICONO, ministry for environmental protection covers the protection of the forest and not the ministry for agriculture. The current research infrastructures and research programmes can be improved to foster a transition towards agroecology-based practices by initialising more research programmes. Research in the field of agroecology is rather new and yet, there are small research infrastructure for agroecology available. However, the research priority of Luxembourg is not about disease prevention but about fighting symptoms of the current situation. A higher status for agroecology projects is needed and would also foster the build-up of competencies for agroecology.</p>
Netherlands	<p>In the Netherlands, research infrastructures (research facilities), research programmes are sufficiently attuned to support agroecological</p>

transition, however, collaborations among the researchers are essential. The agroecology system in the Netherlands is strong but fragmented. Cooperation is very important to integrate the results of monodisciplinary research (on IPM, on nutrients, on biodiversity) into a system with multidisciplinary research in the agroecology-system. Moreover, the goal should be an integrated approach also with the interaction with relevant stakeholders that are needed to meet the aim. In the Netherlands, the research infrastructures are very dense with a lot of Universities and institutes for applied sciences, and the research programs are attuned to support an agroecological transition to a high extent. The research infrastructures can be used for example, by having experiments that compare different management techniques (agroecological and others) and relevant inputs on test farms and green houses. Moreover, in living labs, experiments can be developed in cooperation with farmers and researchers. In regard to consumer sciences, experiments involving consumers can be very promising. Research facilities in the Netherlands include well equipped sensory labs and high level interview methods that can increasingly be used for agroecological research. There is also a test restaurant, where behavioural studies can be done, for agroecological products. This is important, as agroecological products need to be accepted by the consumers. Additionally, test farms can be used to raise the awareness for agroecology by open farm days for schools and for the whole society. In the Netherlands, farmers needs in an agroecological transition are only partly reflected in current research activities. It is a researchers translation of the farmer needs. Question driven research is important for a transition towards agroecology. The farmers needs can be addressed in living labs and will give possibilities to bring agroecology further.

The current research infrastructures in the Netherlands can be improved by making them and the research performed more visible to the public. By making agroecological research visible, the awareness of the people can be raised, leading to a change in consumer behaviour. Moreover, the ministry should be supported in the transition.

For the agroecological transition, skills on several scales need to be considered: regional research skill, national research skill and international research skills. After all, they need to be linked and thus, can build stronger relationships. Living labs are suggested to help to strengthen these relationships. Current research infrastructures and research programmes can be improved by cooperation, by integrating think tanks into projects, by integrating economic aspects and by a multi-discipline approach.

The research infrastructures in the Netherlands are very good. But unfortunately, some infrastructures have closed, such as a bee research institute that worked in connections to hobby bee keepers. Such institutions would, however, help to make the connection to the people / society and also contribute to biodiversity at the same time.

Norway	<p>The opinions on the role of research and innovation systems in support of agroecology in Norway are more balanced than in other countries. Research infrastructures are seen as sufficiently attuned to support agroecological transitions. Research programs are mostly agreed to have a focus on agroecological transitions. Farmers needs in an agroecological transition are seen as reflected in current research activities. Living labs and other forms of multi-actor involvement are agreed to be used in agroecological research and innovation. On farm experimentation is seen as often applied in research activities. The financial resources are, however, not perceived as sufficiently allocated for research into agroecology-based practices.</p> <p>In Norway, there is not so much of a need of a transition to Agroecology anymore, since the transition towards Agroecology is already ongoing. Still, there is not much talking about agroecology, but the practices are there: or even ahead of EU without using the concept. Therefore, the infrastructures in Norway are ready for Agroecology and already doing it to some extent. . However, the principles of agricultural research are different now. A lot of farm studies are being done in close dialog between farmers, farm advisers and researchers. However, discussions on the aim of agriculture is needed and there are many different approaches of Agroecology like organic farming, regenerative agriculture, community based agriculture and more. An improvement of the current research facilities might be achieved by the right incentives for research.</p> <p>In Norway, there is a need for a holistic perspective on whole-farm-level in research programmes, including households, farmers, and social aspects of agroecology. Moreover, there is a need for more awareness of the income of the farmers. It must be possible for them to make a living also on the agroecology practices.</p> <p>Norway is a small country with close cooperation's but more cooperation with NMBU would be desired and especially more interaction with the students. The small research stations all over Norway give diversity. The video platforms and its use in collaborations and knowledge transfer is very valuable and is improving the collaborations and international networks. The current research infrastructures in Norway could be improved by more programmes towards organic agriculture. In the EU there are more programmes but less in Norway. More research goals that lead the research in the direction of Agroecology are desired. However, a broader and holistic research should come.</p>
Poland	<p>Scientific research in Poland does not focus on agroecology. Research is primarily directed towards increasing production and profitability, and agroecology is not perceived as offering that (Pawik). Agroecological research also tends to be more applied, rather than innovation-producing (i.e. generating marketable outcomes). As a result, it struggles to form private-public partnerships, and agroecological projects are less competitive for funding (Pawlik). The research that does focus on agroecology specifically, is marginal. Research on</p>

	<p>agroecology also tends to focus on ‘soft’ projects, i.e. those which focus on perceptions and practices, rather than ‘hard’ projects which would produce evidence to support new practices or develop new market models (Wojtowicz). This is because ‘soft’ projects are easier to deliver, and so research institutes are incentivised to focus on such projects. There is some agroecological or agroecology-relevant research in Poland. However, knowledge exchange and knowledge transfer models are weak, depending predominantly on ‘end of pipe’ knowledge communication from experts to users, if that (some projects focus on publishing only,). There is a problem with knowledge transfer between science and farmers, between farmers and science and lack of mutual trust. Farmers consider research and its results are not appropriate to the actual needs of agriculture.</p> <p>There is very little participation of farmers or stakeholders in research, unless these are very specific rural development focused projects ran by the Ministry of Agriculture. Members of advisory boards tend to be sourced from research institutes, companies, and representatives of ministries, not farming groups. The project Bio-Strateg is a rare example of a project including on-farm experimentation (Pawlik). Cooperation between agricultural extension services, farmers and academia is a big and urgent need. Involvement of stakeholder should become expected and demanded of research projects and institutes.</p> <p>There are well developed research infrastructures in Poland, but these are under-utilised. These partly hark back from pre-1989 investment, and partly from recent EU funding through the Operational Programme ‘Innovative Economy’ and other structural funds. These research infrastructures are not fully used, especially regarding applied research, industrial research and experimental development works. There is a lack of demonstration farms on agroecology.</p> <p>Interviewees agreed that research programmes should to be aimed at long-term climate and environment protection -related goals. At the moment they are focused rather on short term scientific goals (peer-reviewed articles) and, in the case of applied sciences, on short term financial profits</p>
Serbia	<p>In Serbia, research infrastructures /facilities are attuned to support agroecological transition and the main identified challenge is a lack of the national funds. The research institutions actively participate in international projects under the Horizon 2020, but these activities are not further supported by systematic allocation of earmarked national funding for research and innovation in support of the AE. The national funds from the Ministry of Agriculture support mainly the research aspects dedicated to the soil quality.</p> <p>Farmers’ needs required for agroecological transition are not reflected in the current research activities and they are not mapped either. Living-labs and other forms of multi-actor involvement are mainly developing in the urban contexts. The Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops has 600 hectares of land and it provides ready to use agro-technologies to the farmers. There are no experiments on the farms, even if this would</p>

	<p>be very useful, as these experimental activities would require the state funding to support the farmers involvement.</p> <p>The present research infrastructures in the context of AE transition can be used for the technology development and transfer of the tailor-made know-how for specific agroecological conditions. The participation in initiatives on the European level is relevant as it provides an opportunity for Serbian researchers to work also on the national level (e.g. H2020 EcoBreed project, IPA projects (Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance)). Further, it would be relevant to support Living Labs and farms ensuring active participation of users following a practice in the Canadian LLs model.</p> <p>The higher education system provides a good knowledge and educates young agronomists about relevance of the AE. The teaching is performed mainly under the environmental protection study area at the Universities in Novi Sad and Belgrade, and also at the Faculty of Agronomy in Čačak. Among the new graduates main areas of expertise are covering environmental protection and relevant engineering areas, while to a lesser extent social sciences covering economical and sociological aspects. The main challenge after completing education, is the actual transfer of academic knowledge into the practice and ensuring that it is accepted by the farmers and the producers. The AE acceptance is also subjected to a wider set of the social factors as general social attitudes towards agroecology, dietary habits, life styles, etc.</p>
Slovakia	<p>In Slovakia, several research institutes have been working on practices that have been in line with the agroecological principles for a long time by now. The researchers started to coordinate on-farm experimentation that requires the active participation of farmers and other stakeholders. However, at this still initial stage the focus has been on the efforts made to engage farmers in these processes of implementation. There are also some living labs present. However, more systematic support is needed for the transfer of knowledge from research to practice, and the development of cooperation between these two sectors. The field experiments have the potential to demonstrate which processes are needed for the implementation of a selected range of agroecological practices. In the meanwhile, long-term on-farm experiments could showcase the more long-term benefits of the selected agroecological practices. They should receive more financial support. These could both provide space for organizing workshops and training for farmers. The research sector could communicate their results and actively support their implementation. These could also serve as venues for information and practical experience exchange. Currently the on-farm networks are more developed than the living labs.</p> <p>In Slovakia, there is a well-developed scientific network that serves as a background to the agroecological transition. The BIOEAST initiative develops strategic cooperation among a set of stakeholders at a macro-regional level (see the selected agroecology initiatives in Section 9).</p>

	<p>Initiatives, like the Smart-AKIS - a database of smart farming technologies, could also promote agroecology-based practices. This database allows insight into the structure of the current research programs and supports the implementation of their results through advisory and practical training services. More support is needed for extending the field research infrastructures, the demonstration sites and the living labs; also for establishing on-farm research networks that focus on agroecological practices and foster the direct participation of farmers in the research tasks. It is inevitable to focus on building personal competence in general. Researchers should be ready to work within multidisciplinary projects, as the complex nature of the agroecological transition requires a complex insight. The research sector is extremely underfunded, there is a shortage of staff, especially technical. From the point of view of material and equipment, the state funded research sector cannot compete with the corporate sector due to the lack of financial resources and the lengthy process of material procurement.</p>
Switzerland	<p>In Switzerland, there are different opinions on the support of agroecology in research and innovation. In general, the research infrastructures and innovation systems are not considered sufficiently attuned to support agroecological transitions. Switzerland has an entire research institute with its own infrastructures dedicated to organic farming (FiBL), as well as a federal centre of excellence for agricultural research with specific decentralised research centres (Agroscope). Both include the end-users in their research and research centres to bring and apply the results to the practices. Agridea, as Swiss agricultural competence centre for the preparation, exchange and dissemination of practice and research knowledge and know-how in agriculture, help in this task, too. For a transition towards agroecology-based practices, the current research infrastructures should strengthen existing activities i.e. through financial and human resources. Principles of agroecology should be integrated in research and the diversity of the approaches should be explored. Applied research is often practiced in Switzerland and it should focus on integration of new and innovative agroecological measures. However, knowledge transfer from applied research to advisory and field practice can be improved a lot. Also nation-wide implementation of successful approaches can be improved (e.g. results of pilot projects,...). Moreover, approaches should be explored to scale up respectively adapt efficient measures on the regional to national scale. The motivation for agroecological principles among decision-makers should be strengthened. Moreover, current research infrastructures may be used to foster a transition towards agroecology-based practices by implementing LLs, strengthening on-farm experimentation and using trans-disciplinary research. However, it is important, that really all the agroecological principles are implemented rather than isolated principles. Research programmes should check the coherence with the principles. It is crucial, that research infrastructures reflect the systemic character of agroecological research rather than focusing on particular pieces. This requires good infrastructures, synergies, and handling trade-offs between different principles of agroecology. Moreover, social dimensions should be more</p>

	<p>integrated in research, by for example a smart combination of infrastructures and the non-technical elements which are important for an agroecological transition. Thus, sharing of knowledge, exchange of technical and traditional knowledge (including values) and consequently translating them into action knowledge. The combination of knowledge types allows then for a broader understanding of agroecology on the system. All stakeholders must be included in this and an emphasis should be put on landscape approaches rather than on single-farm solutions, to build on synergies of farms in an area. The transition to agroecological practices can only succeed if research can convincingly demonstrate the benefits of such practices to practitioners. Switzerland therefore attaches great importance to good cooperation between and co-creation among research, extension and practice. There are very good research infrastructure in Switzerland, but they are targeted towards classical agricultural research and this must be updated and adapted to include agroecological elements, e.g. monitoring systems, a good combination of technology and agroecology principles, knowledge exchange. Finding and capitalising on the synergies in existing research infrastructures across organisations is necessary. The public needs to be brought into this as well, involvement but also understanding of what this type of research brings and how it could potentially be expanded with a citizen science approach. Many stakeholder groups (e.g. general public, farmers) do not see themselves and their needs reflected in the current research infrastructures nor do they know about these. Thus, synergies should be found in existing infrastructures and information should be consolidated across institutions and more stakeholder groups should get involved. Moreover, the current funding strategy is focussing on short term projects, making it difficult to develop research infrastructure strategies which reflect long-term needs, as well as carry out agroecological research more generally. This hinders synergies, and linkages among institutions and stakeholder groups.</p>
Turkey	<p>In order to ensure the common use of agroecology-based research, Research Infrastructures (RIs) of the public and private sector are prioritizing their research items to develop solutions for the common problems of all stakeholders groups. With the participation of the relevant stakeholders, joint research activities can be carried out within the scope of these determined priorities. Besides, in the implementation of the research results at the farm level, agricultural support payments and incentives should be increased and practical training and promotion activities carried out. Furthermore, there is a wide range of farmers with different needs that need to be tackled with the help of research. At least one year in advance, projects that deal with these priorities have to be planned, budgets calculated and further coordinated based on the mission and vision of the overall aim. The biggest hurdles are diverse. First, the co-creation and communication between the different actors is often difficult and needs to be improved. Further, the arrangement and coordination of data is very important, but difficult. There are big amounts of data on agroecology available, but it is not widely open to the various actors being involved yet. In Turkey one of the main aims is the reduction of use of pesticides and fertilizers, but so far RIs are not</p>

	<p>focusing enough on these issues. Science needs to give better tools and guidelines to the farmers as they need to have the guarantee to not be financially disadvantaged when switching to agroecological practices. On the other hand, there are not enough well equipped RIs (e.g. laboratories) that focus on agroecology. Altogether, the agroecology approach needs to be better applicable through the improvement of the current situation regarding RIs. Living Labs (LLs) are available, but not very common as they are a very new approach within the country.</p>
<p>United Kingdom</p>	<p>Agroecology is not generally recognised and pursued as a research trajectory, and does not have research infrastructures dedicated to it. While there is research into agroecological practices, this is not done under an agroecology umbrella. There is research taking place at e.g. ADAS or Rothamsted, but this is incremental rather than systemic. Importantly, there is an overall continued focus on supporting production-intensive systems, and only mitigating their negative environmental impacts. This also means a continued focus on conventional trials and statistical analysis methodologies, which are not compatible with agroecology. There is no actual research programme on agroecology. Agroecology as a term is too ideologically laden to be taken up by mainstream research councils. This is especially due to the anti-GM sentiment associated with agroecology. There is a strong push into technology-oriented research, which could be linked with agroecology (due to its focus on increasing efficiency). Agroecology projects are struggling to involve mainstream farmers. At the same time, agroecology community of practice is rarely present in e.g. sustainable farming research projects. That is because such research projects tend to be large and competitive and rely on powerful academic institutions, which are, however, stuck in a production-oriented mind-set. The lack of private funding for agroecology also means research projects struggle to create public-private partnerships, which are often a prerequisite in funding calls. Needs: One gap are experimental farms, which were lost following the privatisation of the knowledge exchange sector. Having more instrumented farms would be helpful. Some universities have experimental farms, but these are not involved in ongoing agroecology research. Longer-term funding, and long-term research programmes. Also long-term programmes which award smaller pots of money, to address the dominance of the big consortia approach which excludes smaller stakeholders. It would help to have more comparative research across different sites. There are a few specific programs which are based on farmer-led research, most notably Innovative Farmers – their research is not necessarily agroecology focused, however.</p>

Annex D: Competencies for an agroecology transition

Table 12: Partners synthesis of the interviews with respect to the entry: "*Competencies for an agroecology transition*".

Belgium	<p>There is in both regions a lack of systems thinking among researchers, in the advisory services and in the education system. The training of agroecology competences are focused on practices in primary production and not on aspects of the wider food system, for example looking for sales markets, the link with consumers' side. The colleges and advisory systems are generally not focused on agroecology. There is hardly no formation on agroecology. There should be spent more resources on accompanying farmers in their transition to agroecology. There is a strong division between organic farming and conventional farming in Flanders. The network to support organic farmers is well developed. However, conventional farmers that want to implement agroecological practices without converting to organic production, might have much more difficulties in finding appropriated advise and support.</p>
Cyprus	<p>Because agroecology is not very well spread in Cyprus, the competencies to foster an agroecology transition are only somewhat developed. There are farmer networks for sharing knowledge and practices, but they are not focused on agroecology but on sharing knowledge and best practices. There are resources focused on organic farming for young farmers, but they usually do not include agroecology.</p>
Czech Rep.	<p>University programs should improve their focus and aim to address agroecology and its practices more holistically. The beauty of agroecological practices is that in some cases they do not require high level technological infrastructure. However, the main shortcoming relevant to the Czech technological infrastructure is not the lack of its availability, but the limited extent of its application to promote practices that are in line with the principles of agroecology. There are well functioning knowledge networks among farmers, but these are developed by and benefiting only a limited group of active, progressive farmers. Their networks are not specifically focused on agroecology and also fail to engage the rest of the farmers who would need assistance and could greatly benefit from the agroecological transition. The farmers consult the farm advisory services mostly regarding subsidies and for assistance regarding the efficiency of their production practices. However, the currently available farm advisory services fail to provide sufficient assistance even for those engaged in mainstream agriculture. Only a few advisors have a sufficient understanding of what agroecology is. Regardless, they are unable to provide assistance in several fields that are critical for achieving any level of transition towards agroecology. There are farm advisory services for organic agriculture that address many practices linked to agroecology, but there are no advisory services specifically focused on agroecology. The lack of the level of social capital - the unwillingness to cooperate - characteristic to</p>

	<p>post-communist countries, should be recognized as a significant barrier to agroecological transition. “Even the word ‘cooperation’ acts as a buzzkill.” Actions that require sharing resources are deterrents. Such a transition would require cooperation between farmers and other stakeholder groups, to organize the collective actions needed. Also, there is nobody to help farmers and facilitate these actions. Even the advisors lack the necessary social skills to manage living labs, or coordinate collective actions. They don’t have the necessary training or an insight into what such transition would entail besides the promotion and implementation of specific agroecological practices. There are complaints that there are way too many seminars, as there are sufficient resources for the training or retraining of farmers. However, the structure of these trainings alienates farmers. The content they offer is not in line with their true interests, the language they use is way too complicated, the lectures get way too theoretical, and most importantly farmers have no time to attend. Farmers like and benefit from more practical examples, demo farms, things they can actually see on the fields. Seminars are still the preferred form of knowledge dissemination, as it is easier to collect them for lectures, compared to providing personalized assistance to the farmers suited to their specific needs. The agroecological movement should be more focused on the farmers and it should aim to find ways to provide better information to the wide public about agroecology and its principles, also how they could get engaged in its practices. In general, the perception of the social and the socioeconomic pillar of the agroecological transition should be strengthened. It needs to be made clear that there is more to agroecology than the promotion of organic farming practices. However, there is no institution that would cover agroecology in Czech Republic. There might be some minor movements but there are no institutionalized answers, no institutions in charge to promote it. “No one really owns it.”</p>
Denmark	<p>The opinion of the interviewees is that within Denmark, we have competent farmers, good advisory services and good infrastructure, so the basis is there, but need to be more support from market and/or push from support schemes/regulation (CAP) to facilitate ea green transition. It has to expand beyond the agricultural sector, farmer network etc and into the wider sector of consumers and NGO’s. IT is important that farmers understand the green transition as they are the ones that are producing and documenting. Living labs are a good way to promote and provide evidence, but needs to be more comprehensive in the sense than just on-farm experiments or demonstration plots, but with broader stakeholder engagement</p>
Estonia	<p>In Estonia, there are differing opinions on the development of the competencies regarding agroecology, especially concerning the “education of farmers in agricultural colleges” and the “resources availability for training and retraining of farmers”. The “technological infrastructure in the farming sector”, “the knowledge networks among farmers”, “the farm advisory service” and “farmer networks for</p>

	<p>knowledge sharing” are perceived as developed, neutral or somewhat developed. An additional, well developed competency for an agroecology transition would be knowledge transfer programs. Their main aim is to share new knowledge and bring new knowledge into Estonia. These knowledge transfer programs are based on web portals with knowledge reservoirs, including different formats of trainings etc. But also farm demonstrations were mentioned as a competency which is however, less developed.</p> <p>It was mentioned, that the level of education in university and colleges in Estonia can be improved as well as the farm advisory system. Younger people are not happy about the education system. Colleges perform better in supporting the students. The understanding of the social aspect of agroecology is not well developed, yet. There is also a lack of understanding about agroecology in the population.</p>
Finland	<p>In Finland, the competencies are generally well developed for an agroecology transition: especially the technological infrastructure in the farming sector, the knowledge networks among farmers, the farm advisory service and the farmer networks for knowledge sharing. However, the competencies that would enable a transition towards Agroecology are currently used for the current system, rather than for a transition. The farmers can get support and training in Agroecology based practices, but the amount of practices is limited and they focus on practice oriented approaches.</p> <p>It was mentioned, that in schools the teaching in agricultural can be quite theoretic and recently, the students have not been brought up on farms anymore, so they do not have a practical knowledge and background. More practical knowledge is needed for solving problems. The network among farmers is quite good in these terms. Farmers have the best knowledge to share among themselves. If the advisers are too theoretical they lack the understanding of critical issues. After all, different kinds of knowledge (theoretical and practical) is required and the dialogue between the different stakeholders is needed to solve the problems.</p>
France	<p>The ministry is aiming to push education of farmers towards agroecology, but from the science perspective needs to clearly be improved. The scientists play again a key role here, as they are responsible in developing solutions that can convince the farmers (psychologically and technologically). In France farmer networks and associations are increasing in number (~20.000 currently about agroecology) and are of major importance to transfer knowledge and experiences. Nevertheless, the networks should be used more efficiently and the connection between farmers and scientists improved. A lot of time, money, energy and dedication is needed (but necessary) to allocate all resources and coordinate the network on different levels from national to local. Another important aspect is how the information of competencies can be spread beside schools and networks. One possibility is that farmers learn from each other by on-field observations. If one farmer sees his neighbour farmer positively and</p>

	<p>successfully implementing agroecological practices on his/her farm, the motivation and curiosity for new practices might be thriven and spread. Moreover, especially the newer generation of farmers might be willing to use tutorials on online video platforms such as YouTube to learn and increase their knowledge about agroecological topics such as methods, tools, technologies, experiences or ecology and climate related issues.</p>
Germany	<p>The interviewees emphasised that the education of farmers in agricultural colleges focuses on traditional themes of conventional farming. The curricula of vocational education schools need to be improved with respect to agroecology as well as related themes such as sustainability of farming, biodiversity and carbon farming. Interviewees pointed out that integrated pest management is well covered in teaching courses, but this was seen as an exception. Other agroecological practices and principles are not well covered. It was however acknowledged that smaller education initiatives on agroecology exist. Interviewees agreed that the technological infrastructure in the farming sector is developed, but the level of application in the context of agroecology was seen as low.</p> <p>Knowledge networks among farmers on agroecological issues were acknowledged at smaller scale. But interviewees pointed out that networks are missing which bring agroecological and organic farmers together with conventional farmers for cross-fertilisation. The development of farm advisory services is very pluralistic. In some regions, e.g. in Baden Württemberg and Lower Saxony, specific advisory services exist for biodiversity and increasing demand from farmers for such advice was noted. This is partly EU-funded, thus reducing cost for farmers. But, overall, more tailored modules on sustainable farming practices are needed. Also, it was noted that knowledge requests from farmers to advisors are changing from specific management issues to advice on system issues (e.g. nutrient cycling or managing the farm within the planetary boundaries while at the same time being profitable). These changes in the knowledge and innovation system are also considered in the new CAP programming (cross-cutting objective on knowledge sharing and innovation), but the implementation will depend on how much funds the Federal States will allocate to it.</p>
Hungary	<p>Higher education does not contain targeted curricula, courses, or space for knowledge transfer on agroecology. Therefore, the new generation of farmers who are coming out of universities has very limited understanding on sustainable practices. Most of the farmers rely on books, guidelines written in English or German, which means that this knowledge is available only for those who are familiar with these languages. Also, there is no advisory service on agroecology which would be just as important as university education.</p> <p>Looking at the market, an average consumer never really met the term agroecology, there are no specific products or brands that would convey its importance, which results in a very low demand – even short supply chains do not really use the word agroecology, just organic or</p>

sustainable product. Also, in Hungary farmers and different value chain stakeholders are not really keen to cooperate with each due to lack of trust and lack of entrepreneurial spirit, therefore the actors aren't really organized and not strong enough to enter into or create their own market which in itself will not boost the demand. So, a shift in mindsets needs to happen first along with proper education.

An evidence-base needs to be created for agroecology, including the assessment of cost/benefits. Research infrastructure should have an important role in order to boost the transition and to help the decision-making processes on the policy and on the farm level.

Lastly, diminishing the voice of social movements (including the voice of farmers) is an apparent characteristic in Hungary. It means that social movements/NGOs are channelled to the mainstream policy, as “foreign agents”, working for foreign agricultural interests. This hinders their non-profit work that is restricted to awareness-raising, educational efforts.

Most importantly the advisory system, knowledge networks and the education system available for farmers should be improved, with a focus on the improvement of cooperation between these institutions.

There is a complex system of informal networks that provides space for information and practical experience exchange. It is difficult to assess the extent of these networks. On-farm networks provide more formal venues for cooperation. Many argue that they are ready to start to address issues that are not strictly related to the agronomic practices of agroecology or scientific research related to these practices. These issues could include the promotion of cooperation along the value chain and social justice issues, such as the inclusion of and fair treatment of marginalized groups.

There is a growing interest in digitalization, which could also contribute to the success of agroecology. Digital precision solutions could contribute to monitoring of biodiversity, nutrient management, and pest control. Traditional ecological knowledge should be better appreciated and policies should re-evaluate their heavy reliance on technocratic solutions.

Relevant competencies to support the agroecology transition could be developed anywhere, it shouldn't rely exclusively only on the work of NGOs, research institutions and dedicated farmers. As it is a complex societal issue, a wide range of competences are relevant. There is a bottom-up approach in competence building. Permaculture is a great example of that, as it took only a few years for an actively involved group to develop around this agroecological principle. The members self-educate themselves and support each other through knowledge-exchange. Permaculture is also present in kindergartens. It shows that

	even these informal organisations have a potential to build competencies and engage a diverse range of stakeholders.
Iceland	Similarly to the previous point, the advisor rated the state of competencies for the agroecological transition in Iceland worse than the researcher. From the advisor's point of view, farmers don't have enough access to information. In particular, farmers have low income (especially sheep farmers), so they don't buy the advisory service (often work outside the farm to secure a living). Both agreed that there is a lack of people working in this area, and that farmer networks are developed/well developed, even though they don't deal directly with agroecology-related issues.
Ireland	<p>The interviewees agreed that the competences for an agroecological transition are somewhat developed to neutral, because they are not usually promoted under the agroecological umbrella. There are some knowledge transfer and capacity building programmes about sustainable agriculture, but they are not focused on agroecology.</p> <p>However, there are opportunity under the CAP knowledge transfer and Continuing Professional Development for Advisors measures to examine agroecology. The future partnership should seek to create resources to facilitate knowledge transfer and training of farm advisors. There is the potential to engage with Higher Education Institutions such as UCD to examine this matter.</p>
Latvia	<p>Vocational education schools play an important role in providing knowledge to young specialists in the agricultural sector. Interviewees reported that in recent years the number of vocational education institutions implementing agricultural programmes has fallen significantly due to low demand. In schools continuing to implement agriculture related programmes, improvements have been made to technical provision and improved education programmes to meet the labour market requirements and emerging trends in the sector. Interest in lifelong learning offers has increased significantly, including interest in different areas related to development of agriculture trends.</p> <p>Critical views were expressed in relation to specific competences for an agroecological transition and interviewees identified several knowledge and competence related barriers and challenges. Financial resources for training farmers are available through technical programmes, but these programmes are often not specifically targeted to agroecology.</p> <p>A lack of advisory services for providing training to farmers specifically on agroecology was identified. While some knowledge on agroecology in the advisory services was acknowledged with training on some specific practices provided (example of composting was raised), interviewees agreed on the need to further enhance and update the knowledge of advisors on agroecology. Specific capacity building of advisors on agroecology is needed. Interviewees also suggested that uncertainty</p>

	<p>about the terminology and different understandings of agroecology also contribute to the lack of specific advisory services for, and knowledge sharing on, agroecology.</p> <p>Knowledge networks initiated by advisory services, ministry and farmer organisations do not specifically address competences on agroecology. While smaller farmer networks sharing knowledge on specific agroecological practices (e.g. permaculture and organic farming), the need for more transdisciplinary networks that go beyond traditional conventional agricultural focus was indicated</p>
Lichtenstein	<p>In Lichtenstein, no facilities for farmers education are available, but Lichtenstein is associated with the facilities in Switzerland. The education of farmers in agricultural colleges and the technological infrastructure in the farming sector are seen as developed. Knowledge networks among farmers and farm advisory service are neutrally developed. Resources available for training/retraining of farmers and farmer networks for knowledge sharing are considered less developed. Farmers are trained in Switzerland. There are no training facilities for farmers in Lichtenstein itself. In terms of further training opportunities for farmers, Lichtenstein is also linked to the training opportunities in Switzerland. There is an additional exchange with the training centre in Vorarlberg, Austria, but the focus is in Switzerland.</p>
Lithuania	<p>Competences for an agroecological transition are partly developed. But the interviewees identified several knowledge and competence related barriers and challenges. Financial resources for training farmers are available through technical programmes, but these programmes are not specifically targeted to agroecology.</p> <p>Also a lack of advisory services for providing training to farmers specifically on agroecology was identified. Existing advisory services (e.g. provided through the advisory centre and the agricultural chambers) focus on economic issues. While some knowledge on agroecology in the advisory services was acknowledged, interviewees agreed on the need to further enhance and update the knowledge of advisors on agroecology. Specific agroecology training of advisors is needed. Interviewees reported an increasing number of requests by farmers for specific advice on agroecological practices suggesting that demand for a specific advisory service on agroecology would exist.</p> <p>Smaller farmer networks sharing knowledge on specific agroecological practices (e.g. no till farmer network) exist. Larger knowledge networks initiated by advisory services, ministry and farmer organisations do not specifically address competences on agroecology.</p>
Luxembourg	<p>There is quite some disagreement among the national contact points about the competencies for an agroecological transition. On the one hand, the competencies are perceived as being there and rather well developed, and on the other hand as not developed at all, especially the education of farmers in agricultural colleges and the technological</p>

	<p>infrastructure in the farming sector. The knowledge networks among farmers, the farm advisory service and the resources that are available for training/retraining of farmers are perceived as neutrally developed for an agroecological transition. The farmer networks for knowledge sharing, are however, perceived as not all developed. Although, the three or four cooperatives present in Luxembourg are quiet well connected.</p>
Netherlands	<p>In the Netherlands, the competencies for an agroecological transition are perceived as well to very well developed. In the Netherlands, the education system for agroecology is very well developed with a lot of universities and a lot of institutes for applied sciences. So, the knowledge is there, especially technical knowledge and innovations.</p> <p>Also, the farmers are well educated in the Netherlands, in general. However, there is a broad spectrum of how well the farmers are educated. Farmers need to have a lot of knowledge in many different aspects. It is often not possible to cover all aspects. But it also depends on the individual farmer and his or her interests. The education depends on the type of farmer and the age. Moreover, there are a lot of advisors in the Netherlands. Still, the knowledge and the innovations are fragmented. The issue is, how all the stakeholders can be connected. However, a transition to another system is always difficult. In order to enable an agroecological transition, also the food system needs to be included and brought towards sustainability. The issue is to identify the next steps.</p> <p>In the Netherlands, also the competencies of the consumers are developed. For the consumers, it is important to know where the food comes from and how it is produced – “food literacy” among consumers. Policy makers are an important factor, as their knowledge and understanding on agricultural competencies is having an impact on the development of these agricultural competencies in a country.</p>
Norway	<p>In Norway, there are differing opinions on the development of the competencies regarding agroecology: The opinions on the development of the “education of farmers in agricultural colleges”, the “technological infrastructure in the farming sector”, the “knowledge networks among farmers”, the “farm advisory service”, “resources available for training/retraining of farmers” and “farmer networks for knowledge sharing” range in general from very well developed to somewhat developed. Social media are also used for agroecological aspects. Maybe there is even a facebook-group of Agroecology. In Norway, most farmers do not have an official education as farmer. Moreover, the education is not taking place in the college, but it is done in the family in many cases. But more and more farmers are taking the college now, where the agroecology aspect is not so strong, especially the social sciences are not included in this education. Thus, knowledge transfer via social media is even more important. Some colleges have more focus on organic and some more on conventional agriculture.</p>

	<p>In Norway, one university has a master’s program for Agroecology. The core of competencies is very good, and organic farmers are well connected and well informed, well equipped in knowledge. However, there is not so much focus on Agroecology in knowledge networks among farmers.</p> <p>There is a need to develop the competence on the concept itself. There is a high degree of agroecology practices applied in Norway today. The question is, what would the ideal agroecology situation be for Norway and how is that compared to the situation today?</p> <p>A knowledge gap regarding the competencies exists: how to make money on Agroecology? There are discussions on labels but the competencies are lacking.</p>
Poland	<p>Overall, both interviewees perceived competencies for an agroecology transition in Poland as low. There is a lack of educational programs for either farmers or advisors. Farmer training is not easily available, because agricultural advisors do not have the knowledge themselves and need training in first instance (Wojtowicz). Pawlik argued that agricultural services are sufficient, but are unable to drive change due to the lack of market incentives towards agroecological methods. There are good competencies on the research side, but these are not connected with societal or industry (farming) need. Wojtowicz has undertaken surveys with participants of her agroecology training courses. She reports that farmers, agricultural advisors, local government officials and employees of government institutions all indicated the need for greater availability of agroecology training for farmers in each region delivered by the 16 Agricultural Advisory Centers.</p> <p>There is a very large appetite for peer-to-peer learning. There are very few agroecology farming networks (e.g. Żywa Ziemia, Lokalny Rolnik).</p>
Serbia	<p>Extension services are very well developed on the regional level. Their knowledge is continuously upgraded through courses and additional education, which is an integral practice of the extension services system in Serbia. This model ensures that the advisors provide an excellent support to the farmers. It is nonetheless still difficult to ensure the consumer support for AE that would be a real driving force in the transformation process. Currently, in this context there is mainly the organic production that is primarily exported (e.g. soy, medical herbs, etc.).</p>
Slovakia	<p>Both the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of Economy should strengthen their own competences and knowledge in the field of agroecology. They should be ready to go beyond focusing on their historically inherited topics. They need a broader vision that would fit the complexity of agroecology instead of the current sector-specific approach.</p> <p>The universities show strong competence in supporting the agroecology transition, especially the Slovak University of Agriculture. They do have a holistic approach to agroecology, and have been assigning senior student research projects in cooperation with local producer and</p>

	<p>consumer associations, and social movements with competence to support the agroecology transition. They promote research focused on agroecology, and actively contribute to the dissemination of relevant information (e.g.: building a public knowledge base on circular use of biomass) and general awareness raising also in the field of agroecology. Education of farmers in agricultural colleges and the farm advisory services should be aware of the lack of both their own and the other stakeholders' lack of in-depth understanding of agroecology. Until then, they won't be able to properly address the complexity of the issues behind a successful transition. Also, awareness raising among the general public should be improved in both general and specific relevant environmental and agricultural topics.</p>
Switzerland	<p>The competencies in Switzerland are seen as not specifically developed for an agroecological transition. The “education of farmers in agricultural colleges”, the “technological infrastructure in the farming sector”, the “knowledge networks among farmers”, the “farm advisory service”, the “resources available for training/retraining of farmers” and the “farmer networks for knowledge sharing” are all seen as somewhat developed to neutral. Additional competencies concerning different sectors of the value chain are seen as not developed.</p> <p>The knowledge transfer from science to practice should be strengthened, mainly also to understand the potential of different elements, the limitations, trade-offs etc., e.g. intercropping. For many elements it is difficult to translate this into practice – there is a need for concrete examples on best practices on the ground. That requires advisory, farmer-to-farmer learning, etc., because it is so knowledge intensive. Currently, the focus is on communication elements. However, the combination of voluntary approaches, economic instruments, regulations and incentives is central for the transition. A comprehensive consideration of biodiversity is still missing. An agroecological transition requires competences and changes along the whole value chain and in the entire agricultural food system, e.g. also consumers, processors, retailers, etc.</p>
Turkey	<p>The pure establishment of suitable RIs and LLs for agroecological transition is not enough. At the same time, farmers and producers who are the end users of research results, need to be willing to embrace and accept those developments. That is not fully the case in Turkey yet. The education of farmers is not sufficient yet and needs to be improved by building up more facilities, but also make the farmers aware of the issue. The same counts for the networks of farmers that are only developed on a low level which complicates the sharing of knowledge.</p>
United Kingdom	<p>The interviewees were either not aware of how far agroecology was taught at farming colleges, or judged it to be very low. Where agroecology is taught, this is principally as a scientific approach rather than also as a social movement. There is engagement with technology, however that is mainly linked to production objectives. The knowledge networks amongst farmers are growing. There are some new initiatives, such as Nature Friendly Farming Network, which are influential.</p>

	<p>Established knowledge networks amongst already agroecological farmers are strong, however there are strong boundaries between them and more conventional approaches which prevent dialogue.</p> <p>Regenerative agriculture is emerging as an interesting mixed arena for knowledge exchange, and it is more inclusive of different farming styles. In the advisory services, there is a strong split between specialist advisors who can tackle agroecological issues, and traditional agronomists. The training in agroecological skills is becoming more important now due to a shift in policy towards Environmental Land Management (see 7). In Wales, this will require a huge shift for farmers. Interviewees recognised that agroecology is very knowledge intensive, demanding, and risky, and that farmers and other farming workforce (not just the lead farmer) must have good support to engage with it.</p>
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Annex E: Involvement of stakeholders

Table 13: Partners synthesis of the interviews with respect to the entry: *"Involvement of stakeholders in the agroecology transition"*.

Belgium	<p>There is no agreement about which are the most involved stakeholders. Some say the farmers and farmers' unions are most involved, others say the researchers and NGO's and farmers' unions. They all agree that the food supply chain and the consumers are almost not involved. It is not easy to involve those groups. For the food supply chain, you can involve local actors, but many actors are multinationals and very hard to reach. One interviewee emphasized the role of funding schemes to support the dynamic to involve all actors in value chain (eg. PillarII support for innovative value chains, funding from Walloon nature ministry to support food relocalisation: https://www.mangerdemain.be/2021/04/28/46-projets-pour-accelerer-la-transition-du-systeme-alimentaire-wallon/). The involvement of consumers by raising awareness on the benefits of agroecological practices just as the additional cost of production is necessary to get the transition forward.</p> <p>One interviewee remarks that farmers are not rewarded for their involvement in eg research or demonstration actions. They should be rewarded in monetary terms for spending their time and knowledge and taking risk. They are not perceived as an equal partner in research.</p>
Cyprus	<p>In Cyprus, the stakeholders are not organised driven by the agroecology umbrella. And there are no living labs to foster the agroecology transition. Consumers are not aware of the environmental aspects of food production. However, organic farming is helping to change consumers' awareness about the environmental problems of modern agriculture.</p> <p>The involvement of stakeholders in agroecological transition can be improved with a top-down approach if more policies promote the application of agroecology principles. But also with a bottom-up approach can help, for example, if consumers start demanding more sustainable agriculture and farmers start applying agroecology-based practices.</p>
Czech Rep.	<p>There is no institution or any stakeholder association that would focus specifically on agroecology. Farmers associations are there to defend farmers, but they fail to strategically advance their position, let alone improve their involvement in the agroecological transition. Some may share technical expertise required for the implementation of specific agroecological practices, but these are more linked to the promotion of organic agriculture. Currently few living lab experiments take this role, but just to a limited extent. Stakeholder interests are taken into account in policy making only to some extent, and mostly just those of the farmers and not of the rest of the stakeholder groups. One of the ministries has a standing committee to promote the interests of organic</p>

farming, which was identified to be the closest thing to influence policy making in regard to the potential support or promotion of the agroecological transition. Even though this committee secures a space to provide input into policy making, these inputs often fail to be taken into account. Its influence falls behind its expectations. The policymaker's involvement in the agroecological transition is infinitesimal, contrary to the rare but still notable engagement of local policy makers and the association of action groups - whose engagement and influence could deliver noticeable results at a regional level. It is difficult for small-scale farms to fit into large-scale research programs. However, there is a new trend, where research projects focus on small-scale farming and tend to use living-labs, as a tool to improve actor involvement. Those who participate in these are very active. However, they are still not a representative group, as the majority of farmers, mostly engaged in conventional large-scale farming practices, cannot be reached through such participation-based programs. Stakeholder involvement could be improved through living labs. There is a big demand for creating more spaces where farmers meet and exchange ideas. Bioregions were given as an example of a space that promotes cooperation besides biodiversity. Research programs should focus more on improving stakeholder involvement, and recognize the importance of actively engaging a wider range of stakeholder groups. When talking about the improvement of stakeholder involvement, one could most likely start by identifying attractive practices to work with and listing potential actors in charge of engaging different stakeholder groups in these projects. However, it must be acknowledged that the real problem is the lack of social capital. Those who would be in charge of initiatives aiming to engage different stakeholder groups in the processes of agroecological transition, should be aware of this serious shortcoming and find ways to work around it. Advisors and project facilitators need to be trained, as they need skills to promote cooperation within and among diverse stakeholder groups in a vacuum created by the low social capital (and low trust) that characterize the society they must operate within. It is already difficult to find people to set up and operate living labs, but the environment they need to work in constitutes the real challenge. Particular types of innovations, many of which are associated with agroecological farming practices, tend to create space for networks to develop around them. These could be seen as a lighter approach than living labs, allowing for a more gradual approach towards the development of stakeholder involvement. The systems approach that would entail the restructuring of farms and engaging them more deeply in diverse forms of cooperation requires a big leap of faith. Therefore, it might be easier to engage farmers through smaller steps in cooperation. The pressure to cooperate within living labs poses a challenge even in countries where cooperation is not perceived to be so dissenting. It is worth considering how stakeholders need to put graduality in the transition, as the competences that will be needed through the journey are being developed on the way. The lack of the understanding of what

	<p>is meant by agroecological transition comprises the extent of stakeholder involvement. Farmers understand their interest in actively participating in exchanging ideas about how to farm ‘better’, but they fail to recognize that it would be in their interest to learn about and engage in other practices, such as actively shaping value chains, involving local inhabitants, supporting the development of consumer groups, etc. Even the farmers who actively participate in such practices, would not call themselves active in the agroecological transition. Research on cooperation among Czech farmers found that “farmers cooperate not for their common benefit, but to face the same threat”. Besides farmers, mostly NGOs, local authorities and local interest groups, and local consumers groups are expected to have both the potential and the interest in being involved in the promotion of agroecological practices. There are many initiatives that actively promote the implementation of agroecological practices. However, they don’t promote them deliberately. Also, the engagement of the broad public is missing.</p>
Denmark	<p>The Involvement of stakeholders are given much importance throughout all the interviews by participants. Universities and SEGES especially was identified as playing a big role in getting everyone onboard towards a green transition. Universities plays an important role as they provide the evidence base. Right now, we have some farming organisations and farmers themselves, but the whole retail chain has to be included to make a difference. This will ensure there is support for products that are potentially more expensive. We also have to remember to include technologic developers as they are part of transition. One interviewee stated that currently, the main involved parties were: the organic industry, farmers, companies, advisors, and minorly other conservation agriculture groups and similar initiatives. They furthermore identified the following lacking stakeholders: a broader set of farmers, industry, input suppliers, nature conservation groups, recreational landscape users, financial institutes and retail.</p>
Estonia	<p>The perception of the involvement of stakeholders and on the development of stakeholder associations with respect to agroecology related matters in Estonia are dissimilar. There is a disagreement on whether “stakeholders are organised in associations that represent their interests”. Estonian contact points do not agree on whether “stakeholder associations possess a high level of technical expertise”, and on whether “stakeholders’ views are taken into consideration in policymaking”. Further, Estonian contact points do not agree on the following statements: “living labs and other open innovation arrangements are frequently used to foster transition within Estonia” and “stakeholders are actively participating in multi-stakeholder living labs”. However, stakeholders are seen as rather well integrated in research programmes. And stakeholder associations representing farmers are perceived to have some interest in pursuing an agroecology transition in Estonia.</p> <p>The involvement of stakeholders for agroecological transition in Estonia</p>

	<p>may be improved by public awareness on why agroecology is important as well as by political support. Newspapers and agricultural policies could be used to increase the awareness of agroecology. Moreover, incentives should be provided to motivate stakeholders to participate in research & living lab concept. Clear targets on what should be achieved are necessary would help as well as multi-actor approaches.</p> <p>In Estonia, there is a need for good examples of agroecology and strong networks. Moreover, innovation projects are required such as innovation clusters on agroecological transition</p> <p>A lot of stakeholders are involved in agroecological transition already: Scientists, farmer union, agricultural chamber, organic associations, food processor, but mainly the organic farmers. Also, some small communities are involved: e.g. permaculture communities and households. Many conventional farmers, big processors, retailers organizations and consumer organizations are not yet involved in the agroecological transition. The involvement of stakeholders for agroecological transitions can be improved by providing more information about agroecology that stakeholders really know what it means. However, stakeholder know already a lot about agroecology, but for the participants of the organizations it is sometimes not clear what needs to be changed for the transition.</p>
Finland	<p>Regarding the involvement of stakeholders in the agroecology transition, there are different opinions in Finland, but the national contact points agree that stakeholder associations possess a high level of technical expertise and that living labs and other open innovation arrangements are frequently used to foster a transition.</p> <p>The knowledge of stakeholders in Agroecology should be increased, as well as their motivation. Associations for organic farming are there, but no transition to Agroecology is in their focus, other things are more prioritised. Incentives are lacking. The farming associations are more working on and in the current system, rather than on a transition. Organic associations are more involved in a agroecological transition, but to a limited extent. No consumer organisation is involved, the NGOs are not interested, having a narrow perspective of the important aspects of agriculture.</p> <p>The involvement of stakeholders for agroecological transition could be improved by creating places where people can meet and exchange physically. It should be the aim to, in addition to scientist, include, farmers, industry, retailers, consumers, policy makers etc. But the number of agricultural researchers that are interested in Agroecology is rather small in Finland and if this number would be bigger, their impact would rise. Also agricultural schools are important because they train the actors of the future. It is sometimes difficult to get all these stakeholders together. Farmers are a very diverse group with different characteristic in relation to their farm. Moreover, farmers are quite busy and often do not have extra time to go to meetings. Thus, it is difficult to get the audience for living labs and there is competition for participants/audience. Good speakers are needed to attract this</p>

	<p>audience. People need to be able to discuss and to be creative. Different kinds of knowledge and views are appreciated. People should feel that they are treated in a fair way and an innovative atmosphere requires trust between people.</p> <p>It is important, that the whole food system and food chain works and that also the market functions. The agroecological changes in the system should be working within the system. So, there should be a market for the new elements in the system and the new products.</p>
France	<p>In France many different groups of stakeholders are involved in the transition process, from farmers to consumers and policy-makers. All of them are important, but each of them plays a different role. The amount of associations is increasing (especially farmers), but not all of them possess a high level of technological expertise, and if, then many of them are still working in conventional agriculture. Positively is seen that stakeholders are more and more represented and considered by the policy-makers as well as being actively involved in research programs. Here, they can participate in the selection of specific research projects to make sure that that the approach of science is farm-eligible and compatible with their needs. It is also seen as important that beside politics, the consumers push the stakeholders into the right direction. Furthermore, LLs (as mentioned above) play an increasing role in the transition. These must ensure to maintain their research ability and not just functioning as a pure network of communicating the results of science. The most pushing and maybe relevant (beside farmers) stakeholder group is represented by the consumers. They not only want an improvement of the quality of food and its production, but also less (direct in the own, but also indirectly in other countries through imports) impact on the agroecosystem, the biodiversity, climate and animal welfare. One possibility to bring farmers and consumers together, could be organised celebration and open farm days related to agroecology and biodiversity to involve the wider public into the process . Nevertheless, there are still several problems regarding the involvement of stakeholders. For instance, the co-creation and knowledge sharing between the various groups of stakeholders with different backgrounds, interests and experience is often a long and complicated process. Stakeholders need to be closely involved in the work of LLs and other Open Innovation Arrangements.</p>
Germany	<p>Interviewees agreed that stakeholder organisations have a relative good technical expertise. But the need for improvement was highlighted, in particular in relation to the integration of stakeholders in research programmes and their active participation in living labs and other forms of engagement. Interviewees expressed a need for more decision power for stakeholders in research programmes. Living labs could provide a framework for research that might enable such governance changes in designing and conducting research. While the use of living labs is increasing questions remain about the financing of long term research in living labs. There is a need for highlighting good practices in living lab development and application, which requires a set of indicators to</p>

	<p>measure the impact of the living labs. The involvement of stakeholders differs also between research programmes. While stakeholder involvement is seen as good in the innovation programme for agriculture, the need for improvements was highlighted for other programmes.</p> <p>The importance was highlighted of defining concrete problems that involved stakeholders agree with and see as urgent issues that can be addressed through their engagement. Stakeholders need to be able to identify a clear benefit of their involvement. This also applies to the benefits of a European network of living labs. Some actors might be curious about developments and experiences in other countries and would be happy to travel and attend knowledge exchange events abroad. Other actors might not want to travel and attend large workshops but might still be interested in videos and other material available online to find solutions that they benefit from on their own farm.</p> <p>Interviewees also raised the issue of stakeholder fatigue. Stakeholder analysis is needed to identify and clarify which stakeholders to involve in which activities and to identify the most suitable approach of how to involve them. Further, the extent of the involvement needs to be considered, as in many cases stakeholders will be engaged on a voluntary basis without remuneration. It was also noted that it is easier to involve stakeholders at a smaller scale, addressing specific problem that fosters engagement of actors from the whole value chain. The example was raised of trying to promote regional food in a particular city with targeted involvement of farmers from the vicinity of the city, retailers and other actors of the specific value chains. This example also reflects recent developments of food policy councils in urban areas in Germany.</p> <p>While the interviewees acknowledged an increasing number of examples of food policy councils and producer-consumer associations, particular reference was made to the need for improved linkages between producers and consumers and stronger involvement of consumers, retailers and other value chain actors in transitions to agroecology. It was also emphasised that is important to involve stakeholders who are impacted on by agricultural land management, e.g. fishermen who are impacted on by water pollution from agriculture.</p>
Hungary	<p>As a first step, all relevant stakeholders should be identified and assessed before developing a network for them. With a functioning national network, it would be much easier to communicate with the stakeholders and engage them. Another important aspect for involvement is the knowledge of the stakeholder needs and mainly their cost/benefit scenarios and how it relates to the market. It is always easier to involve actors when we know their clear motivation for the transition.</p>

	<p>Stakeholders don't really know each other, the channels of communication they could use are missing. Stakeholders should get organized, mostly with the assistance provided by informal, bottom-up organizations. These organisations need state support as they operate with limited resources. Also, policy makers should be required to consult with such organizations. It would be easier for policy makers to take into consideration stakeholder interests if the stakeholders would be better organized.</p> <p>Currently the following stakeholders are involved in the support of agroecology transition: mainly researchers and research institutions, organic or agroecological farmers/producers, some NGOs, civil society with its diverse range of movements, ministry of agriculture and SMEs. The participation of the following stakeholders would be important: medium or big retailers, wholesalers, conventional farmers, integrators, seed, input companies, banks, insurance companies, agricultural authorities, and municipalities.</p> <p>Farmers are the most difficult group to get on board, to get them to participate and cooperate with each other. Their involvement in projects, like those related to EIP, could be improved if the requirements for participation would be made easier. Farmers tend to stay away from the seminars organized for them, as the presentations are full of details they are not interested in and the wording they use is often way too complex. Also, it is challenging for them to find time to participate, or to travel. The covid situation showed that the online format for such seminars increased their participation.</p> <p>Based on the principles of social justice, marginalized groups (e.g. roma) should also be included.</p>
Iceland	<p>On this point, the advisor focused mostly on farmers as stakeholders, while the researcher on industry (seed companies, fertilizers, dairy and meat). According to the advisor, the involvement of farmers is limited, and there is no discussion about agroecology (a bit about organic). Their involvement could be improved by educating them about agroecology, and what they could gain from adopting agroecology-based practices. According to the researchers, stakeholders (industry) are driven by profit and are active to some extent. More meetings with farmers association could be beneficial, pointing to a need for integrating the points of view of different stakeholders.</p>
Ireland	<p>There are different stakeholders that might be considered involved in sustainable agriculture and specific agroecology-based practices, but they are not explicitly involved in agroecology. For example, regarding social movements, only Talamh Beo are addressing agroecology and agroecology transition. There are others, but they are not constrained to agroecology.</p>

	<p>As part of some initiatives (e.g. EIP Agri, Signpost Programme, Farming for Nature, etc.) there are different ways of multi-actor involvement (lighthouse farms, living labs, EIP operational groups... including farmer needs on research and innovation and also on farm experimentation).</p> <p>The larger corporate stakeholders are lacking and need to be integrated into specific agroecology groups.</p> <p>A mirror group from research perspective will be organised, but also it should involve policy making. Engagement with development of CAP Strategic Plan related knowledge transfer programme, Continuing Professional Development for advisors, Innovation Hub under CAP Network.</p>
Latvia	<p>Interviewees agreed that stakeholders are organised in associations that represent their interests and that these stakeholder organisations have a relative good technical expertise. But the need for improvement was highlighted, in particular in relation to the integration of stakeholders in research programmes and their active participation in multi-stakeholder living labs. Living labs and other open innovation arrangements are rather seldomly used to foster transitions to agroecology. In the existing cases it is the leaders or managers of farmer networks and stakeholder organisations who are actively involved, but the involvement of the members was seen more of a passive nature. It was acknowledged that changing attitudes towards a more active engagement is a long term process.</p> <p>The involvement of the farming industry in the development of science and innovation by investing in private funds was seen as insufficient, and interviewees indicated the need for a greater understanding of the farming industry and increase of interest in the introduction of innovations in everyday business. This would facilitate the exchange of experiences and the development of awareness at a local level. Overall, interviews concluded that conventional farmers have less interest than the organic farmers, beekeepers and the horticulture industry. Organic farming associations are active in branding and promoting organic farming, but do not refer to agroecology (issue of terminology and understanding). At the same time it was emphasized that the agriculture sector is segregated and the involvement of regional authorities, nature protection stakeholders should also be increased.</p> <p>Improvements were suggested in relation to processes of engagement aiming to increase the involvement of stakeholders in an active dialogue. Particular reference was made to the need for improved linkages between producers and consumers and stronger involvement of consumers. Reference was made to bottom-up initiatives regarding healthy food and direct marketing of organic food products. But the current extent of these movements was seen as fairly marginal, more common amongst environmentalist. Using increasing interest in slow-</p>

	<p>food movement and locally produced food and (social) media to stimulate consumers to demand food produced through agroecological farming practices was highlighted.</p>
Lichtenstein	<p>In Lichtenstein, the stakeholder structures and organizations and their alignment with agroecology is reflected in the following statements: Stakeholders are well organised in associations that represent their interests and their associations possess a high level of technical expertise. Stakeholders' views are taken into consideration in policymaking. Stakeholder associations representing farmers have some interest in pursuing an agroecology transition. But stakeholders are less well integrated in research programmes and living labs and other open innovation arrangements are less frequently used to foster transition in Lichtenstein. Stakeholders are also not considered as actively participating in multi-stakeholder living labs.</p> <p>In Lichtenstein, there is a considerable lack of processing structures for agricultural products. Therefore, the processing of agricultural products is often outsourced to Switzerland, especially for large quantities. However, smaller product quantities with more diversity could also be produced in Lichtenstein. However, this would require structures, the majority of which would first have to be created. There are already regional products in Lichtenstein. However, they reach consumers through very different channels, such as direct sales in farm shops. Though, the offer is rather one-sided. In order for a larger range to be available, the appropriate coordination of production and processing of the products is needed. There is a need for targeted communication of agroecological aspects to the population in order to arouse interest. This can be done, for example, within the framework of events such as the "Open Farm Day".</p> <p>In Lichtenstein, mainly associations or individual farmers and extension services are involved in agroecological transition. In general, there is little effort on the part of farmers to push for adaptation to agroecology, at least not as pioneers. It is usually the municipalities that push products, such as the "lokal und fair Vaduz" label. Farmers are generally less involved and need someone to coordinate the whole thing, for example through extension.</p> <p>In Lichtenstein, agriculture should be more involved in education at schools. The topic of agriculture should be brought closer to society. In addition, consumers could be informed even more and better. The available agroecological products need better visibility. Consumers need to know that these products exist.</p> <p>Lichtenstein is affiliated with Switzerland for the production of larger goods and supplies customers in Switzerland. The produced goods then usually return to Lichtenstein on the shelves. Since the products do not return to the farmer directly, the link to the products is partially lost. Local products produced in Lichtenstein are to be preferred in this sense. However, this is only possible for small quantities.</p>

Lithuania	<p>Interviewees agreed that stakeholder organisations have a relative good technical expertise and indicated that stakeholders are to some extent organised in associations that represent their interests. But the need for improvement was highlighted, in particular also in relation to the integration of stakeholders in research programmes and their active participation in multi-stakeholder living labs.</p> <p>Agroecological initiatives are often started by research organisations or research projects. Overall, stakeholders are not substantially engaged in multi-stakeholder living labs. But in those few cases of existing living labs and other co-creation arrangements (e.g. multi-actor platforms) stakeholders participate actively. Once the new rules for research with living labs are defined by the ministry, the involvement of stakeholders is expected to increase.</p> <p>Improvements were suggested in relation to processes of engagement aiming to increase the involvement of stakeholders in an active dialogue. New mechanisms are needed to engage and link producers and consumers. Stimulating consumers to demand food produced through agroecological farming practices was highlighted as an example. A result-oriented approach was suggested to increase the involvement of farmers and uptake of agroecological practices. This would enhance the flexibility and motivation of farmers to take up such practices. Strengthening advisory services and their intermediary and facilitating role in a multi-stakeholder dialogue as well as sharing good practices, for example, through agroecological championships are further suggestions identified by the interviewees.</p>
Luxembourg	<p>In Luxembourg, national policies aim to support the following principles and practices associated with agroecological transition: “Integrated Pest Management and Biological Control”, “Diversified Crop Rotation”, “Fertiliser and Nutrient Management Efficiency”, “biodiversity preservation” and “sustainable water management” are to some or even to high extent supported by the existing policies. “Mixed cropping systems” are not supported by the existing policies at all. On the following practices, there is some disagreement among the national contact points to which extent they are supported by the policies: “wetland restoration/paludiculture”, “conservation tillage”, “circularity in biomass utilisation”, “Multi-stakeholder innovation arrangements such as living labs”.</p> <p>In Luxembourg, the most important agricultural policies are the organic action plan, concerning pest management, green deal of EU, agroecology programmes in the national law of agriculture (e.g. diversified crop management, grazing, hedges, less nitrogen fertilizer, organic farming); The most important environmental policies concern water and biodiversity management and water protection areas (e.g. farmers need to have a nutrient management plan etc.).</p> <p>The most important limitation of an agroecological transition is the</p>

	<p>market: at the moment many products are national and regional. Luxembourg supports the regional and local production but makes it difficult to support organic farming and there is no clear vision on where to go. There is also an accumulation of subsidies: sometimes you get more if you accumulate agroecology subsidies than if you would switch to organic. Moreover, the natural conservation plan defines for example that trees should be protected. This makes it harder for farmers to develop agroforestry systems because they are not allowed to really use them as such, same for structural elements. Thus, plans in the national strategic plan are often contradicting the ones in the natural conservation plan or vice versa.</p> <p>The focus in Luxembourg is on reaching the goal of 20 % organic agriculture. However, it seems more important to find out whether this is really desirable than the actual result. A holistic approach between the ministries would be desirable and that they have a consistent vision.</p>
Netherlands	<p>In the Netherlands, stakeholders are already involved e.g. through public-private research infrastructure and topsector approach. However, living labs can be expected to play an important role in the agroecological transition, because the stakeholders (retail, suppliers, etc.) are then directly involved in interaction with the farmers and the research. They have to find the solutions to questions together. We can also learn where the main bottle necks in policy are and on what scale (regional, national, EU, worldwide). Stakeholders in the Netherlands are well organised in associations that represent their interest, and they possess a high level of technical expertise. In policymaking, the stakeholders views are taken in to consideration and stakeholders are also well integrated in research programmes. However, it seems not so clear whether stakeholder associations of farmers have a strong interest in an agroecological transition. The process of agroecological transition works in circles. By involving the people / stakeholders a little bit, more people can be reached. Often, extremist positions of stakeholders are dominating the discussions, making it difficult for the policy makers to not do something. However, this is not a democratic process, when a minority of the farmers (can) do a lot. Stakeholders associations, that represent those farmers with a strong interest in agroecological transition are unfortunately less well heard than the extremist positions mentioned.</p> <p>Living labs and other open innovation arrangements are frequently used to foster an agroecological transition in the Netherlands and stakeholders are actively participating in multi-stakeholder living labs, as far as it is known. Farmers like to learn from farmers. In order to improve the involvement of stakeholders for an agroecological transition, these opportunities for farmers needs to be improved, by for example living labs. Big issue is the regional approach, which is part of the new cap program. How can the regional stakeholders be included. Suggested approaches would be to organized regional approaches, and</p>

	<p>to allocate money in a way that all stakeholders from one region are involved. Moreover, more stakeholders should be involved to foster an agroecological transition.</p> <p>Moreover, living labs are expected to play an important role in the agroecological transition, because they are involved in discussions regarding policies, research programs, etc. Still, the decision on the policies remains with the ministry. After all, the farmers have to work based on the policies. Living labs would allow to work on this issue, for example on pilot farms, where future research structures can be addressed.</p> <p>The stakeholders that are primarily involved in an agroecological transition in the Netherlands, are the farmers, the NGOs, farmer associations and the water boards.</p> <p>The stakeholders that are mostly absent in the agroecological transition are the citizens, the consumers. Social innovation is, however, only possible with the involvement of consumers. It would also be desirable to involve people in the process that have no expertise in the field of agroecology like artists, or people from the hospital, who can help to solve problems from another perspective. Moreover, nature / environmental organisations - NGOs for nature and nature management organisations - are lacking in the agroecological transitions. They are assumed to not agree with the general claim for agricultural land due to agroecological transition, that leads to a damage of natural lands.</p> <p>In the Netherlands, in the public-private approach, the supermarkets are not directly involved. They might be involved after all, but it is difficult to get them on board and have them committed to the transition.</p> <p>Moreover, on EU level as well as National level, the retailer structures and the value chains do not seem to be very flexible and ready for a transition. Fair prices for agroecological products should be aimed for. This would result in higher prices in supermarkets. So far this only feasible and accepted for organic products with their labelling. Other agroecological products like nature inclusive agriculture, resilient agriculture do not have a label. However, it is unclear whether a label would help, since consumer do often not pay attention to them. It is very important that retailers, consumers and supermarkets are involved in the agroecological transition.</p>
Norway	<p>The perception of the involvement of stakeholders and on the development of stakeholder associations with respect to agroecology related matters in Norway are rather dissimilar. Norwegian contact points do not agree on whether “stakeholder associations possess a high level of technical expertise”, and on whether “stakeholders’ views are taken into consideration in policymaking”. There is also no clear agreement in Norway on the statement “Stakeholder associations representing farmers have a strong interest in pursuing an agroecology transition” However, “stakeholders are perceived as quite well organised in associations that represent their interests”. Moreover, stakeholders are perceived as well integrated in research programmes and living labs and other open innovation arrangements are seen as</p>

	<p>rather frequently used to foster transition within Norway. The stakeholders are, however, not perceived to actively participate in multi-stakeholder living labs”. There is a need to have a public discussion on the agroecology strategy. The involvement of stakeholders for agroecological transition in Norway can be improved by for example highlighting example farms that are very good like the in the project “The young farmer of the year”. This would help to more widely spread knowledge on agroecology. Depending on where the transition should start, a bottom-up could be addressed, by having more engagement from the grass root. This requires, however, resources and incentives which is also required from above. Additionally, more cooperation would help, rather than money. Local distribution channels are an important stakeholder, that has not been considered yet. Supermarkets have their own labels and control the value chains back to the producers. For farmers it is difficult to find their way into this value chain, as there are many prerequisites, like for example, enough yield of specific crops. The value chain is not supporting the agroecological principles. The consumers want cheap food and are not ready to pay more for expensive local products, which are not sold in the super markets. A change in the food culture would be desired. People need to start caring about where the food comes from, how it is produced and what quality it has? On a daily basis the cheapest food is bought. But in discussions, the food quality does matter. Another important part of the system is represented by the consumers, as well as the farmer markets and cooperatives. Cooperatives are a very good way of including interested consumers.</p>
Poland	<p>Overall stakeholder associations in Poland were perceived as weak by both interviewees, and involvement of stakeholders was also perceived as weak.</p> <p>In addition to the overall weakness, there is a big gap in terms of consumer involvement. Beyond specific groups in urban areas, awareness of agroecology is low, and needs to be addressed through public information campaigns (although this is an important and growing demand-side, Wojtowicz).</p> <p>There is a need for more demonstration farms and living labs as the base for necessary training. Living labs should be included in higher education projects and PhD programmes. Involvement of stakeholders should be an obligatory part of research projects.</p>
Serbia	<p>The national legal framework does not stipulate directly rules on AE agricultural production, but rather there are other national laws that indirectly set the rules together with more specific organic agriculture legislation.</p> <p>The following web sites provide the source of the existing national regulations:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. National regulation on plant protection, recycling, etc.:

	<p>https://www.secpa.rs/regulativa/nacionalni-propisi</p> <p>2. National regulation on food safety: https://www.paragraf.rs/propisi/zakon_o_bezbednosti_hrane.html</p> <p>3. National organic food and agriculture regulation: ‘Production of organic products in the Republic of Serbia is regulated by the Law on Organic Production ("Official Gazette of RS", no. 30/10 and 17/2019 – Dr. Law), which came into force on 01.01.2011.[...] This law and bylaws regulate the objectives and principles of organic production, methods of organic production, control and certification, processing, marking, storage, transportation, trade, import and export of organic products. The system of control of organic products in Serbia was established according to the system of control prescribed by EU regulations, by Council Regulation (EC) No. 834/2007 and by Regulation of the Commission (EC) No. 889/2008.’ (Translated from Serbian using Google translate tool), https://serbiaorganica.info/domaci-propisi/</p> <p>The agricultural information and mobilisation of relevant agricultural community is occurring also both via the Facebook groups, and informally via specialised groups and Viber groups (invisible actors). The information about the AE is also disseminated via seminars organised by the Institute and private companies.</p> <p>The most relevant policies for the AE transition are: 1) policies regulating the state subsidies and 2) sociological aspect of rural policies (innovation) that are regulating rural life. The important support for AE transition are Green Deal targets: (i) to devote at least 25% of agricultural land under organic farming management by 2030, and significantly increase the uptake of agro-ecological practices; and (ii) to diminish the loss of nutrients from fertilizers by 50% in 2030, resulting in the reduction of the overall use of fertilizers by at least 20%, although the latter one could be considered somewhat unrealistic.</p>
Slovakia	<p>The Ministry of Economy together with its institutions are responsible for the promotion of innovation ecosystems. They should be more involved in the promotion and the coordination of agrarian research, especially in those areas that support the agroecology transition. They should provide innovative mechanisms and support schemes in order to foster cooperation among stakeholders and facilitate the exchange of know-how and practical experiences. Demonstration farms should be developed, so they could serve as a venue where “research could be linked with practice”. The lack of understanding of the concept of agroecology hinders stakeholder involvement. Therefore, awareness raising should be done through the relevant branches of the education system, and the farm advisory systems in general.</p> <p>Stakeholders need to be better engaged in the implementation of agroecology research, which is mainly practice oriented in Slovakia. The appropriate setting of eco-schemes in the next period will provide supportive context for the spread of agroecology practices through the engagement of a more diverse range of stakeholders. Living labs provide similar space for that.</p>

	<p>At this early stage, mainly NGOs and smaller, sustainable farmers are the stakeholders primarily involved in the agroecology transition. There are exemplary initiatives in the Northern part of Slovakia, with actively engaged farmers and farmers' associations, some organized producers and processors, research institutions, and engaged mayors of small towns and villages. They are still at the stage of developing a framework for their activities, and have no significant impact yet. The group of consciously and not just accidentally involved farmers is too small. If they were presented with an opportunity to verify how the promoted agroecology practices work, a wider range of farmers would get engaged in the transition. This would require financial support from the state and the engagement of NGOs and research institutions to organize venues where farmers could be informed and get engaged. Such activities are small-scale by nature at this point, and have a limited reach so far.</p>
Switzerland	<p>The opinions on stakeholder involvement with respect to agroecology related matters in Switzerland are diverging. Stakeholders are perceived on the one hand as organised in associations that represent their interests to a high extent and on the other hand to a limited extent. Stakeholder associations are generally agreed to possess a high level of technical expertise. There is some disagreement on whether stakeholders' views are taken into consideration in policymaking and on whether stakeholders are well integrated in research programmes. Stakeholder associations representing farmers in Switzerland are not perceived to have a strong interest in pursuing an agroecology transition, in general, with some exception. Living labs and other open innovation arrangements are only to a limited perceived as frequently used in Switzerland to foster transition. Stakeholders are in general seen to actively participate in multi-stakeholder living labs, but only to some extent.</p> <p>We can't really speak of a current agroecological transition in Switzerland. For sure, there are individual actors implementing practices and there is an organic movement but the involvement of stakeholders for agroecological transition should be improved. Currently, the Swiss farmer association and the Federal office of agriculture are primarily involved in agroecological transition. The Federal office of environment, health, food safety and veterinary services, however, are involved to a very limited extent. Environmental associations are relatively strong in Switzerland but they are not coming together with the other stakeholder groups which are primarily involved in agroecological transition (e.g. Swiss farm association, governmental office, etc.). Stakeholder involvement could be improved by for example creating the spaces for agroecological transitions, which are not currently there. At least, the interest is there. It is easier to convince stakeholders to participate, if discussions target specific targets/measures and processes are based on real participation. Thus, there is a need to bring all stakeholders in the agriculture and food system at the same table to discuss the system view. A strong support from the policy side of agroecology would trigger a lot in all stakeholder groups. However, the</p>

	<p>Swiss citizens are not perceived as ready for such regulations (e.g. like in France, no food waste at grocery stores, reduced plastic waste). This would require an awareness raising in all the stakeholder groups to show them the urgency of the need for transition.</p> <p>However, the risk of getting more stakeholders involved could create space for various interpretation.</p>
Turkey	<p>Stakeholders and farmers in the agricultural sector should be connected to develop agricultural model practices, including identified leading farmers, using agroecological practices in partnership with all the relevant stakeholders from the food chain. In addition, marketing processes could be improved by evaluating the outputs of these sample applications in appropriate supply chains. Farmers and farmer associations are seen as the priority stakeholder groups within the agroecological transition. Nevertheless, the pressure that comes from the consumers and citizens must also play a major role for it. Indeed, the highest amount of stakeholder groups represent the consumers which do not care so much about the technical aspects of the production, but mainly about the outcomes and the certainty of environmentally friendly farming. In general, enough experts in science are present in the country, but they are not always working in a way that farmers can use their results in an easy applicable way. Also, more projects are needed that bring together the various groups of stakeholder working on one major target. Policy-makers are not yet enough considering the interests of the stakeholders which might be directly related to financial and economic problems of the agricultural sector. Furthermore, since agroecological methods are often information and observation-intensive production methods, they are not widely used yet. The used technologies are not always completely new to the farmers, but it requires a new and different way of thinking. Of high importance is also that common work cycles and routines of agroecological farmers and growers need to be fully understood by the other stakeholders. For this purpose, the following could be done: i) pilot agroecology practices in the production areas of pioneer farmers should be developed. ii) providing practical training and consultancy to pioneer farmers willing to clean production and sales without intermediaries, ensuring the visibility of farmers, increasing the interaction between producers, consumers and NGOs including farm tours and city events. iii) awareness-raising activities: seminars, meetups and workshops on small scale farming and food communities at local level. iiiii) documentation and dissemination: providing visibility for pioneer farmers to share information on agroecology and food communities, documenting and promoting agricultural biodiversity, local varieties, traditional agricultural and culinary culture.</p>
United Kingdom	<p>There are different stakeholder groups to consider. There are groups representing overall farming interests (e.g. National Farmers' Union or National Farmers' Union Wales), as well as more specialised groups representing particular sectors (e.g. Sheeppowners Association), particular landowners (e.g. Country Land and Business Association,</p>

	<p>National Parks, National Trust), environmental conservation bodies (e.g. Royal Society for the Protection of Birds) or particular farming styles, including agroecology (e.g. Soil Association). There are significant power differences between those groups, which translates into their inclusion in research programmes. Some of these groups have a lot of expertise, but not necessarily in agroecology. In Wales, there are frequent policy consultations, so there is an opportunity to 'air views', although it is not clear how far that translates to policy. The interviewees were not very familiar with Living Labs as sites of involvement. European Innovation Partnerships were mentioned as interesting examples, however interviewees noted these mainly focused on specific and technical forms of innovation, rather than looking at holistic approaches. Defra's new Environmental Land Management policy is undertaking tests and trials which could be seen as Living Labs, but it is not clear how and if these learning cycles will continue. There is a gap in terms of stakeholder involvement in agroecological transition. That gap includes involvement with mainstream farming unions, extension services such as Farming Connect (Wales), vets' associations, food supply (processors, retailers) associations, and consumer associations.</p>
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Annex F: Policies in support of agroecology

Table 14: Partners synthesis of the interviews with respect to the entry: "*Policies in support of agroecology*".

Belgium	<p>The most influencing policy for the interviewees in agriculture is the CAP. However the interviewees indicate it doesn't support agroecology and is rather focused on agroindustry. They mention that there are also good intentions in the EU policy From Farm to Fork and the Green Deal, but there is not enough money to implement this policy. Overall in Flemish and Walloon regional policy there are no clear choices for agroecology, mostly because of the strong lobby from agro industry. Policy is often organised in separated sectors/themes (nature/environment-agriculture) and there is not always a good cooperation between these. Eg.The Flemish law about manure is not compatible with agroecology. Besides this, environmental policies are difficult to align with trade policies allowing competition with cheap food from abroad. However in Wallonia, there is some support to local agri-food dynamics // Support to organic farming // Support to advisory groups for organic farming - low till farming – feed autonomy // support to research on these different domains //eco arrangements, integrated pest management.</p>
Cyprus	<p>This question was not addressed during the interview because of the interviewee's background.</p>
Czech Rep.	<p>General comment regarding the questionnaire: One respondent argued that to say that certain practices receive low policy support could be misleading. The correct assessment of the level of support would require an understanding of how ambitious these policies are, how serious is the budget allocated to them, whether the farmers are ready to apply these practices, and the extent of their engagement. Also, it was highlighted that several of the practices (e.g.: integrated pest management, conservation tillage) are basic conditions of direct payments, hence they can't be subject to policy support - if by definition policy support would require the allocation of a budget as well. He also argued that in his definition, policy support should include a budget allocated with payments dependent on the implementation of the supported practices. He emphasized that as cross-compliance is forbidden to be paid for, the focus should be on the development of other supportive policy tools pursuing cross-compliance through practices identified to be crucial in the agroecological transition. Looking at the list of agroecological practices provided in the questionnaire in order to assess their policy support, it is clear that many of these fit into organic farming. The national policies that focus on assisting organic farming aim high, but fail to deliver. Demonstration farms, which are the closest thing to living-labs, receive some policy support, but that is not enough. Also, there are many policies that focus on environmental protection and organic farming, but they fail to mention their role in the agroecological transition. There are no policies</p>

	<p>or regulations that specifically address agroecological practices. The CAP is not designed to support the transition towards agroecology. If we focus on strengthening the social pillar of agroecology, some of the social policies originally focused on the development of the countryside could be recognized as policies with potential to promote the agroecological transition. The employment of disadvantaged people and people with diminished working abilities in agriculture is finally addressed through recent legislation. Social agriculture could be an opportunity to help small-scale farming, also to learn about and tap into these dimensions of agroecology. Other policies that work well for rural development programs could have good potential for the agroecological transition as well. Also, the implementation of the new CAP, and the integration of Farm to Fork and the Green Deal into the national policies throughout the next few years could induce some progress in this field. Farmers with an interest in intensive farming have significant influence on state level decision making. As a consequence, sustainability related issues might have been formally supported by the policies just to the extent to which EU funds could be obtained, but the will to actually implement measures to make a difference lacked true dedication. It is expected that the new government with no such direct ties to intensive farming, might be less inclined to serve its interests. However, the fact remains that the majority of agricultural land is cultivated under intensive large-scale farms. They apply significant pressure on state institutions, so they could escape the “complications” they see in these “green measures”. On the other hand, small scale farms find it difficult to have any say in national policies. The most significant limitation of the implementation of policies supportive of the agroecological transition is the dire state of social capital. Even though there is a lot of experience accumulated, which could support the implementation of such policies, the lack of communication and cooperation with and among farmers and other stakeholder groups, is the true bottleneck that needs to be addressed.</p>
Denmark	<p>All interviewees agreed that the most relevant policies are on EU level, the CAP and agricultural politics. But also, that there needs to be more incitements and monitoring. Economic support to organic farming is important as well as support to develop more plant-based food in value chains and agricultural practices.</p>
Estonia	<p>In Estonia, many agroecology-based principles and practices are supported by existing policies, such as integrated pest management and biological control, conservation tillage, diversified crop rotation, fertiliser and nutrient management efficiency, biodiversity preservation, circularity in biomass utilisation and co-creation arrangements in agriculture. Sustainable water management and wetland restoration/paludiculture is somewhat less supported. Multi-stakeholder innovation arrangements such as living labs are not at all supported by the existing policies. Regarding mixed cropping systems and cover crops, there is some disagreement by the national contact points on whether they are supported by existing policies. The organic</p>

	<p>farming action plan by government is additionally supported by the existing policies in Estonia.</p> <p>The most relevant policy for the transition towards agroecology in Estonia is the agricultural program until 2030, involving agriculture and fishery strategies as well as the new European support measures: https://www.agri.ee/en/agriculture-and-fisheries-strategy-2030).</p> <p>However, it is not clear what is directly concerning Agroecology in this action plan. Also, the new green deal and cap policies were mentioned as important, as well as organic policies. The ministries are still working on a bioeconomy strategy for Estonia.</p> <p>The most important limitations in national and European policies with respect to agroecology arise from a lack of clear targets in regard to agroecology. European policies are suggestive but not compulsory. The European monitoring system is not adapted to an Estonian context (i.e. the soil monitoring is not adapted for the very spatially heterogenic soils in Estonia). Moreover, there is not enough funding.</p> <p>European commission statements include many paradoxes and sometimes contradictions, making it difficult for farmers to understand what to do.</p> <p>Policies should support holistic agroecosystem management with sufficient support measures.</p>
Finland	<p>In general, the current policies are supporting the agroecology practices, especially conservation tillage, cover crops and sustainable water management. However, multi-stakeholder innovation arrangements such as living labs and other co-creation arrangements in agriculture (eg communities of practice, farmer field schools etc) are not supported or only to a minor extent.</p> <p>In general, both the national and the European policies are considered important, as Finland is part of the EU. Policies with a bigger impact on the structure of the food system are needed, including subsidies policies. Additionally, more regional policies are needed that recognise better the differences between the regions. The existing national subsidies and northern subsidies are paid in the central and northern regions. In the southern region there are different subsidies paid. They are focussing on maintaining the production and protecting the environment. The subsidies are hectare based. Some subsidies are animal based, where some subsidies are paid for milk litre and for cattle, sheep and goat meat, which are paid as direct subsidies. However, the livestock production should be limited to keep it sustainable, be addressing a more restricted manure management. However, as a farmer it is risky to ask for more policies, as they may lead to an increase in bureaucracy with little efficiency. Still, subsidies are all very relevant, as they are very important for the income of the farmers. The income level and economic profitability is in general low at farms. It is important that the policy supports the transition towards Agroecology. But the fact that the subsidised are tied to production area hinder change. Many farmers do not care about how they produce, as</p>

	<p>they get the subsidies anyway. Subsidies should be tied to sustainable production ways.</p> <p>The current agricultural policies maintain the current system, rather than initiating a change or a transition towards another system. A vision for a sustainable food production system in Finland is required that would enable to design policies for this vision. Moreover, policy coherency is important. Joint goals of agroecological production should be pursued and these goals should be practical for farmers.</p>
France	<p>The French government is officially supporting the transition towards agroecology. Nevertheless, often negative practices of conventional agriculture are not stopped immediately, but being extended or postponed. Very important for the development of changing policies is the European Green Deal of the EU which is forcing the member countries to end intensive agricultural practices. Beside the EU, it is mainly the consumers and citizens which are pushing the farmers towards agroecology, who consequently present their needs to the policy-makers, which then might change their policies. Additionally, science and research can play a major role in affecting and improving politics. Therefore, it is very important that research and politics are well connected, as they widely determine the practices. In France, very high on the agenda of the ministry is the protection of biodiversity, the improvement of animal welfare and the reduction of pesticides. On the political agenda there are also several problems and limitations that must be overcome. First, financial resources are not a major problem in France. However, the administrative resources and time spent (through missing manpower) to change the agricultural system is not enough. Moreover, there needs to be a better connection between the different actors and the involved ministries. Different regions with different ambitions and expertise might need decisions and laws that can easily be adapted separately. Hence, it would be useful to decentralize decision-making and act also on a regional level instead of mainly nationally. Finally, sometimes political decisions are made, but the main problem is the implementation of it. Farmers who are not convinced by agroecology yet due to missing solutions from policy and science, might prefer to stay with the status quo of conventional agriculture instead of risking a change that is not clear for them to be successful.</p>
Germany	<p>Policy support exists for a number of agroecological practices (e.g. integrated pest management, diversified crop rotation, fertiliser and nutrient management, biodiversity conservation), while for other practices such as wetland restoration and paludiculture and sustainable water management policy support was seen as limited. Also for multi-stakeholder innovation arrangements such as living labs and other co-creation arrangements in agriculture policy supported was indicated only to a limited extent.</p> <p>The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) was highlighted as the key policy with payments for organic farming, agri-environmental measures and</p>

	<p>support for knowledge exchange, awareness raising and innovation identified as important instruments for promoting a transitions towards agroecology. In addition to support payments for good practices interviewees also highlighted the important role of regulations as a driver for innovation by banning bad, or regulating potentially harmful, practices, e.g. the use of pesticides. Also the role of key policy strategies such as Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategies and at national level also the Sustainable Development Strategy and National Bioeconomy Strategy was highlighted.</p> <p>Regarding limitations in national and European policies interviewees suggested a lack of policy support to establish sustainable technologies (e.g. establishment of no or reduced tillage) and policy changes with negative impacts on local small-scale producers, e.g. increased hygiene regulations for dairy production which forced local (and small) cheese producers out of the market increasing market concentration of few large producers. In addition, it was pointed out that direct payments paid according to agricultural area instead of being targeted to sustainable land use hinder a transition to agroecology.</p> <p>Interviewees emphasised the need for a more comprehensive approach in policy integrating a food systems approach into the policies to address the complexities of, and linkages between, sustainable production and consumption. Further the importance of capacity building for policy stakeholders was highlighted with reference being made to the role of the candidate partnership on agroecology at EU level in strengthening the science-society-policy dialogue.</p>
Hungary	<p>Relevant practices that receive policy support to some extent</p> <p>There were some specific calls for the development of short supply chains and local market development in general. These aimed to engage not just farmers, but SMEs and NGOs as well.</p> <p>Ex situ and in situ heritage seed preservation (to some extent)</p> <p>Extensive grazing is an exemplary practice with clear policy support behind it</p> <p>Even though classical agroforestry is mostly overlooked, some related agroecological practices, such shelter belts, and wooded pastures that enjoy policy support</p> <p> Policymakers should recognize agrarian research and its innovations as tools not just to inform their policies but to support their implementation</p> <p>Many of the agroecological practises that currently characterise the Hungarian agroecology sector were developed through a bottom-up</p>

	<p>approach, mainly by NGOs without significant policy or financial support (such as the promotion of short value chains, producer markers, consumer associations). Farmers should receive training so they could learn how to participate in them.</p> <p>The relevant policies address a range of agroecological practices, one by one. By doing so they fail to address the agroecology transition systematically, which would require coordinated efforts. This is just another evidence that there is a lack of understanding of the nature of the concept of agroecology, and a lack of understanding of how policies should address the transition. Decision makers rarely consult with a wide range of stakeholders when deciding on policies. Therefore, the needs and opinions of important stakeholders (NGOs, farmers, universities etc.) are missing from their considerations. There is a lack of willingness to accept this newly introduced concept (questioning its economic feasibility) and take steps to provide financial support for it, to promote it or to legitimize it. Policy makers fail to keep up with the NGOs and research organizations that are actively addressing certain aspects of the agroecology transition. It is due to the lack of commitment on behalf of the government to assist the agroecology transition. Even if/when the policymakers' priorities fall in line with the principles of agroecology, it is hard to predict if their efforts to implement the new legislation, regulations they develop could actually make a difference. It is not entirely in their control the nature and extent of changes they induce, and they might not reach the desired effect.</p> <p>Policy makers prioritize the interests of the large-scale, intensive farms, where the practices of agroecology are perceived to be a hard fit. The lack of support of crop rotation in favor of the four major grains, the lack of support of sustainable water management in favor of irrigated arable lands, and the lack of protection of ecologically more valuable land types in favor of arable lands shows that the agrarian policies are dedicated to support the status quo, which is the most significant barrier of the agroecological transition.</p> <p>The current EU subsidy system delays the agroecological transition, because farmers get paid in order to produce something, instead of being motivated to engage in certain ways of land management by linking payments to support their efforts. They could be motivated to contribute to the agroecological transition this way. It will be difficult to shift attitudes to accept such changes as the current subsidy structure has been around for decades.</p> <p>During the last CAP 2014-2020 cycle in Hungary, two programs could be considered as programs that actually helped farmers to implement agroecological practices. These were the Agricultural and Environmental Management program and the Organic Farming Conversion Support</p>
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	<p>Mechanism. In the new CAP cycle, the previously mentioned two programs will be complemented with a new Agroecological Target program which will be focusing explicitly on benefitting agroecological practices. Also, the new Action Plan on the Development of Organic Agriculture considers agroecology as a synergistic concept and practice and sets the national target to join and co-fund the future European Partnership on Agroecology and to establish three agroecology living labs and five agroecological research infrastructure in Hungary by 2027. Besides this, there is no other policy or strategy considering agroecology in Hungary.</p>
Iceland	<p>There are no national policies about specific agroecological practices. Both interviewees pointed out that the new government wants to support sustainable practices, and carbon neutrality is a big goal. A new national policy may come up, setting an aim for increasing organic production (but organic farmers are concerned about not getting enough support for the transition). Regarding European policies, the researcher's opinion is that GMOs and all the available technology should be used to reach ambitious sustainability goals.</p>
Ireland	<p>Both interviewees agreed that national policies in Ireland are promoting specific agroecological-based practices associated with agroecological transition, from a limited extent to a high extent specific. However, there is no agreement about the degree of development of the different supporting initiatives.</p> <p>Interviewees mentioned the following programmes and schemes that can be considered as enablers of agroecology: EIP-AGRI Schemes, LEADER programme, DAFM Research Programme, Teagasc Signpost Farms, Teagasc Signpost programme. CAP RDP Knowledge transfer groups. Multistakeholder innovation included in last covered by EIP operational groups. LIFE funded projects involve co-creation and multi-actor approach.</p> <p>The most relevant policies mentioned are: Food Vision 2030 – the national 10-year strategy for the agri-food sector in Ireland (https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/c73a3-food-vision-2030-a-world-leader-in-sustainable-food-systems/); Bioeconomy – for the developments of the circular economy, reduction and valorisation of waste; National Climate Action Plan – linked to Climate Action Act that have legally binding targets for GHG emission reductions for all sectors of the Irish economy; AgClimatise – specific actions and targets for the agri-food sector linked to the National Climate Action Plan for climate change mitigation, adaptation; National pollinator plan, Biodiversity Strategy 2030, Farm-to-Fork Strategy.</p> <p>The most critical limitations detected by the interviewees are: Knowledge, Education, Training & Skills as well as the limited integration of agroecology into mainstream policies, schemes and services. Lack of understanding of the concept and considerable overlap between</p>

	<p>different concepts e.g., regenerative agriculture, organics, sustainable agriculture and agroecology. Environment legislation and policy seen as restrictions and constraining food production. Need to get to point where the environment and good ecological condition and functioning ecosystems are seen as the foundation of and integral to or food production system.</p> <p>As a general reflection, one of the interviewees mentioned that there is a widespread belief in agriculture industry circles that there is nothing wrong with the conventional systems and that they are essential to feeding a growing world population. Combining this with a lack of clear description and vision of what an agroecological agricultural sector would look like means it is not on the policy/industry radar in Ireland. There is a narrative that we need to switch to a more sustainable system but this is poorly defined apart from incremental improvements to conventional system. Economic consideration overrule social and environmental considerations.</p>
Latvia	<p>Policy support exists for a number of agroecological practices (e.g. diversified crop rotation, fertiliser and nutrient management), while for other practices such as circularity in biomass utilisation and wetland management support was seen as weaker or not existent. for multi-stakeholder innovation arrangements such as living labs and other co-creation arrangements in agriculture was seen as weaker.</p> <p>The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) was highlighted as the key policy and interviewees agreed that within the CAP payments for organic farming, agri-environmental measures and eco schemes are key instruments. But uncertainty about benefits of eco schemes for a transition towards agroecology and a risk of “greenwashing” were expressed, too.</p> <p>Important limitations in national policies are an insufficient budget and a lack of targeting interventions towards key barriers of transitions to agroecology (e.g. knowledge gaps, lower profitability of agroecological farming). Interviewees saw scope provided by the European policy framework to better target national policies. Interviewees also suggested to strengthen policy support for knowledge generation and diffusion on agroecology including enabling advisory services to consult farmers more broadly regarding the whole farm ecosystem. Interviewees also highlighted the importance of improving impact monitoring to provide robust evidence for future policy support for agroecological practices.</p>
Lichtenstein	<p>In Lichtenstein, even though agroecology-based practices are common, this is not much reflected in existing policies. Only cover crops are supported by the policies to some extent. All the other agroecology-based practices are neutrally or to a limited extent supported. At best, new forms of support could be established to promote agroecology. Local products could be promoted. In addition, it may</p>

	<p>make sense to provide support not only in the form of a financial contribution per area and per animal, but also in the form of targeted support for projects and structures that promote agroecology.</p> <p>In Lichtenstein, the "Agricultural Policy Report" is published regularly. In it, a description of the current orientation of agriculture can be found, which is pursued by agriculture. Agroecology could also be described there. However, a state-imposed agroecology makes little sense. The orientation of agriculture from above is not very desirable. Rather, the orientation of agriculture should be discussed and decided in a participatory manner, together with interest groups.</p> <p>The main constraints in national and European policies related to agroecology are different: European agricultural policy is very different from national agricultural policy in terms of structural differences, but also in terms of interests and orientation of agriculture. It seems difficult to find a common denominator. European policy is sometimes perceived as restrictive.</p> <p>The constraints at national political level are the strong roots in the existing dairy industry and in arable farming. In order to achieve a change, larger value chain structures would have to be broken up. However, this cannot happen overnight. The farms have grown over the years. A transition to agroecology takes time in Lichtenstein. Various initiatives and projects (e.g. "Liveable Lichtenstein", which are active in the areas of cereals, legumes and local marketing) can lead the way here.</p>
Lithuania	<p>Policy support exists for a number of agroecological practices (e.g. cover crops, fertiliser and nutrient management, biodiversity preservation – grassland management), while support for multi-stakeholder innovation arrangements such as living labs and other co-creation arrangements in agriculture was seen as weaker.</p> <p>Key policies are the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and environmental policies. Within the CAP agri-environmental measures and eco schemes are seen as key instruments and beyond the CAP environmental regulations, e.g. on manure and fertiliser management, were highlighted.</p> <p>Changes in the design of policy instruments were seen as important aspects of successfully promoting a transition to agroecology. Currently, agri-environmental measures and other CAP instruments do not provide a sufficient incentives to mainstream agroecology. More flexibility for farmers to achieve the desired environmental outcomes, shorter contract periods and less bureaucracy were suggested as improvements. Interviews further agreed that the payment levels are too low to incentivise a transition to agroecological practices. In some cases, definitions of eligibility criteria are detrimental to environmental objectives. For example, grazing land is only eligible for payment without shrubs, yet, it was argued, provides suitable areas for grazing,</p>

	<p>which deliver biodiversity benefits.</p> <p>The importance of long-term funding strategies for living labs was highlighted. Financial support and funding rules are needed that reflect a long term investment in open innovation arrangements.</p>
Luxembourg	<p>In Luxembourg, the opportunities for a transition towards agroecology-based practices and research infrastructures are seen as limited. Current national policies are not sufficiently fostering agroecological transition. Moreover, resource allocations and advisory systems do not support agroecological transition. The current organization of the food market does not support agroecological initiatives and the underlying values of the current agriculture and food production system do not sufficiently foster an agroecological transition. Current European policies are seen as fostering for agroecological transition.</p> <p>The most important barrier for an agroecological transition is the market situation and the prizes the consumers have to pay. Moreover, research resources are seen as barriers as well as the national priorities. For farmers, changing to agroecology does not seem to be economic, yet. Moreover, funding, knowledge and competencies regarding agroecology are still missing in scientific institutions, and farmers are rather conservative and not ready to change.</p> <p>There is a new agricultural regulation in Luxembourg, which is only allowing subsidies for bio-ready or climate-ready farms. This is, however, not yet implemented. Moreover, Luxembourg is trying to reduce soybean imports, but the vision on how it will be done is still lacking.</p> <p>The light houses are the peer-to-peer learnings, which are most effective. Moreover, there are indicators showing that agroecology actually has effects for example on biodiversity which would also potentially allow for financial support to farmers using such measures.</p>
Netherlands	<p>The policies should all aim for a transition towards agroecology. So far, the majority of the listed agroecology based practices are supported by the policies. Only mixed cropping is less supported, yet.</p> <p>For transition it is important to look at all the relevant policies that are important for a transition towards agroecology. That is not only on National scale. Several policies are on EU level that can be difficult to find solutions on a regional scale. Moreover, there is a lot asked from the farmers by the different National and EU policies, climate mitigation, biodiversity improvement, water-management. It would be important to see if the different policies are in agreement with each other. Moreover, agriculture is desired to become circular. Thus, for the transitions towards agroecology, the circular agriculture policy is most relevant as well as the European cap policy (common agriculture policy). Further policies towards agroecology are the “nitrogen law”, the “European law”, as well as the “water framework” and biodiversity regulations. However, the Dutch policies on nitrogen management are also seen as contra productive for the soil.</p>

	<p>The most important limitations in national and European policies are the economic aspects and the labour aspects. There are a lot of limiting factors for farmers and their work: on the one hand the supermarket with their requirements and conditions and on the other hand the wider variety of policies, but also the soil prices are high with a growing population and not more land. These non-technical aspects have to be considered, as for transition towards agroecology. Another limiting aspect is the resource allocation. Yet, the resources and the allocation of them do not support the agroecology in a way that it can become mainstream.</p> <p>For policies to be effective and adaptable for farmers, they should be stable and predictive. There is a lot asked from the farmers by the policies, on the national and also on EU level. It would be important that the different policies are in agreement with each other.</p>
Norway	<p>The policies are slightly ahead of the implementation of the practices. Partly due to the economy of the farmers. In general, the current policies are supporting the agroecology practices, especially cover crops and fertilizer and nutrient management efficiency. Regarding integrated pest management and biological control, conservation tillage, mixed cropping systems, diversified crop rotation, biodiversity preservation, circularity in biomass utilisation, wetland restoration/paludiculture, sustainable water management, multi-stakeholder innovation arrangements such as living labs, and other co-creation arrangements in agriculture (eg communities of practice, farmer field schools etc), the opinions are rather different. The majority of the national contact points see these practices as supported by the policies to some extent and others to a limited extent. This might be explained by the fact that Norway is very diversified. Thus, there are subsidies to support environmental development in the different regions. These subsidies are different in the different regions according to the conditions in the regions and the local government can decide. Integrated pest management and biological control in fruit and greenhouse is supported by policies to a high extent; the others, like cereals, vegetables not so much. Agroecology is not so clearly defined, therefore, it is difficult to say how it can be supported? It is easier to support agroecological techniques. Social aspects should be integrated in the policies, but what would they mean – maybe Cooperatives? Agricultural policies could go towards small farms again and support more local products like local cheese production. also the development of organic farming should be supported, especially since many organic farms have social experiments on their farms. After all, there a lot of different single policies already existing. But the most relevant policy is still lacking: the policy that balances the trade-offs of Agroecology and that ties everything together.</p> <p>The European policies take more advanced goals then the policies in Norway. Moreover, it is important that policies that are supporting knowledge on a holistic farm perspective.</p> <p>The most important limitations in national and European policies is the</p>

	<p>emphasize on the competition situation for food and the race for cheap food. Moreover, the focus on volume and low cost food are important limitations. Many actors in the food system are most concerned to produce as much food as possible for low costs to survive as a business in the system. Moreover, farmer need to earn enough also if the agroecological practices are applied. The goal should not be to have large farms. A concentration of for example many animals should be avoided. A stronger policy supporting Agroecology (food, environment, climate...) in general is needed. It is a process to increase the consciousness for the concept of agroecology in Norway. The consciousness for agroecology practices is there already, however, there is a need for an improve regarding the holistic thinking.</p>
Poland	<p>Overall the interviewees saw agroecology policies as coming exclusively from the EU's conservation or ecological policies. However, the main EU agricultural policy instrument, ie the CAP, is not helping to support organic or sustainable farming systems in Poland.</p> <p>Changing the subsidy system was seen by both interviewees as the most powerful mechanism for driving the transition. Current subsidy structures have had negative ecological outcomes, for example driving farmers to reduce tree and shrub cover. Water Boards (Spółki Wodne) have been legally allowed to reduce buffer zones by watercourses and ditches without farmers' or land managers' consent. The so-called 'revitalisation' of banks and watercourses was funded from EU funds, and has actually produced increases of nitrates and phosphates in the water. This is an example of how mis-management of subsidies can lead to powerful negative ecological effects in Poland. This needs to be reversed.</p> <p>Some national policies could be aligned with agroecological goals. For example Polski Ład, which is an economic development policy programme, could be used to strengthen shorter supply chains, small food businesses, and to introduce greater food chain transparency through digital tools.</p>
Serbia	<p>AE methods that are tailored-made for local/regional needs.</p>
Slovakia	<p>There are several policy fields where policies not directly aimed to promote agroecology incidentally support the agroecology transition. The two most significant fields in this sense are sustainable land management and organic farming (e.g.: the promotion of specific crop rotation methods, green fertilization, and the introduction of mechanical, physical and biological methods for plant protection). The extension of organic farming through supporting policies simultaneously develops agroecology.</p> <p>There are two limiting factors that hinders the effectiveness of policies that could support the agroecology transition: the difficulty of understanding the CAP and its structure in general, and the limited availability of financial sources linked to policies that could support the</p>

	<p>transition. There is also a critical shortage of available labor and other economic factors required for the implementation of the policies in support of the agroecology transition.</p> <p>There should be more EU initiatives in which state institutions could engage, which would allow them to improve their competences required to support the agroecology transition.</p> <p>The most relevant policies for the transition towards agroecology are the following:</p> <p>The CAP (mostly those parts that focus on biodiversity preservation, circularity in biomass utilization, sustainable water management and nature-friendly forest management) and the Regional Development Program with its relevant measures and payments.</p> <p>National Strategy for the Protection of Biodiversity.</p> <p>Greener Slovakia – Strategy of the Environmental Policy of the Slovak Republic until 2030 (Objectives: Supporting more environmentally friendly practices in agriculture Stopping the loss of biodiversity - By 2030, at least 15% of degraded ecosystems in Slovakia, such as the upper boundary of the forest, especially salt marshes, wetlands, peatbogs and lowland forest, which have been significantly affected by human activity will be restored)</p> <p>Action Plan to Address the Consequences of Drought and Water Scarcity (Objectives: By 2030, ensure sustainable food production systems and implement resilient agricultural practices that increase productivity and production, which will help preserve ecosystems and progressively improve soil quality.)</p> <p>National Action Plan to Achieve Sustainable Use of Plant Protection 2021-2025, REV. 2 (The use of pesticides for plant protection can be successful only if it is properly complemented by other means of regulation within an integrated plant protection system.)</p> <p>Low-carbon development strategy of the Slovak Republic until 2030 with a view to 2050 (https://www.minzp.sk/klima/nizkoughlikova-strategia/)</p> <p>Adaptation Strategy of the Slovak Republic on Adverse Impacts of Climate Change (https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/repository/11273729.pdf)</p> <p>Slovak Agenda 2030, SDGs priorities (http://socisdg.com/en/blog/slovak-sdg-priorities/)</p>
Switzerland	<p>In Switzerland, agroecology is reflected in existing policies in general to a high extent. National policies aim to support the majority of the following principles and practices associated with agroecological</p>

transition: integrated pest management and biological control, conservation tillage, diversified crop rotation, cover crops, fertiliser and nutrient management efficiency, biodiversity preservation, wetland restoration/paludiculture, sustainable water management, multi-stakeholder innovation arrangements such as living labs and other co-creation arrangements in agriculture. Only mixed cropping systems and circularity in biomass utilisation are less supported by policies.

In Switzerland, there is not one specific way of agricultural production that is fostered by the policies but rather many different ways are fostered. Switzerland is quite diverse in that way which can be seen as a limitation but also an opportunity, as it mirrors the diversity in Swiss agriculture. In general, the standard on Swiss farms, needs to increase. However, no specific agroecology policy is planned, but rather the implementation of the principles in existing and future policies. This allows for a broader application of these principles.

Direct payments and all measures linked to this are very important to drive on-farm management practices – so if we can connect agricultural policies and direct payments to agroecological principles the leverage points on-farm are tackled. However, in addition to this, the landscape approach from an agroecological perspective are key and necessary. In Switzerland, several policies and strategies are considered as relevant for agroecological transitions (e.g. agricultural policy, sustainable development strategy, biodiversity strategy, landscape concept Switzerland, climate strategy, environmental goals for agriculture (UZL), action plan for plant protection products; Legislation: Agriculture act / DZV; Environmental legislation; Nature and culture heritage protection act). However, a focus should be on the reduction of pesticide and fertiliser use. But also animal welfare policies are important to include (grazing management, manure management, crop residues and animal health). Also agroecology themes such as gender, youth equity etc. should be encompassed.

The most important limitations in national and European policies with respect to agroecology in Switzerland concern incentives in agricultural policy that are harmful to the environment and biodiversity. But also a lack of discussion of trade-offs in and between policies are limiting, as well as a lack of SMART agroecological objectives in the agricultural policy. A lack of financial and human resources for environmental protection, resource conservation and biodiversity promotion is also limiting. Another limiting aspect is the huge power concentration of big agri-business and its related actors, who are not interested in an agroecological transition because then they would become obsolete. Moreover, there is no coherence check on policies if they are supporting or hindering agroecological principles to be fulfilled. There needs to be a rigorous check if policies whether they hinder or help all agroecological principles. Additionally, the policies are not yet linked strong enough with the ecological performance measures. But a market-based approach is not enough, we need to better internalize the environmental and social costs of farming – and agroecological

	<p>principles can help identify impacts areas to measure/include these externalities, and building on the benefits of agroecology for all systems (environ, social, etc.).</p> <p>After all, it is about the understanding of agroecology – in the last 30-40 years it was based more on ecological principles applied to agriculture, now it is shifting. And it's a long way to go.</p>
Turkey	<p>Agricultural policy should be directed towards adding more value through the sustainable use of natural resources, aiming to increase agricultural productivity rather than simply supporting the production. The re-orientation of agricultural policies should enable producers to react flexibly to market conditions. It should be focused on policies for programs such as payments and subsidies to support organic farming, good farming practices and land conservation to develop an environmentally friendly agricultural sector. The most appropriate agricultural support policies are so far: i) a balanced and environmentally compatible infrastructure that aims to protect natural resources and is contributing to environmental management and quality. ii) increasing the quality and efficiency in production. iii) improving living standards of farmers by increasing income.</p> <p>Nevertheless, for several practices and agroecological principles there are no rules, laws or regulations so far. While there are for IPM and biological control, also due to demand from abroad which increases export rates, there are none for e.g. diversified crop rotation or cover crops. Often there are advices giving to the farmers by the ministries, but farmers are not bound to these. Therefore, most farmers ignore these advices. As mentioned before, it is not just a political issue, but especially science needs to provide better and more innovative solutions to convince the farmers beside political regulations.</p>
United Kingdom	<p>The UK is undergoing a big policy shift due to Brexit. Cross-compliance regulations are being replaced with the Environmental Land Management schemes (ELMs), which have an overall much greater emphasis on environmental outcomes ('public goods') than previous policies. Sustainable Farming Incentive will also be relevant, this is now in pilot stage (https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/sustainable-farming-incentive-scheme-pilot-launch-overview/sustainable-farming-incentive-defras-plans-for-piloting-and-launching-the-scheme). Water is already a strongly regulated area, especially in terms of the link between water pollution and fertilisation. Other relevant policies include : environmental impact assessments which regulate the change of land use; the Glastir agri-environmental scheme (Wales only, see https://gov.wales/glastir). There are also voluntary codes such as Woodland Carbon Code, Peatland Code. Policies associated with the Net Zero government strategy could also be relevant. There is a lot of recognition of the need for farmer involvement and co-creation, as exemplified by such schemes as the Farming Innovation Pathways (https://apply-for-innovation-</p>

funding.service.gov.uk/competition/852/overview). A challenge and limitation is 'a change in mindset' from production-focus to holistic approaches with lower inputs and lower impacts. Knowledge transfer and exchange need to play a key role. One big issue with current policies such as ELMs is that they do not take the market-level approach, i.e. they focus on changing production practices, but without creating supportive market conditions. As a result farmers in the UK will suffer a 'double whammy' of environmental policies and market competition. ELMs are also not agroecology in a different guise – their approach is incremental, and production is still the central value. AE4EU: Scotland is seeing a very strong drive on net zero policies. A number of farming groups are using this focus to direct attention to land use. Agroecology is now a term heard in policy, even if it is still not well understood. The work on water pollution has

5. References

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